

207 Magic Squares in Honor of the 138th Anniversary of S. Ramanujan with Hardy-Ramanujan Number 1729

Site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17312>

138th Birth Anniversary of S. Ramanujan,
December 22, 1887-April 26, 1920
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Abstract

*This work brings magic squares connected with S. Ramanujan's life and with Hardy-Ramanujan number 1729. On December 22, 2025 there is 138th anniversary of S. Ramanujan. This work brings magic squares of orders 3 to 20 with magic sum either 1729 or multiple of 1729. This number is famous in the literature as Hardy-Ramanujan Number. The special entries, such as, 2212, 1887, 2025 and 138 are considered in every magic square. There are total 207 different magic squares. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares. These type of magic squares are recently studied by the author [16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The advantage of **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares is that they allow us to choose entries as well as magic sum of our choice. Sometimes, we may call them as **self-made** magic squares.*

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1 Introduction

This work brings magic squares connected with S. Ramanujan's life and with Hardy-Ramanujan number 1729. On December 22, 2025 there is 138th anniversary of S. Ramanujan. This work brings magic squares of orders 3 to 15 and order 19 having magic sum as 1729. Some special entries, such as 2212, 1887, 2025 and 138 are considered. These represents date of birth of S. Ramanujan 22.12.1887 and 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. Total there 207 different magic squares. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27]. The advantage of **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares is that they allow us to choose entries as well as magic sum of our choice. Sometimes, we may call it as **self-made** magic squares. The table below give the details of in numbers of each order magic squares studied in this work:

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Total
3	1	1	2
4	2	0	2
5	2	1	3
6	5	1	6
7	8	3	11
8	8	2	10
9	15	8	23
10	16	11	27
11	28	23	51
12	23	12	35
13	3	0	3
14	5	0	5
15	6	0	6
16	4	0	4
17	3	0	3
18	8	0	8
19	3	0	3
20	5	0	5

There are total 207 magic squares of orders 3 to 20 studied in this work. All the magic squares brings the four special entries, i.e., 2212, 1887, 2025 and 138. All the magic squares are with magic sum Hardy-Ramanujan number 1729 or the multiples of 1729.

2 Magic Squares of Order 3

Let's consider following two magic squares of order 3 having the magic sum 1729:

1	mgc				1729	2	semi				8445
	2212	1887	-2370	1729		2212	-2370	1887	1729		
	-4005 2/3	576 1/3	5158 1/3	1729		-2508	4533	-296	1729		
	3522 2/3	-734 1/3	-1059 1/3	1729		2025	-434	138	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		6883

• **Details**

Above there are two magic squares of order 3. The first one is magic square, while the second one is *semi-magic*. Both are with magic sum 1729. The difference is that the first is with fractional entries, while second one is with normal entries. The first is only with two numbers 2212 and 1887, while the second one is with all the four special entries, i.e., 2212, 1887, 2025 and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on *reduced-entry algebraic* magic squares recently studied by the author [16, 18]

3 Magic Squares of Order 4

Let’s consider following two magic squares of order 4 in two different having the magic sums 1729 and 2×1729 :

4x4	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	4x4	mgc				1729
1729	2212	1887	2025	-4395	1729		2212	1887	-2384	14	1729
1729	138	-2508	325	3774	1729		2025	138	17	-451	1729
1729	-1160.5	5259.5	-1347.5	-1022.5	1729		-2000	2206	-632	2155	1729
	539.5	-2909.5	726.5	3372.5	1729		-508	-2502	4728	11	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

4x4	pan	3458	3458	3458	3458	4x4	mgc				3458
3458	-187	2212	-158	1591	3458		-4415	2212	1887	3774	3458
3458	1916	-483	1887	138	3458		6144	-483	-158	-2045	3458
3458	1887	138	1916	-483	3458		2025	138	3961	-2666	3458
	-158	1591	-187	2212	3458		-296	1591	-2232	4395	3458
	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

• **Details**

Above there are two examples magic squares of order 4 with magic sum 1729. The first example is in two different ways. First one is *pandiagonal*, but having decimal entries. The second way is not *pandiagonal* but don’t require decimal entries. This example is also written in two parts. Both are with two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×4 . Here the magic sum is 2×1729 . This we have considered to avoid decimal entries. The magic rectangles sums are as follows:

-187	2212	-158	1591	3458	-4415	2212	1887	3774	3458
1916	-483	1887	138	3458	6144	-483	-158	-2045	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
1887	138	1916	-483	3458	2025	138	3961	-2666	3458
-158	1591	-187	2212	3458	-296	1591	-2232	4395	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	

Some times these magic squares are called as *striped* magic squares. The construction of these magic squares is based on *reduced-entry algebraic* magic squares recently studied by the author [17]

4 Magic Squares of Order 5

Let's consider following three magic squares of order 5 having the magic sum 1729:

5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	2	mgc				1729	3	semi					-428	
1729	21	2212	-2421	1887	30	1729		3998	-1685	-2010	1982	-556	1729		138	1489	-902	985	19	1729
1729	-2131	2025	1948	138	-251	1729		-5907	101	6109	19	1407	1729		1694	3897	-1483	-1808	-571	1729
1729	2065	-2325	39	-1993	3943	1729		2212	1887	-3796	138	1288	1729		936	-5503	202	5907	187	1729
1729	177	-75	4060	-398	-2035	1729		-2611	2025	2725	713	-1123	1729		14	2212	1887	-3493	1109	1729
	1597	-108	-1897	2095	42	1729		4037	-599	-1299	-1123	713	1729		-1053	-366	2025	138	985	1729
1	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

• **Details**

Above there are three examples magic squares of order 5 with magic sum 1729. The first example is a *pandiagonal*. The second example is a *cornered* magic square having magic square of order 3 at the upper-left corner. The third example is a single-digit bordered *semi-magic* square. All 3 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on *reduced-entry algebraic* magic squares recently studied by the author [16, 18].

5 Magic Squares of Order 6

Let's consider following six magic squares of order 6 having the magic sum 1729:

1	mgc						1729	2	mgc							3458
	77	13	16	20	24	1579	1729		2212	-2370	1887	6614	-4907	22	3458	
	-2436	2212	17	21	1887	28	1729		3273	-1370	-174	-4904	4951	1682	3458	
	4055	-4544	2025	138	26	29	1729		-3756	5469	16	19	1685	25	3458	
	10	3541	-1902	23	27	30	1729		28	1667	34	2025	-434	138	3458	
	11	15	1554	2758	-2640	31	1729		1670	-1599	1658	-339	526	1542	3458	
	12	492	19	-1231	2405	32	1729		31	1661	37	43	1637	49	3458	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	

3	mgc							5187
	1018	2212	22	23	1887	25	5187	
	711	-483	1707	1706	-158	1704	5187	
	26	27	28	-1061	6138	29	5187	
	1703	1702	1701	2790	-4409	1700	5187	
	-926	2025	3886	31	138	33	5187	
	2655	-296	-2157	1698	1591	1696	5187	
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	

4	mgc							5187
	11	1718	2212	29	1887	-670	5187	
	14	1715	-483	1700	-158	2399	5187	
	17	1712	-7601	35	10986	38	5187	
	20	1709	9330	1694	-9257	1691	5187	
	5102	-3373	2025	-6482	7777	138	5187	
	23	1706	-296	8211	-6048	1591	5187	
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	

5	mgc							1729
	2212	407	-3900	1887	1110	13	1729	
	12	2025	138	-1569	1109	14	1729	
	1886	2085	-3642	277	1108	15	1729	
	-3504	-3911	8010	11	1107	16	1729	
	1105	-7698	1104	4464	1103	1651	1729	
	18	8821	19	-3341	-3808	20	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

6	semi							819
	928	734	-1368	709	708	18	1729	
	-1135	2212	800	-3898	1887	1863	1729	
	713	14	2025	138	-1176	15	1729	
	712	1884	2085	-3247	279	16	1729	
	711	-3109	-3909	8008	11	17	1729	
	-200	-6	2096	19	20	-200	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

• **Details**

Above there are six examples magic squares of order 6 with magic sum 1729. The first example is a normal magic square of order 6. The second example is with four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3.

semi				-3239	semi				4992
2212	-2370	1887	1729	6614	-4907	22	1729		
3273	-1370	-174	1729	-4904	4951	1682	1729		
-3756	5469	16	1729	19	1685	25	1729		
1729	1729	1729	858	1729	1729	1729	11590		
semi				-1534	semi				707
28	1667	34	1729	2025	-434	138	1729		
1670	-1599	1658	1729	-339	526	1542	1729		
31	1661	37	1729	43	1637	49	1729		
1729	1729	1729	-1534	1729	1729	1729	2600		

The third and fourth examples are with magic rectangles. See below the magic sums of these magic rectangles:

1018	2212	22	23	1887	25	5187
711	-483	1707	1706	-158	1704	5187
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
26	27	28	-1061	6138	29	5187
1703	1702	1701	2790	-4409	1700	5187
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
-926	2025	3886	31	138	33	5187
2655	-296	-2157	1698	1591	1696	5187
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

			2212	29	1887	-670	3458
11	1718	1729	-483	1700	-158	2399	3458
14	1715	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
17	1712	1729	-7601	35	10986	38	3458
20	1709	1729	9330	1694	-9257	1691	3458
5102	-3373	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
23	1706	1729	2025	-6482	7777	138	3458
5187	5187		-296	8211	-6048	1591	3458
			1729	1729	1729	1729	

The fifth one is *cornered* magic square of order 6. The the last example is a *single-digit bordered semi-magic* square of order 6.

All 6 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on reduced-entry algebraic magic squares recently studied by the author [17, 18].

6 Magic Squares of Order 7

Let's consider following 11 magic squares of order 7 having the magic sum 1729:

► First-Type

1	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	796	2212	-368	798	797	1887	-4393	1729
	23	22	1186	20	21	5211	-4754	1729
	1642	-824	-8	50	51	1071	-253	1729
	-1207	2025	90	31	-28	138	680	1729
	792	26	11	12	70	18	800	1729
	4083	5218	1198	14	15	-8815	16	1729
	-4400	-6950	-380	804	803	2219	9633	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

2	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	3	29	31	-826	1764	31	697	1729
	49	21	-7	2212	-1274	1887	-1159	1729
	11	13	39	21	917	35	693	1729
	3969	17	-2579	469	-875	-170	898	1729
	-3031	921	3517	-875	469	37	691	1729
	8511	2025	27	-8881	138	364	-455	1729
	-7783	-1297	701	9609	590	-455	364	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

3	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	1887	1178	-1104	-779	19	24	504	1729
	-2273	-8	50	51	3381	25	503	1729
	3622	90	31	-28	-2514	1218	-690	1729
	14	11	12	70	1094	26	502	1729
	-2049	-70	2212	1887	-779	27	501	1729
	1121	2025	-1986	22	138	264	145	1729
	-593	-1497	2514	506	390	145	264	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

4	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	21	2212	-3649	1887	30	57	1171	1729
	-2131	33	4042	36	-1479	60	1168	1729
	4057	-3655	39	-3985	4045	2824	-1596	1729
	-1815	27	4060	366	-2137	63	1165	1729
	369	1884	-3991	2197	42	66	1162	1729
	3175	2025	-2322	138	54	614	-1955	1729
	-1947	-797	3550	1090	1174	-1955	614	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5	7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
	1729	2611	-4018	2212	16	15	1887	-994	1729
	1729	-1967	-2673	12	2025	138	4165	29	1729
	1729	-2422	7146	1988	1077	-6116	26	30	1729
	1729	3441	2179	-2525	-1446	22	27	31	1729
	1729	-4539	-5956	13	18	7623	4538	32	1729
	1729	4540	6042	14	19	23	-8942	33	1729
		65	-991	15	20	24	28	2568	1729
	5	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

6	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	2212	13	14	1887	-2891	478	16	1729
	-1718	481	480	-1393	3385	477	17	1729
	1139	-645	-226	483	484	476	18	1729
	25	469	957	247	-463	475	19	1729
	24	470	10	11	720	-671	1165	1729
	23	471	-618	-1531	473	356	2555	1729
	24	470	1112	2025	21	138	-2061	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729	8	mgc	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						1729
	16	2212	22	25	-2464	1887	31	1729		3852	-1393	-1718	478	16	466	28	1729
	478	-1718	472	469	2958	-1393	463	1729		-5323	247	5817	475	19	463	31	1729
	634	-140	1916	356	-1531	448	46	1729		2212	1887	-3358	-212	706	460	34	1729
	55	439	-3200	247	3694	445	49	1729		-5139	-1531	7193	356	356	457	37	1729
	52	442	2025	138	-1422	-152	646	1729		5633	2025	-6699	138	138	-611	1105	1729
	-1396	460	3048	457	454	451	-1745	1729		-5927	454	451	448	5413	445	445	1729
	1890	34	-2554	37	40	43	2239	1729		6421	40	43	46	-4919	49	49	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► **Second-Type**

9	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						91	10	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						-1397
	25	-1277	2212	-1164	1887	20	26	1729		38	2941	2212	-5421	1887	33	39	1729
	6768	2062	64	-1823	1016	-318	-6040	1729		2498	26	247	671	28	29	-1770	1729
	-4196	-3784	101	3986	15	683	4924	1729		35	1745	2062	64	-1823	-1047	693	1729
	23	2025	138	-1860	16	682	705	1729		36	25	-3784	101	3986	673	692	1729
	24	-2452	14	3485	349	-395	704	1729		37	24	2025	138	-1860	674	691	1729
	21	3150	684	-2787	-395	349	707	1729		34	-819	451	27	670	672	694	1729
	-936	2005	-1484	1892	-1159	708	703	1729		-949	-2213	-1484	6149	-1159	695	690	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

11	semi	7x7 Inder J. Taneja ©IJT						784
	62	671	39	801	44	47	65	1729
	53	14	2212	-3036	1887	23	576	1729
	1830	-2145	2025	1941	138	-859	-1201	1729
	56	2065	-2933	32	-2007	3943	573	1729
	59	170	-89	4067	-1006	-2042	570	1729
	50	996	-115	-1904	2088	35	579	1729
	-381	-42	590	-172	585	582	567	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

● **Details**

Above there are 11 examples magic squares of order 7 with magic sum 1729. The first eight examples are based on the different types of magic squares. The last three examples are of *semi-magic squares* of order 7.

All 11 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on *reduced-entry algebraic* magic squares recently studied by the author [16, 18].

7 Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider following 10 magic squares of order 8 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

1	mgc	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/							1729	2	mgc	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/							1729
	29	30	839	26	27	28	-78	828	1729		2212	606	-3896	1887	472	20	401	27	1729
	-784	838	-379	434	433	432	828	-73	1729		16	2025	138	-1370	-429	921	6477	-6049	1729
	863	-403	2212	606	-3896	1887	-394	854	1729		1883	2086	-3440	280	471	21	-6791	7219	1729
	18	442	16	2025	138	-1370	439	21	1729		-3302	-3908	8007	12	470	22	400	28	1729
	19	441	1883	2086	-3440	280	438	22	1729		474	-6595	6632	473	246	71	399	29	1729
	20	440	-3302	-3908	8007	12	437	23	1729		18	7087	-6140	19	71	246	398	30	1729
	1530	-770	-364	429	428	427	24	25	1729		1830	1803	-3558	404	403	402	214	231	1729
	34	711	824	31	32	33	35	29	1729		-1402	-1375	3986	24	25	26	231	214	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

3	mgc	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/							1729
	1	36	27	8	7	21	1604	25	1729
	37	2212	-133	-3896	1887	-7	-6704	8333	1729
	12	16	2025	138	-2109	18	5181	-3552	1729
	11	1883	2086	-4179	280	19	1603	26	1729
	10	-4041	-3908	8007	12	20	1602	27	1729
	29	-6	3	22	23	29	1601	28	1729
	18154	16625	-34689	1600	1599	1598	814.5	-3972.5	1729
	-16525	-14996	36318	29	30	31	-3972.5	814.5	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► **Second-Type**

4	semi	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/							2555	5	semi	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/							-7685
	296	7627	299	-8920	298	297	295	1537	1729		1572	-2872	1575	-4779	1574	1573	1571	1515	1729
	304	2212	-123	-3896	1887	1300	20	25	1729		1581	15	17	-5975	6030	16	17	28	1729
	303	16	2025	138	-2099	-1257	2577	26	1729		1580	21	2212	-123	-3896	1887	19	29	1729
	302	1883	2086	-4169	280	1299	21	27	1729		1579	20	16	2025	138	-2099	20	30	1729
	301	-4031	-3908	8007	12	1298	22	28	1729		1578	19	1883	2086	-4169	280	21	31	1729
	300	1302	-5668	5705	1301	660	-1900	29	1729		1577	22	-4031	-3908	8007	12	18	32	1729
	305	18	6988	-4385	19	-1900	660	24	1729		1582	23	23	6015	-5990	24	25	27	1729
	-382	-7298	30	9249	31	32	34	33	1729		-9320	4481	34	6388	35	36	38	37	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► **Third-Type**

6	mgc	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								6916	7	mgc	8x8 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								6916
	16	2212	18	19	1887	1035	1708	21	6916		14	2212	16	17	18	2732	1887	20	6916		
	1713	-483	1711	1710	-158	694	1707	22	6916		1715	-483	1713	1712	1711	-1003	-158	1709	6916		
	5030	-3301	10	3446	-10	12	1706	23	6916		3368	-1639	3427	-1698	12	1717	1708	21	6916		
	33	1696	15	13	14	3416	1705	24	6916		31	1698	10	1719	13	1716	1707	22	6916		
	32	1697	8	7	3424	19	1704	25	6916		30	1699	11	1718	8	1721	1706	23	6916		
	31	1698	3425	-8	30	11	-3343	5072	6916		29	1700	10	1719	3425	-1696	-1663	3392	6916		
	30	1699	1094	-296	1701	1702	1591	-605	6916		158	2025	6577	27	26	25	138	-2060	6916		
	31	1698	635	2025	28	27	138	2334	6916		1571	-296	-4848	1702	1703	1704	1591	3789	6916		
	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916		6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916		

8	mgc									6916
	-4415	2212	1887	3774	15	1714	1708	21	6916	
	6144	-483	-158	-2045	16	1713	1707	22	6916	
	2025	138	3961	-2666	17	1712	1706	23	6916	
	-296	1591	-2232	4395	3410	-1681	1705	24	6916	
	-4915	1711	1710	3263	1709	1709	1704	25	6916	
	6644	18	19	-1534	20	20	-3343	5072	6916	
	6648	1703	1702	1701	1700	-9936	1699	1699	6916	
	-4919	26	27	28	29	11665	30	30	6916	
	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	

► **Forth-Type**

	pan	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916		pan	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916
6916	1885	781	3458	-2666	2882	-216	1275	-483	6916	6916	1902	-331	346	1541	15	18	21	3404	6916
6916	-156	948	-1729	4395	-1153	1945	454	2212	6916	6916	2212	-325	3768	-2197	1887	1538	1881	-1848	6916
6916	-3912	2212	2027	3131	-1729	29	1030	4128	6916	6916	1383	188	-173	2060	1708	-1675	1714	1711	6916
6916	5641	-483	-298	-1402	3458	1700	699	-2399	6916	6916	-2039	3926	-483	2054	-152	3577	-158	191	6916
6916	-1482	-592	3645	1887	-485	-1589	1462	4070	6916	6916	2025	30	33	1370	138	42	45	3233	6916
6916	3211	2321	-1916	-158	2214	3318	267	-2341	6916	6916	36	1367	2028	27	48	3230	141	39	6916
6916	267	2025	1028	138	2450	-158	31	1135	6916	6916	1696	359	-296	1699	1684	-1504	1591	1687	6916
	1462	-296	701	1591	-721	1887	1698	594	6916		-299	1702	1693	362	1588	1690	1681	-1501	6916
9	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	10	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916

• **Details**

Above there are 10 examples magic squares of order 8 with magic sum 1729. The first three examples are based on the different types of magic squares. The examples 4 and 5 are of **semi-magic** square of order 8. The examples 8, 9 and 10 are little different. The examples 8 and 9 are **striped** magic square of order 8. The example 10 is based on four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The examples 9 and 10 both are **pandiagonal**. In both these examples the magic sums ie $6916 = 4 \times 1729$. This we have considered to avoid decimal entries.

All 10 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on

22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on reduced-entry algebraic magic squares recently studied by the author [19]

8 Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider following 20 magic squares of order 9 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

9x9	pan	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	2	mgc	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1729				
5187	-2508	2855	1382	-2329	4235	-177	-2500	2650	1579	5187	-283	38	3615	-1848	334	-1523	332	732	332	1729
5187	4226	-1157	-1340	2365	977	-1613	4399	-1125	-1545	5187	107	647	-3251	2212	30	1887	32	32	33	1729
5187	11	31	1687	1693	-3483	3519	-170	204	1695	5187	-404	768	-78	190	191	1016	-318	812	-448	1729
5187	4032	-2315	12	4211	-2802	320	2212	-2370	1887	5187	330	34	370	101	-168	15	683	23	341	1729
5187	-4178	2371	3536	-4172	4505	1396	-499	2403	-175	5187	329	35	11	12	280	16	682	24	340	1729
5187	1875	1673	-1819	1690	26	13	16	1696	17	5187	328	36	-312	14	1345	349	-395	25	339	1729
5187	18	1692	19	2025	-434	138	26	1676	27	5187	327	37	1010	684	-647	-395	349	26	338	1729
5187	1691	-1651	1689	-320	483	1566	1675	-1619	1673	5187	653	22	-1293	2025	19	138	21	27	117	1729
	20	1688	21	24	1680	25	28	1672	29	5187	342	112	1657	-1661	345	226	343	28	337	1729
1	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

3	mgc	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1729	4	mgc	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1729									
	407	47	-145	411	409	37	37	65	461	1729	-78	190	191	1016	-318	21	179	31	497	1729
	45	43	595	39	41	413	27	67	459	1729	370	101	-168	15	683	22	178	32	496	1729
	-125	575	3998	-1685	-2010	607	-157	69	457	1729	11	12	280	16	682	23	177	33	495	1729
	401	49	-5907	101	6109	33	417	71	455	1729	-312	14	1345	349	-395	410	-210	34	494	1729
	399	51	2212	1887	-3796	35	415	1421	-895	1729	1010	684	-647	-395	349	24	176	1647	-1119	1729
	53	427	-1488	2025	138	17	31	73	453	1729	1796	2212	19	-5414	1887	100	601	35	493	1729
	23	11	1938	-1575	312	61	433	75	451	1729	-1596	-2012	181	5614	-1687	601	100	36	492	1729
	55	687	57	59	859	61	63	263	-375	1729	2025	6994	27	28	-7393	29	138	264	-383	1729
	471	-161	469	467	-333	465	463	-375	263	1729	-1497	-6466	501	500	7921	499	390	-383	264	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5	mgc	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1729	6	mgc	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1729									
	16	-397	681	682	19	24	176	7679	-7151	1729	25	-931	18	2024	19	20	26	33	495	1729
	1087	-78	190	191	-389	25	175	494	34	1729	1060	3998	-1685	-2010	1016	-318	-860	34	494	1729
	693	370	101	-168	5	398	-198	493	35	1729	-1128	-5907	101	6109	15	683	1328	35	493	1729
	14	11	12	280	684	26	174	492	36	1729	23	2212	1887	-3796	16	682	177	36	492	1729
	-809	1095	17	16	682	27	173	-8291	8819	1729	24	-4388	14	5421	349	-395	176	1635	-1107	1729
	1714	2212	-5336	1887	23	100	601	491	37	1729	21	5086	684	-4723	-395	349	179	37	491	1729
	-1514	-2012	5536	-1687	177	601	100	490	38	1729	1176	1131	182	-1824	181	180	175	38	490	1729
	2025	1950	-2358	30	31	32	138	264	-383	1729	28	2882	2025	138	-3288	31	32	264	-383	1729
	-1497	-1422	2886	498	497	496	390	-383	264	1729	500	-2354	-1497	390	3816	497	496	-383	264	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
79	255	51	619	55	59	83	-1432	1960	1729	1729	
-273	31	225	663	39	43	473	115	413	1729	1729	
67	1753	3998	-1685	-2010	-1055	133	119	409	1729	1729	
71	27	-5907	101	6109	671	129	123	405	1729	1729	
75	23	2212	1887	-3796	675	125	2665	-2137	1729	1729	
63	-833	473	35	659	667	137	127	401	1729	1729	
1119	-55	149	-419	145	141	121	131	397	1729	1729	
91	2025	99	103	-719	138	111	264	-383	1729	1729	
437	-1497	429	425	1247	390	417	-383	264	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

8	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
-373	69	-555	463	461	459	457	291	457	1729	1729	
-559	887	1069	51	53	55	57	57	59	1729	1729	
-515	1029	11	2212	-3426	1887	17	1117	-603	1729	1729	
453	61	-2164	19	4064	21	-1239	39	475	1729	1729	
451	63	4074	-3430	23	-4032	4066	41	473	1729	1729	
449	65	-1845	15	4076	623	-2168	43	471	1729	1729	
447	67	625	1885	-4036	2202	25	45	469	1729	1729	
899	37	-944	2025	31	138	35	47	-539	1729	1729	
477	-549	1458	-1511	483	376	479	49	467	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

9	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
11	14	939	17	20	47	153	3831	-3303	1729	1729	
47	2212	-4066	1887	921	50	150	451	77	1729	1729	
-2190	2794	29	2242	-1874	294	-94	448	80	1729	1729	
2224	-1844	2	-1283	1902	53	147	445	83	1729	1729	
909	-2175	4097	-1862	32	56	144	-4208	4736	1729	1729	
2167	2025	-3874	138	44	100	601	442	86	1729	1729	
-1967	-1825	4074	62	156	601	100	439	89	1729	1729	
62	-88	1596	65	68	71	74	264	-383	1729	1729	
466	616	-1068	463	460	457	454	-383	264	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

10	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
63	135	42	802	45	48	66	441	87	1729	1729	
54	15	2212	-3027	1887	24	36	438	90	1729	1729	
-880	-2143	27	4048	30	-851	970	-753	1281	1729	1729	
57	4063	-3033	33	-4003	4051	33	435	93	1729	1729	
60	-1827	21	4066	1000	-2149	30	432	96	1729	1729	
51	1003	1884	-4009	2197	36	39	429	99	1729	1729	
1796	-45	48	-712	45	42	27	426	102	1729	1729	
2025	641	-1190	75	78	81	138	264	-383	1729	1729	
-1497	-113	1718	453	450	447	390	-383	264	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

11	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
1130	2171	11	16	2100	25	-4252	40	488	1729	1729	
6263	-5141	2212	17	1887	-4066	29	41	487	1729	1729	
1113	1945	-136	-6131	4354	26	30	42	486	1729	1729	
-3160	-22	-2939	7242	22	27	31	43	485	1729	1729	
-819	4252	13	18	-7324	5029	32	44	484	1729	1729	
-1191	45	2025	19	138	132	33	45	483	1729	1729	
-2135	-2049	15	20	24	28	5298	1593	-1065	1729	1729	
35	7940	36	37	38	39	-6277	264	-383	1729	1729	
493	-7412	492	491	490	489	6805	-383	264	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

12	mgc	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/									1729
-522	41	3249	-1600	579	-1275	577	103	577	1729	1729	
-1006	1134	-2637	2212	33	1887	35	35	36	1729	1729	
-764	1376	16	267	185	18	19	1420	-808	1729	1729	
575	37	277	-78	190	191	-75	26	586	1729	1729	
574	38	15	370	101	-168	187	27	585	1729	1729	
573	39	14	11	12	280	188	28	584	1729	1729	
572	40	183	-65	17	184	186	29	583	1729	1729	
1140	25	-679	2025	22	138	24	30	-996	1729	1729	
587	-1001	1291	-1413	590	474	588	31	582	1729	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

► **Second-Type**

13	semi	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								-4011
891	-489	79	83	87	91	95	99	793	1729	
919	147	63	-3	155	151	43	151	103	1729	
915	59	55	205	47	51	51	239	107	1729	
911	2182	-1980	-75	187	191	-1623	1825	111	1729	
907	-2010	2212	367	101	-165	1887	-1685	115	1729	
903	131	71	11	15	277	39	163	119	1729	
899	75	79	-1860	2025	138	219	31	123	1729	
895	123	207	2062	-1823	64	91	-17	127	1729	
-5511	1511	943	939	935	931	927	923	131	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

14	semi	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								435
487	-370	28	29	30	31	32	33	1429	1729	
494	3998	-1685	-2010	428	-122	21	571	34	1729	
493	-5907	101	6109	15	291	22	570	35	1729	
492	2212	1887	-3796	16	290	23	569	36	1729	
491	-4192	14	4637	153	-3	1390	-798	37	1729	
490	4498	292	-4331	-3	153	24	568	38	1729	
489	-1879	2025	138	1176	20	296	-575	39	1729	
488	2471	-1433	454	-584	572	-575	296	40	1729	
-2195	898	500	499	498	497	496	495	41	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

15	semi	T/7=L/9								435
486	-367	29	30	31	32	33	34	1421	1729	
493	16	570	378	18	19	24	176	35	1729	
492	4615	3897	-1483	-1808	-4220	25	175	36	1729	
491	-4047	-5503	202	5907	4442	398	-198	37	1729	
490	14	2212	1887	-3493	381	26	174	38	1729	
489	403	-175	17	377	379	27	173	39	1729	
488	2191	2025	-3877	138	23	100	601	40	1729	
487	-1991	-1825	4077	62	177	601	100	41	1729	
-2187	895	499	498	497	496	495	494	42	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

16	semi	M/3=S/5=T/7=L/9								37
487	-4409	2212	29	30	31	1887	33	1429	1729	
494	25	419	18	674	19	20	26	34	1729	
493	1110	2062	64	-1823	716	-218	-710	35	1729	
492	22	-3784	101	3986	15	483	378	36	1729	
491	23	2025	138	-1860	16	482	377	37	1729	
490	24	-2352	14	3085	249	-195	376	38	1729	
489	21	2850	484	-2587	-195	249	379	39	1729	
488	-24	-19	382	-274	381	380	375	40	1729	
-2195	4937	-1684	499	498	497	-1359	495	41	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

17	semi	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								376
660	-613	49	50	51	52	53	54	1373	1729	
667	38	2325	2212	-5513	1887	33	39	41	1729	
666	-490	26	550	276	28	29	602	42	1729	
665	35	257	1961	266	-1621	46	77	43	1729	
664	36	25	-3380	202	3784	278	76	44	1729	
663	37	24	2025	138	-1557	279	75	45	1729	
662	34	577	-247	27	275	277	78	46	1729	
661	1331	-2213	-2100	5625	-1775	79	74	47	1729	
-3579	1321	659	658	657	656	655	654	48	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

18	semi	9x9 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/								426
434	-139	56	59	62	65	68	71	1053	1729	
455	5	2212	-3118	1887	14	41	159	74	1729	
452	-2163	2025	1932	138	-932	44	156	77	1729	
449	2065	-3006	23	-2025	3943	318	-118	80	1729	
446	161	-107	4076	-1079	-2051	47	153	83	1729	
443	932	-124	-1913	2079	26	50	150	86	1729	
440	186	32	209	35	38	100	600	89	1729	
437	14	168	-9	165	162	600	100	92	1729	
-1827	668	473	470	467	464	461	458	95	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

19	semi	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1437	20	semi	9x9	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	1326									
485	-364	30	31	32	33	34	35	1413	1729	381	-250	35	36	37	38	39	40	1373	1729	
492	27	221	20	862	21	22	28	36	1729	388	1031	2171	11	16	2100	25	-4054	41	1729	
491	24	11	2212	-3123	1887	14	176	37	1729	387	6263	-5042	2212	17	1887	-4066	29	42	1729	
490	-98	-2177	2025	1944	138	-929	298	38	1729	386	1212	1747	-136	-5933	4354	26	30	43	1729	
489	25	2071	-3003	17	-2039	3955	175	39	1729	385	-3061	-22	-2840	7143	22	27	31	44	1729	
488	26	155	-109	4082	-1070	-2057	174	40	1729	384	-720	4252	13	18	-7225	4930	32	45	1729	
487	23	941	-124	-1919	2085	18	177	41	1729	383	-1290	45	2025	19	138	330	33	46	1729	
486	1174	-21	180	-662	179	178	173	42	1729	382	-2135	-1851	15	20	24	28	5199	47	1729	
-2179	892	498	497	496	495	494	493	43	1729	-1347	679	394	393	392	391	390	389	48	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► Third-Type

Let's consider following three examples of magic square of order 9

9	mgc	9x9	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	15561				
19	20	21	22	23	24	11974	3433	25	15561
3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	-8516	3432	26	15561
9889	-6431	2212	12	4521	13	1887	3431	27	15561
40	3418	23	15	4076	16	4515	3430	28	15561
39	3419	1880	4519	17	25	2204	3429	29	15561
2025	1433	19	2214	8	6383	21	3320	138	15561
37	3421	4511	1885	23	2208	18	-8372	11830	15561
36	3422	-8448	3423	3424	3425	3426	3427	3426	15561
37	3421	11906	35	34	33	32	31	32	15561
15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561

9	mgc	9x9	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	15561				
35	38	41	44	47	50	15197	53	56	15561
3423	3420	3417	3414	3411	3408	-11739	3405	3402	15561
6341	-2883	2212	14	4515	17	1887	3381	77	15561
89	3369	47	23	4052	26	4497	3378	80	15561
92	3366	1866	4509	29	53	2188	3375	83	15561
2025	1433	35	2218	2	6349	41	3320	138	15561
98	3360	4485	1881	47	2200	32	-4809	8267	15561
3402	3399	-11571	3396	3393	3390	3387	3384	3381	15561
56	59	15029	62	65	68	71	74	77	15561
15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561

9	mgc	9x9 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										15561
	2370	1571	1246	3445	13	3441	17	3433	25			15561
	605	1729	2853	3444	14	3440	18	3432	26			15561
	2212	1887	1088	-1702	5160	3439	19	3431	27			15561
	2801	3443	-4483	3442	3442	3438	20	3430	28			15561
	657	15	7941	16	16	-5113	8571	3429	29			15561
	12788	1433	3436	3320	-15742	3434	3434	3428	30			15561
	-9330	2025	22	138	19200	24	24	-8480	11938			15561
	1596	3427	3426	3425	3424	3423	-10004	3422	3422			15561
	1862	31	32	33	34	35	13462	36	36			15561
	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561			15561

• **Details**

Above there are 23 examples magic squares of order 9 with magic sum either 1729 or multiple of 1729. The first example is **pandiagonal** with 9 equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. The next 11 examples, i.e., from 2 to 12 are different types of magic squares. The next 8 examples, i.e., from 13 to 20 are of **semi-magic** squares of order 9. The last three examples are of different types. Except the magic squares of order 3 or 5, the others are all **magic rectangles** of equal width, i.e., 2×1729 . The lengths are proportional according to values of the width. In all the three example the magic sum is $S_{9 \times 9} := 15561 = 9 \times 1729$

All 23 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [20]

9 Magic Squares of Order 10

Let’s consider following 13 magic squares of order 10 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

1	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729	50	2	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	1098	-1254	25	26	27	28	1701	29	19	30	1729			28	29	122	25	26	27	833	111	490	38	1729		
	37	38	587	586	585	584	-1089	583	-213	31	1729			-69	121	-22	75	74	73	111	838	489	39	1729		
	1666	-1054	2212	-1905	-1885	1887	176	20	573	39	1729			146	-46	2212	-1214	-1884	1887	-37	137	-1297	1825	1729		
	32	580	16	14	15	264	-133	329	572	40	1729			17	83	16	13	14	958	80	20	488	40	1729		
	33	579	1883	2209	-1929	-1854	175	21	-1019	1631	1729			18	82	1882	2209	-1235	-1855	79	21	487	41	1729		
	34	578	-3802	-9	4108	12	174	22	571	41	1729			19	81	-3109	-7	4106	11	78	22	486	42	1729		
	35	577	-1829	-3661	5824	58	98	15	570	42	1729			1009	-55	-7	70	69	68	23	24	485	43	1729		
	36	576	2025	3857	-5628	138	15	98	569	43	1729			33	906	107	30	31	32	34	28	484	44	1729		
	-1293	1356	507	-925	565	564	563	562	43	-213	1729			423	-1548	2906	-1497	481	390	479	478	264	-647	1729		
	51	-247	105	1537	47	48	49	50	44	45	1729			105	2076	-2378	2025	47	138	49	50	-647	264	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

3	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		-2231	-2259	100	4490	4068	-4018	31	19	1500	29	1729
		2281	2309	-50	-4440	-4018	4068	19	31	1499	30	1729
		4401	11	-2170	-2142	2200	2212	-6199	1887	-4363	5892	1729
		-4351	39	2220	2192	-2150	-2162	6249	-1837	1498	31	1729
		2138	-2076	25	13	45	17	17	21	1497	32	1729
		-2088	2126	25	37	5	33	33	29	1496	33	1729
		2013	2025	-4076	138	20	16	18	46	1495	34	1729
		-1963	-1975	4126	-88	30	34	32	4	1494	35	1729
		1506	-12244	9339	1505	1504	1503	1502	1501	764.5	-5152	1729
		23	13773	-7810	24	25	26	27	28	-5152	764.5	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

4	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		59	-2280	562	1749	19	33	-1799	1837	1442	107	1729
		2212	-99	1887	-3910	27	-11	1756	-1682	1438	111	1729
		-400	-1765	67	2188	1833	-1714	59	-88	1434	115	1729
		-1781	4234	-2426	63	-1789	1782	74	23	1430	119	1729
		31	-1923	1943	39	55	27	-55	63	1426	123	1729
		2025	43	138	-2116	75	67	71	-123	1422	127	1729
		-1951	-72	-19	2132	47	43	-91	91	1418	131	1729
		-15	2042	-1972	35	-87	-47	165	59	-3814	5363	1729
		1466	-147	1462	1458	1454	1450	1446	-2393	774.5	-5242	1729
		83	1696	87	91	95	99	103	3942	-5242	774.5	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		176	-48	175	180	-56	179	760	35	281	47	1729
		-47	243	107	-55	411	-53	759	36	280	48	1729
		174	108	21	178	-52	177	758	37	279	49	1729
		22	258	23	26	250	27	757	38	278	50	1729
		257	-209	255	249	-41	95	756	39	277	51	1729
		24	254	25	28	94	181	-1405	2200	276	52	1729
		-528	-1417	764	763	-1092	3895	397.5	-1381.5	275	53	1729
		1323	2212	31	32	1887	-3100	-1381.5	397.5	-634	962	1729
		-994	-1697	286	285	284	283	190	2675	164	253	1729
		1322	2025	42	43	44	45	138	-2347	253	164	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

6	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		2212	-1710	-1884	1887	476	20	173	27	495	33	1729
		16	13	14	462	-433	929	4757	-4557	494	34	1729
		1882	2209	-1731	-1855	475	21	-4843	5043	-1332	1860	1729
		-3605	-7	4106	11	474	22	172	28	493	35	1729
		-1529	-2862	5025	358	248	-239	171	29	492	36	1729
		2025	3358	-4529	138	-239	248	170	30	491	37	1729
		-2638	-2745	5458	176	175	174	100	501	490	38	1729
		2838	2945	-5258	24	25	26	501	100	489	39	1729
		-531	488	-270	487	486	485	484	483	264	-647	1729
		1059	40	798	41	42	43	44	45	-647	264	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		145	17	23	31	39	746	333	67	237	91	1729
		-3203	2212	25	33	1887	47	331	69	235	93	1729
		4020	-3173	27	35	43	49	329	71	233	95	1729
		11	2560	-1703	37	45	51	327	73	231	97	1729
		13	21	2600	-211	-1475	53	325	75	229	99	1729
		15	-636	29	1076	462	55	-445	845	227	101	1729
		341	1032	-1625	262	335	855	200	1	225	103	1729
		59	-632	2025	138	65	-455	1	200	-305	633	1729
		249	-1876	247	245	243	241	239	1724	164	253	1729
		79	2204	81	83	85	87	89	-1396	253	164	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

8	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		3126	857	-4659	828	827	22	174	26	493	35	1729
		-2343	2212	-53	-3896	1887	3194	-13642	13842	-1318	1846	1729
		832	16	2025	138	-2029	19	13552	-13352	492	36	1729
		831	1882	2085	-4098	281	20	173	27	491	37	1729
		830	-3960	-3907	8006	11	21	172	28	490	38	1729
		-2275	-6	5510	23	24	-2275	171	29	489	39	1729
		22153	22954	-45014	170	169	168	100	501	488	40	1729
		-21953	-22754	45214	30	31	32	501	100	487	41	1729
		423	-29343	28617	485	484	483	482	481	264	-647	1729
		105	29871	-28089	43	44	45	46	47	-647	264	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

9	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		147	4378	-1825	-2633	151	62	145	976	245	83	1729
		141	2212	-1411	-1883	1887	357	39	59	243	85	1729
		139	31	27	29	718	-273	669	61	-361	689	1729
		137	1879	2206	-1457	-1823	355	41	63	241	87	1729
		135	-3317	-17	4116	23	353	43	65	239	89	1729
		133	361	-727	799	359	198	211	67	237	91	1729
		143	35	1123	-403	37	211	198	57	235	93	1729
		426	-4178	2025	2833	49	138	55	53	233	95	1729
		1618	257	-1818	255	253	251	249	247	164	253	1729
		-1290	71	2146	73	75	77	79	81	253	164	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

10	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
		165	-1127	168	503	167	166	164	995	489	39	1729
		173	927	929	-6004	3322	928	899	27	488	40	1729
		172	932	2212	-149	-3900	1887	19	28	-1290	1818	1729
		171	931	12	2025	138	-2125	20	29	487	41	1729
		170	930	1886	2085	-4198	277	21	30	486	42	1729
		169	933	-4060	-3911	8010	11	18	31	485	43	1729
		174	-3652	22	6955	-2371	23	24	26	484	44	1729
		7	1327	32	-303	33	34	36	35	483	45	1729
		482	-14166	15436	423	-1497	479	478	477	264	-647	1729
		46	14694	-14908	105	2025	49	50	51	-647	264	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

11	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	-788.0	3497.5	2212	28	29	30	-5192.5	1887	-6.0	32.0	1729	
	25.0	26.0	-2547.5	-363.5	-364.5	-365.5	4857.0	-2222.5	2651.5	33.0	1729	
	-1116.5	781.0	784	-367	783	788	-375	787	-375.5	40	1729	
	20	-355.5	-366	1160	406	-374	1946	-372	-376.5	41	1729	
	21	-356.5	782	407	11	786	-371	785	881.0	-1216.5	1729	
	22	-357.5	12	1175	13	16	1167	17	-377.5	42	1729	
	23	-358.5	1174	-1146	1172	1166	-360	394	-378.5	43	1729	
	24	-359.5	14	1171	15	18	393	789	-379.5	44	1729	
	3459.5	-3393.5	-2360.5	2942.0	-370.5	-371.5	-372.5	-473.5	45.0	2624.5	1729	
	39.0	2605.5	2025	-3277.5	35	36	37	138	45.0	46.0	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

12	mgc	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	-35	1576	33	34	35	36	-25	37	0	38	1729	
	31	32	17	16	15	14	75	13	1477	39	1729	
	10	40	22	549	-3	519	520	22	4	46	1729	
	26	24	-483	2212	883	-3896	1887	1026	3	47	1729	
	27	23	524	16	2025	138	-1093	19	140	-90	1729	
	28	22	523	1882	2085	-3162	281	20	2	48	1729	
	29	21	522	-3024	-3907	8006	11	21	1	49	1729	
	30	20	521	-6	546	24	23	521	0	50	1729	
	1538	-1460	-55	2156	9	8	7	-1975	51	1450	1729	
	45	1431	105	-2106	41	42	43	2025	51	52	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

► Second-Type

13	semi	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1897
	-1561	6913	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	-3917	1729	
	-1369	-1804	3895	-1479	396	-179	395	151	25	1698	1729	
	32	2026	-3494	2080	-178	966	-176	150	26	297	1729	
	33	390	211	11	394	-175	393	149	27	296	1729	
	34	12	587	13	2212	-3487	1887	148	28	295	1729	
	35	586	-558	584	-1618	3902	-1672	147	29	294	1729	
	36	14	583	15	18	197	397	-217	393	293	1729	
	37	-7595	-1849	155	154	38	9625	88	784	292	1729	
	38	7771	2025	21	22	138	-9449	784	88	291	1729	
	4414	-6584	290	289	288	287	286	285	284	1890	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

14	semi	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										3193
	-1561	6883	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-3901	1729	
	-1367	157	1317	-1837	161	160	50	158	1234	1696	1729	
	34	168	388	-169	387	-1808	3897	-1483	20	295	1729	
	35	167	-168	566	208	2024	-3118	1700	21	294	1729	
	36	166	386	209	11	390	-173	389	22	293	1729	
	37	165	2212	-3493	1887	16	573	17	23	292	1729	
	38	164	-1620	3522	-1296	572	-162	196	24	291	1729	
	39	163	14	577	15	18	195	393	25	290	1729	
	40	250	-1129	2025	27	28	138	30	31	289	1729	
	4398	-6554	288	287	286	285	284	283	282	1890	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

15	semi	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										-93
	-3498	12274	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	-7390	1729	
	-1163	28	29	-3926	2212	1887	27	833	111	1691	1729	
	39	-69	121	4026	-2112	-1787	73	111	838	489	1729	
	40	146	-46	2025	-1026	-136	138	-37	137	488	1729	
	41	17	83	16	14	15	956	80	20	487	1729	
	42	18	82	134	2022	-1050	-105	79	21	486	1729	
	43	19	81	-1174	-9	2172	12	78	22	485	1729	
	44	1009	-55	-7	70	69	68	23	24	484	1729	
	45	33	906	107	30	31	32	34	28	483	1729	
	6096	-11746	482	481	480	479	478	477	476	4026	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

16	semi	10x10 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1907
	-1551	6870	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	-3891	1729	
	-1369	2212	-1305	-1885	1887	272	20	173	27	1697	1729	
	33	16	14	15	864	-229	521	716	-516	295	1729	
	34	1883	2209	-1329	-1854	271	21	-802	1002	294	1729	
	35	-3202	-9	4108	12	270	22	172	28	293	1729	
	36	274	-862	899	273	146	471	171	29	292	1729	
	37	18	1154	-607	19	471	146	170	30	291	1729	
	38	1002	1503	-317	-1825	175	62	100	701	290	1729	
	39	-802	-1303	517	2025	25	138	701	100	289	1729	
	4397	-6542	288	287	286	285	284	283	282	1879	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

17	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	-93	1729			
-3551	12455	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	-7483	1729
-1168	425	407	-609	379	378	21	175	25	1696	1729
34	-546	2212	-1614	-1885	1887	947	-3107	3307	494	1729
35	383	16	14	15	555	18	3013	-2813	493	1729
36	382	1883	2209	-1638	-1854	19	174	26	492	1729
37	381	-3511	-9	4108	12	20	173	27	491	1729
38	-24	-6	1010	22	23	-24	172	28	490	1729
39	5136	5937	-8880	-1825	170	62	100	501	489	1729
40	-4936	-5737	9080	2025	30	138	501	100	488	1729
6189	-11927	487	486	485	484	483	482	481	4079	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

18	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	3109	1729			
-1551	6810	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-3859	1729
-1365	167	4379	-1825	-2926	169	62	166	1209	1693	1729
37	175	2212	-1305	-1885	1887	272	20	25	291	1729
38	174	16	14	15	864	-229	521	26	290	1729
39	173	1883	2209	-1329	-1854	271	21	27	289	1729
40	172	-3202	-9	4108	12	270	22	28	288	1729
41	171	274	-862	899	273	146	471	29	287	1729
42	176	18	1154	-607	19	471	146	24	286	1729
43	193	-4179	2025	3126	31	138	34	33	285	1729
4365	-6482	284	283	282	281	280	279	278	1879	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

19	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	-289	1729			
-3495	12223	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-7363	1729
-1160	163	-1589	166	983	165	164	162	987	1688	1729
42	172	475	-1525	-1523	2314	362	898	28	486	1729
43	171	481	2212	-1713	-1885	1887	19	29	485	1729
44	170	480	16	14	15	456	20	30	484	1729
45	169	479	1883	2209	-1737	-1854	21	31	483	1729
46	168	482	-3610	-9	4108	12	18	32	482	1729
47	173	-1396	2025	2023	-1814	138	25	27	481	1729
48	15	1789	34	-783	35	36	38	37	480	1729
6069	-11695	479	478	477	476	475	474	473	4023	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

20	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	1907	1729			
-1551	5370	143	147	151	155	159	163	167	-3175	1729
-1290	-500	14	595	21	25	1046	161	39	1618	1729
115	-2967	2212	18	22	1887	29	160	40	213	1729
119	4632	-3530	19	23	27	30	159	41	209	1729
123	11	2891	-1784	24	28	31	158	42	205	1729
127	12	16	2333	-605	-587	32	157	43	201	1729
131	13	-402	20	1716	-179	33	-195	395	197	1729
135	-1825	-296	164	163	62	2332	100	701	193	1729
139	2025	496	36	37	138	-2132	701	100	189	1729
3681	-5042	185	181	177	173	169	165	161	1879	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

21	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	3109	1729			
-1551	6645	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	-3771	1729
-1354	162	6369	165	-6891	164	163	161	1108	1682	1729
48	159	-3877	2212	17	21	1887	941	41	280	1729
49	158	1091	15	18	22	26	29	42	279	1729
50	157	1939	-837	19	23	27	30	43	278	1729
51	156	11	2937	-1830	24	28	31	44	277	1729
52	155	12	16	2957	-6698	4882	32	45	276	1729
53	160	2025	-3142	20	7809	-5649	138	40	275	1729
54	294	-6169	35	7091	36	37	39	38	274	1729
4277	-6317	273	272	271	270	269	268	267	1879	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

22	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	3897	1729			
484	1238	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	-280	1729
-1570	1545	-3751	3341	-335	13	1522	-1944	1209	1699	1729
31	2212	-794	1887	-2505	15	750	467	-432	98	1729
32	-1001	1204	-1497	2094	1208	-440	23	9	97	1729
33	-1956	4141	-2931	1546	-436	-1032	2254	14	96	1729
34	16	782	-16	18	22	-1222	1976	24	95	1729
35	21	19	20	740	2025	25	138	-1388	94	1729
36	14	13	748	25	-1978	-93	730	2141	93	1729
37	749	-14	48	17	731	2090	-2044	23	92	1729
2577	-1109	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	-355	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

23	semi	10x10	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	©IJT	-10503	1729			
-13961	41738	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	-26293	1729
-136	-2163	2087	80	76	4	26	31	19	1705	1729
25	2203	-2047	-40	-36	36	14	9	21	1544	1729
26	7	11	2156	-2094	3	15	42	20	1543	1729
27	33	29	-2116	2134	37	25	-2	20	1542	1729
28	4074	-4032	25	13	-2104	2146	17	21	1541	1729
29	-4034	4072	15	27	2144	-2106	23	19	1540	1729
30	2200	2212	-6219	1887	2029	2025	138	-4112	1539	1729
31	-2160	-2172	6259	-1847	-1989	-1985	-98	4152	1538	1729
15630	-40169	1537	1536	1535	1534	1533	1532	1531	15530	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► **Second-Type**

	pan	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458
3458	9	11	1684	12	13	17	18	1655	19	20	3458	3458
3458	21	2212	-4070	1887	1679	29	21	8	22	1649	3458	3458
3458	-2192	3555	16	2221	-1871	13	1653	23	31	9	3458	3458
3458	2216	-1862	7	-524	1892	25	19	14	1644	27	3458	3458
3458	1675	-2187	4092	-1867	16	1645	18	29	13	24	3458	3458
3458	25	26	1623	27	28	33	34	1592	35	35	3458	3458
3458	37	2025	-2088	138	1617	44	36	26	37	1586	3458	3458
3458	-1975	1729	31	2035	-91	30	1589	38	45	27	3458	3458
3458	2029	-81	22	-384	143	39	36	31	1582	41	3458	3458
	1613	-1970	2141	-87	32	1583	34	42	30	40	3458	3458
23	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

● **Details**

Above there are 24 examples magic squares of order 10 with magic sum 1729. The first 12 examples are different types of magic squares. The next 13 to 23 examples are of *semi-magic* squares of order 10. The last example 24 is *pandiagonal* with four equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5. The example 11 is with decimal entries. See below the sums of four equal sums magic sums of order 5:

	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	9	11	1684	12	13	1729	1729	17	18	1655	19	20	1729
1729	21	2212	-4070	1887	1679	1729	1729	29	21	8	22	1649	1729
1729	-2192	3555	16	2221	-1871	1729	1729	13	1653	23	31	9	1729
1729	2216	-1862	7	-524	1892	1729	1729	25	19	14	1644	27	1729
	1675	-2187	4092	-1867	16	1729		1645	18	29	13	24	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	25	26	1623	27	28	1729	1729	33	34	1592	35	35	1729
1729	37	2025	-2088	138	1617	1729	1729	44	36	26	37	1586	1729
1729	-1975	1729	31	2035	-91	1729	1729	30	1589	38	45	27	1729
1729	2029	-81	22	-384	143	1729	1729	39	36	31	1582	41	1729
	1613	-1970	2141	-87	32	1729		1583	34	42	30	40	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► **Third-Type: Striped Magic Squares**

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										8645
	40	43	46	49	52	55	58	6573	1668	61	8645	
	1689	1686	1683	1680	1677	1674	1671	-4844	1665	64	8645	
	6168	-4439	5152	1	4	7	10	13	1662	67	8645	
	115	1614	-3423	1728	1725	1722	1719	1716	1659	70	8645	
	112	1617	2212	19	22	5274	-4227	1887	1656	73	8645	
	109	1620	-483	1710	1707	-3545	5956	-158	1653	76	8645	
	106	1623	7280	2025	-4324	31	138	37	1650	79	8645	
	103	1626	-5551	-296	6053	1698	1591	1692	-4697	6426	8645	
	100	1629	-4565	1632	1635	1638	1641	1644	1647	1644	8645	
	103	1626	6294	97	94	91	88	85	82	85	8645	
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										8645
	41	2212	47	50	53	56	59	4175	1887	65	8645	
	1688	-483	1682	1679	1676	1673	1670	-2446	-158	1664	8645	
	4637	-2908	5147	-3418	17	1712	5174	-3445	1661	68	8645	
	116	1613	2	1727	20	1709	29	1700	1658	71	8645	
	113	1616	5	1724	23	1706	-121	1850	1655	74	8645	
	110	1619	8	1721	5165	-3436	32	1697	1652	77	8645	
	107	1622	11	1718	-64	1793	35	1694	1649	80	8645	
	104	1625	14	1715	26	1703	38	1691	-3088	4817	8645	
	-2118	-296	1863	1631	1634	1637	1640	1643	1591	-580	8645	
	3847	2025	-134	98	95	92	89	86	138	2309	8645	
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	

10	mgc	10x10 https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										8645
	3451	2	3	2	6	1723	1717	12	1707	22	8645	
	-1722	1727	1726	1727	7	1722	1716	13	1706	23	8645	
	4	5	0	3449	8	1721	1715	14	1705	24	8645	
	1725	1724	1729	-1720	3437	-1708	1714	15	1704	25	8645	
	2967	-483	-158	-575	1718	1718	1713	16	1703	26	8645	
	-1238	2212	1887	2304	11	11	-3388	5117	1702	27	8645	
	4723	1712	1711	-296	1591	-5941	1708	1708	1701	28	8645	
	-2994	17	18	2025	138	7670	21	21	-5012	6741	8645	
	-309	1700	1699	1698	1697	1696	1695	-4619	1694	1694	8645	
	2038	29	30	31	32	33	34	6348	35	35	8645	
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	

Above there are three magic square of order 10 based on magic rectangles. The first and second are **double-digit** magic squares, while the third one is **cornered-type** magic square. The the width of the strip is always same, i.e., 1729. The change is only in the lengths. The magic sum for all the three magic square is same, i.e., $S_{10 \times 10} := 8645 = 5 \times 1729$.

All 27 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on reduced-entry algebraic magic squares recently studied by the author [21, ?, ?]

10 Magic Squares of Order 11

Let's consider following 48 magic squares of order 11 having the magic sum 1729:

► First-Type

1	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729	2	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	114	52	1	98	97	96	95	94	93	1807	-818	1729		366	36	3310	350	-1812	348	-1487	346	345	-269	196	1729
	51	50	163	66	67	68	69	70	71	982	72	1729		35	34	-2910	50	2212	52	1887	54	55	204	56	1729
	-131	295	1295	10	11	12	13	14	46	205	-41	1729		-817	1217	378	24	-159	380	379	19	-92	1127	-727	1729
	120	44	2212	16	53	2115	-4899	17	1887	59	105	1729		372	28	23	22	559	20	21	492	-208	43	357	1729
	119	45	-4221	4243	19	20	21	1297	22	60	104	1729		371	29	-149	549	-20	74	75	565	-165	44	356	1729
	118	46	23	2044	24	25	26	27	-768	61	103	1729		370	30	375	25	138	43	-52	17	383	45	355	1729
	117	47	28	29	1218	30	31	32	33	62	102	1729		369	31	374	26	11	12	106	18	382	46	354	1729
	116	48	2025	35	36	-842	37	-28	138	63	101	1729		368	32	27	499	572	13	15	-213	16	47	353	1729
	115	49	39	-4976	40	41	6172	42	43	64	100	1729		367	33	-99	-216	-172	387	385	31	613	48	352	1729
	57	-769	241	53	54	55	56	57	58	65	1802	1729		41	513	-922	2025	38	39	40	138	42	49	-274	1729
	933	1822	-77	111	110	109	108	107	106	-1699	99	1729		-113	-254	1322	-1625	362	361	360	262	358	345	351	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
3	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729	4	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	130	36	-95	114	113	112	111	110	109	1855	-866	1729		233	33	3638	-1948	216	215	214	-1623	212	964	-425	1729
	35	34	259	50	51	52	53	54	55	1030	56	1729		32	31	-3374	2212	48	49	50	1887	52	689	53	1729
	-227	391	2212	1887	-5555	2025	138	23	671	301	-137	1729		-495	759	-80	191	192	880	-274	20	272	669	-405	1729
	136	28	-1852	15	6214	16	-3686	24	670	43	121	1729		239	25	373	101	-171	14	592	21	271	40	224	1729
	135	29	4018	-5557	17	-3862	6091	1637	-943	44	120	1729		238	26	10	11	282	15	591	22	270	41	223	1729
	134	30	-1993	2214	3895	-1555	-1854	25	669	45	119	1729		237	27	-268	13	1164	303	-303	644	-352	42	222	1729
	133	31	-1678	2148	-3864	4083	18	26	668	46	118	1729		236	28	874	593	-558	-303	303	23	269	43	221	1729
	132	32	680	20	992	21	22	347	-681	47	117	1729		235	29	-263	17	18	939	19	146	325	44	220	1729
	131	33	14	674	-298	673	672	-681	347	48	116	1729		234	30	555	275	274	-647	273	325	146	45	219	1729
	41	-785	337	37	38	39	40	41	42	49	1850	1729		38	-238	-1386	2025	35	36	37	138	39	46	959	1729
	949	1870	-173	127	126	125	124	123	122	-1779	115	1729		502	979	1650	-1761	229	228	227	126	225	-894	218	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	230	36	-345	214	213	212	211	210	209	955	-416	1729	
	35	34	609	50	51	52	53	54	55	680	56	1729	
	-477	741	2212	-1966	382	-1814	1887	23	477	651	-387	1729	
	236	28	2356	-80	191	192	-1958	24	476	43	221	1729	
	235	29	-1803	373	101	-171	2201	1152	-652	44	220	1729	
	234	30	13	10	11	282	385	25	475	45	219	1729	
	233	31	-2077	2364	16	2212	-1814	26	474	46	218	1729	
	232	32	2319	20	-1132	21	22	250	-299	47	217	1729	
	231	33	-1819	480	1632	479	478	-299	250	48	216	1729	
	41	-235	-1398	2025	38	39	40	138	42	49	950	1729	
	499	970	1662	-1761	226	225	224	126	222	-879	215	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

6	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	553	39	-2238	561	560	559	558	-1827	2436	206	322	1729	
	40	38	2829	30	31	32	33	-1845	13	49	479	1729	
	-2222	2813	2212	12	-4105	13	1887	2849	-2258	1806	-1278	1729	
	557	34	23	15	4076	16	-4111	25	566	50	478	1729	
	556	35	1880	-4107	17	25	2204	26	565	51	477	1729	
	555	36	19	2214	8	-2243	21	27	564	52	476	1729	
	554	37	-4115	1885	23	2208	18	28	563	53	475	1729	
	-1838	-1855	748	2025	21	138	23	1889	50	54	474	1729	
	2446	24	-157	-1434	570	453	568	29	-1298	55	473	1729	
	-1169	42	3230	43	44	45	46	47	48	264	-911	1729	
	1697	486	-2702	485	484	483	482	481	480	-911	264	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

7	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	-122	91	3795	-1916	229	-1591	223	469	223	118	210	1729	
	94	418	-3499	2212	67	1887	73	73	76	121	207	1729	
	-110	406	-78	189	192	712	-206	538	-242	124	204	1729	
	217	79	371	101	-169	22	484	46	250	127	201	1729	
	214	82	10	13	280	25	481	49	247	130	198	1729	
	211	85	-188	19	928	253	-203	52	244	133	195	1729	
	208	88	694	487	-422	-203	253	55	241	136	192	1729	
	436	43	-1497	2025	34	138	40	58	124	139	189	1729	
	253	109	1793	-1729	262	158	256	61	238	448	-120	1729	
	2961	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	-2227	164	89	1729	
	-2633	231	228	225	222	219	216	213	2555	89	164	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

8	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	-209	40	-314	265	264	263	262	568	262	49	279	1729	
	87	505	610	31	32	33	34	34	35	50	278	1729	
	-294	590	2212	-3797	490	17	1887	634	-338	51	277	1729	
	260	36	863	-80	191	192	-357	25	271	52	276	1729	
	259	37	14	373	101	-171	492	26	270	53	275	1729	
	258	38	13	10	11	282	493	27	269	54	274	1729	
	257	39	-2293	4303	16	489	-1706	28	268	55	273	1729	
	511	24	654	20	21	22	23	29	97	56	272	1729	
	272	92	-358	276	275	274	273	30	267	1056	-728	1729	
	-891	42	2025	44	45	46	138	48	-21	164	89	1729	
	1219	286	-1697	284	283	282	190	280	349	89	164	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

9	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	180	24	3998	-2010	-1685	19	181	33	461	47	481	1729	
	23	22	-3796	2212	1887	21	338	34	460	48	480	1729	
	-50	252	-78	190	191	268	-66	35	459	49	479	1729	
	177	25	370	101	-168	17	185	36	458	50	478	1729	
	176	26	11	12	280	18	184	1516	-1022	1972	-1444	1729	
	27	28	-1860	2025	138	333	16	37	457	51	477	1729	
	174	330	2062	-1823	64	31	-131	38	456	52	476	1729	
	28	-4078	29	30	5657	31	32	247	-775	53	475	1729	
	466	4572	465	464	-5163	463	462	-775	247	54	474	1729	
	40	-859	41	42	2934	43	44	45	46	264	-911	1729	
	488	1387	487	486	-2406	485	484	483	482	-911	264	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

10	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	21	2212	-4115	1887	24	33	939	1815	-1615	57	471	1729	
	-2157	25	4066	26	-1931	34	938	157	43	-1507	2035	1729	
	4071	-4117	27	-4019	4067	2292	-1320	156	44	3463	-2935	1729	
	-1835	23	4072	-72	-2159	35	937	155	45	58	470	1729	
	-71	1886	-4021	2207	28	36	936	-1890	2090	59	469	1729	
	2943	2025	-2708	138	32	486	-1915	154	46	60	468	1729	
	-1971	-1053	3680	834	940	-1915	486	153	47	61	467	1729	
	38	-64	564	39	40	41	42	100	401	62	466	1729	
	162	264	-364	161	160	159	158	401	100	63	465	1729	
	49	50	1956	51	52	53	54	55	56	264	-911	1729	
	479	478	-1428	477	476	475	474	473	472	-911	264	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	543	-426	28	29	30	31	32	33	991	50	388	1729
	550	180	2212	-60	182	181	1887	-3875	34	51	387	1729
	549	23	22	262	20	21	4077	-3718	35	1543	-1105	1729
	548	1949	-1747	-78	190	191	148	54	36	52	386	1729
	547	177	25	370	101	-168	17	185	37	53	385	1729
	546	-1823	2025	11	12	280	138	64	38	54	384	1729
	545	4083	4084	274	14	15	-7779	16	39	55	383	1729
	544	-3882	-5914	-72	188	187	2219	7981	40	56	382	1729
	-3081	1010	556	555	554	553	552	551	41	57	381	1729
	75	43	1574	44	45	46	47	48	49	219	-461	1729
	363	395	-1136	394	393	392	391	390	389	-461	219	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

12	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	16	-157	441	442	19	24	106	-19	529	47	281	1729
	607	-78	190	191	-149	25	105	476	34	48	280	1729
	453	370	101	-168	5	223	-93	475	35	49	279	1729
	14	11	12	280	444	26	104	474	36	50	278	1729
	-329	615	17	16	442	27	103	-566	1076	51	277	1729
	-307	21	566	22	23	65	501	473	37	52	276	1729
	437	109	-436	108	107	501	65	472	38	53	275	1729
	2212	2137	-4544	30	31	32	1887	255	-639	54	274	1729
	-1702	-1627	5054	480	479	478	-1377	-639	255	1072	-744	1729
	6821	2025	41	42	43	44	45	138	-7723	164	89	1729
	-6493	-1697	287	286	285	284	283	190	8051	89	164	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

13	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	1089	11	12	13	14	15	47	51	149	65	263	1729
	2212	17	54	2114	-5101	18	1887	52	148	66	262	1729
	-4218	4242	20	21	22	1091	23	53	147	67	261	1729
	24	2043	25	26	27	28	-972	54	146	68	260	1729
	29	30	1012	31	32	33	34	55	145	69	259	1729
	2025	36	37	-1046	38	-27	138	56	144	70	258	1729
	40	-5178	41	42	6169	43	44	379	-179	71	257	1729
	-1876	46	47	48	49	50	2336	100	601	72	256	1729
	2076	154	153	152	151	150	-2136	601	100	928	-600	1729
	5564	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	-4515	164	89	1729
	-5236	270	269	268	267	266	265	264	4843	89	164	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

14	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	37	932	30	-99	31	32	38	155	45	8824	-8296	1729
	34	20	2212	-4042	1887	23	867	154	46	60	468	1729
	4268	-2159	24	4067	25	-1857	-3367	-215	415	-6889	7417	1729
	35	4072	-4044	26	-4022	4068	866	153	47	61	467	1729
	36	-1837	22	4073	3	-2161	865	152	48	62	466	1729
	33	4	1886	-4024	2207	27	868	151	49	63	465	1729
	-3442	-31	871	1000	870	869	864	150	50	64	464	1729
	2025	5276	-6865	41	42	43	138	100	401	65	463	1729
	-1825	-5076	7065	159	158	157	62	401	100	66	462	1729
	52	53	1932	54	55	56	57	58	59	264	-911	1729
	476	475	-1404	474	473	472	471	470	469	-911	264	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

15	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	24	-812	801	-49	18	19	25	32	-20	46	1645	1729
	1573	12	-3	3	-23	27	-1563	33	-21	47	1644	1729
	-1603	-5	4	13	14	-10	1613	34	-22	48	1643	1729
	22	5	11	-4	15	-11	-12	35	-23	49	1642	1729
	23	328	303	-625	2	8	-13	-165	177	50	1641	1729
	20	-324	-299	629	8	2	-10	36	-24	51	1640	1729
	-33	822	-791	59	-8	-9	-14	37	-25	52	1639	1729
	1200	-229	2212	29	-5088	1887	31	6	-10	53	1638	1729
	-1188	241	-2200	-17	5100	-1875	-19	-10	6	7213.5	-5522.5	1729
	678	1201	2025	41	42	138	44	45	3395.5	845.5	-6726	1729
	1013	490	-334	1650	1649	1553	1647	1646	-1704.5	-6726	845.5	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

16	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1729
	28	518	21	360	22	23	29	341	-141	51	477	1729
	1874	16	267	185	18	19	-1378	37	163	-808	1336	1729
	25	277	-78	190	191	-75	471	38	162	52	476	1729
	26	15	370	101	-168	187	470	39	161	53	475	1729
	27	14	11	12	280	188	469	164	36	2806	-2278	1729
	24	183	-65	17	184	186	472	40	160	54	474	1729
	-1003	-22	475	136	474	473	468	41	159	55	473	1729
	2212	1887	33	34	-5629	2025	138	100	401	56	472	1729
	-2012	-1687	167	166	5829	-1825	62	401	100	57	471	1729
	43	44	45	46	2004	47	48	49	50	264	-911	1729
	485	484	483	482	-1476	481	480	479	478	-911	264	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

17	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	2212	-1763	16	22	415	28	34	-1456	1887	136	198	1729	
	-1760	1795	430	418	-359	406	394	1146	-1075	139	195	1729	
	13	433	19	25	409	31	37	775	-347	142	192	1729	
	43	373	49	55	352	58	64	331	70	145	189	1729	
	376	-275	364	3086	-2967	346	334	-191	322	148	186	1729	
	46	367	52	-2676	3080	61	67	325	73	151	183	1729	
	76	307	82	88	283	94	100	259	106	154	180	1729	
	-1636	1803	298	286	-95	274	262	-18	221	157	177	1729	
	2025	-1645	85	91	277	97	103	224	138	331	3	1729	
	90	115	118	121	124	127	130	133	545	167	59	1729	
	244	219	216	213	210	207	204	201	-211	59	167	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

18	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	543	-426	28	29	30	31	32	33	991	50	388	1729	
	550	180	2212	-60	182	181	1887	-3875	34	51	387	1729	
	549	23	22	262	20	21	4077	-3718	35	1543	-1105	1729	
	548	1949	-1747	-78	190	191	148	54	36	52	386	1729	
	547	177	25	370	101	-168	17	185	37	53	385	1729	
	546	-1823	2025	11	12	280	138	64	38	54	384	1729	
	545	4083	4084	274	14	15	-7779	16	39	55	383	1729	
	544	-3882	-5914	-72	188	187	2219	7981	40	56	382	1729	
	-3081	1010	556	555	554	553	552	551	41	57	381	1729	
	75	43	1574	44	45	46	47	48	49	219	-461	1729	
	363	395	-1136	394	393	392	391	390	389	-461	219	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

19	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	44	369	115	118	121	124	127	130	253	181	147	1729	
	65	1005	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	184	144	1729	
	62	2212	28	139	2039	-5133	31	1887	136	187	141	1729	
	59	-4249	4275	37	40	43	1011	46	139	190	138	1729	
	56	49	2102	52	55	58	61	-1174	142	193	135	1729	
	53	64	67	774	70	73	76	79	145	196	132	1729	
	50	2025	85	88	-1120	91	-104	138	148	199	129	1729	
	47	97	-5364	100	103	6052	106	109	151	202	126	1729	
	965	-171	83	80	77	74	71	68	154	-56	384	1729	
	-1531	160	163	166	169	172	175	178	1824	164	89	1729	
	1859	168	165	162	159	156	153	150	-1496	89	164	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

20	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	240	-103	38	39	40	41	42	43	911	3173	-2735	1729	
	247	20	2212	-3562	1887	23	33	387	44	61	377	1729	
	246	-2159	24	4067	25	-1377	34	386	45	-1650	2088	1729	
	245	4072	-3564	26	-4022	4068	912	-492	46	62	376	1729	
	244	-1837	22	4073	483	-2161	35	385	47	63	375	1729	
	243	484	1886	-4024	2207	27	36	384	48	64	374	1729	
	242	2393	2025	-3538	138	32	210	-260	49	65	373	1729	
	241	-1973	-1605	3958	282	388	-260	210	50	66	372	1729	
	-657	394	253	252	251	250	249	248	51	67	371	1729	
	53	54	1519	55	56	57	58	59	60	219	-461	1729	
	385	384	-1081	383	382	381	380	379	378	-461	219	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

21	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	-43	160	28	29	30	31	32	33	1101	50	278	1729	
	-36	3998	-1685	-2010	848	-262	21	493	34	51	277	1729	
	-37	-5907	101	6109	15	571	22	492	35	52	276	1729	
	-38	2212	1887	-3796	16	570	23	491	36	53	275	1729	
	-39	-4332	14	5197	293	-283	1195	-681	37	54	274	1729	
	-40	4918	572	-4611	-283	293	24	490	38	55	273	1729	
	-41	-4104	18	19	5332	20	257	-139	39	56	272	1729	
	-42	4618	496	495	-4818	494	-139	257	40	57	271	1729	
	1717	-162	-30	-31	-32	-33	-34	-35	41	1048	-720	1729	
	6782	43	2025	45	46	47	138	49	-7699	164	89	1729	
	-6454	285	-1697	283	282	281	190	279	8027	89	164	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

22	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
	156	-37	29	30	31	32	33	34	1093	51	277	1729	
	163	2212	-3797	569	18	1887	24	290	35	52	276	1729	
	162	1087	-78	190	191	-501	25	289	36	53	275	1729	
	161	29	370	101	-168	557	683	-369	37	54	274	1729	
	160	14	11	12	280	572	26	288	38	55	273	1729	
	159	-2453	4383	17	568	-1626	27	287	39	56	272	1729	
	158	301	21	418	22	23	157	261	40	57	271	1729	
	157	13	293	-104	292	291	261	157	41	58	270	1729	
	125	235	169	168	167	166	165	164	42	1040	-712	1729	
	-893	2025	45	46	47	48	49	138	-29	164	89	1729	
	1221	-1697	283	282	281	280	279	190	357	89	164	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

23	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729	24	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729
157	-36	30	31	32	33	34	35	885	-1471	1999	1729	157	-40	28	29	30	31	32	33	1101	50	278	1729				
164	27	242	20	641	21	22	28	36	53	475	1729	164	2212	333	18	-3286	19	20	1887	34	51	277	1729				
163	24	20	2212	-3362	1887	23	197	37	3455	-2927	1729	163	266	-78	190	191	848	-262	48	35	52	276	1729				
162	228	-2159	24	4067	25	-1177	-7	38	54	474	1729	162	22	370	101	-168	15	571	292	36	53	275	1729				
161	25	4072	-3364	26	-4022	4068	196	39	55	473	1729	161	23	11	12	280	16	570	291	37	54	274	1729				
160	26	-1837	22	4073	683	-2161	195	40	56	472	1729	160	24	-256	14	1121	293	-283	290	38	55	273	1729				
159	23	684	1886	-4024	2207	27	198	41	57	471	1729	159	21	842	572	-535	-283	293	293	39	56	272	1729				
158	648	-21	201	-420	200	199	194	42	58	470	1729	158	-1365	-19	296	3600	295	294	-1898	40	57	271	1729				
-83	236	170	169	168	167	166	165	43	59	469	1729	117	238	170	169	168	167	166	165	41	1048	-720	1729				
2025	46	-78	47	48	49	50	51	138	264	-911	1729	2074	2025	44	45	46	47	48	138	-2991	164	89	1729				
-1497	482	606	481	480	479	478	477	390	-911	264	1729	-1746	-1697	284	283	282	281	280	190	3319	89	164	1729				
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			

25	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729										
-1194	1221	39	40	41	42	43	44	-231	1652	32	1729	-1187	28	2413	2212	-5391	1887	23	29	31	54	1630	1729
-1188	-102	16	267	681	18	19	302	32	55	1629	1729	-1189	25	1765	-78	190	191	-1067	175	33	56	1628	1729
-1190	26	15	370	101	-168	683	174	34	5527	-3843	1729	-1191	27	14	11	12	280	684	173	35	57	1627	1729
-1192	24	-809	431	17	680	682	176	36	58	1626	1729	-1193	1173	-2213	-2012	5591	-1687	177	172	37	59	1625	1729
9569	-2377	-1195	-1196	-1197	-1198	-1199	-1200	38	60	1624	1729	46	2025	48	49	5117	50	138	52	53	842	-6691	1729
1638	-341	1636	1635	-3433	1634	1546	1632	1631	-6691	842	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► Second-Type

1	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-4051	2	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-4051
78	92	439	30	27	24	21	18	15	1649	-664	1729	84	86	4234	-2048	33	30	27	-1723	21	1667	-682	1729				
89	86	-275	134	137	140	143	146	149	828	152	1729	83	80	-4070	2212	131	134	137	1887	143	846	146	1729				
43	121	59	1267	38	-110	41	44	62	-149	313	1729	7	157	53	3844	32	-2657	35	38	56	-113	277	1729				
96	68	50	11	2212	-3955	1887	20	1176	113	51	1729	102	62	3193	-12	60	63	47	17	-1967	107	57	1729				
93	71	5752	-2151	23	4052	26	-1775	-4526	116	48	1729	99	65	2627	112	37	-38	23	41	-1401	110	54	1729				
90	74	53	4067	-3961	29	-4015	4055	1173	119	45	1729	96	68	47	11	14	86	26	38	1179	113	51	1729				
87	77	56	-1835	17	4070	80	-2157	1170	122	42	1729	93	71	50	35	20	41	32	47	1176	116	48	1729				
84	80	47	83	1884	-4021	2197	32	1179	125	39	1729	90	74	41	29	44	23	47	32	1185	119	45	1729				
81	83	-4616	-41	1188	1336	1185	1182	1167	128	36	1729	87	77	-4610	-2618	1194	3883	1191	1188	1173	122	42	1729				
107	-717	-2002	2025	98	101	104	138	110	131	1634	1729	101	-723	-1978	2025	92	95	98	138	104	125	1652	1729				
881	1694	2166	-1861	66	63	60	26	54	-1453	33	1729	887	1712	2142	-1861	72	69	66	26	60	-1483	39	1729				
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729				

3	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-141										
76	94	4266	-2048	25	22	19	-1723	13	1643	-658	1729	174	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	520	1729
91	88	-4102	2212	139	142	145	1887	151	822	154	1729	198	522	94	-2166	546	543	540	537	-1696	2481	130	1729
55	109	61	539	40	608	43	46	64	-161	325	1729	195	97	91	2779	67	70	73	76	-1868	16	133	1729
94	70	1364	25	241	574	31	34	-868	115	49	1729	192	-2118	2731	10	2212	-3953	1887	19	2839	-2226	136	1729
91	73	52	1471	-78	189	192	-869	444	118	46	1729	189	534	79	-2153	22	4053	25	-1772	52	561	139	1729
88	76	55	22	371	101	-169	580	441	121	43	1729	186	531	82	4068	-3959	28	-4018	4056	55	558	142	1729
85	79	58	19	10	13	280	583	438	124	40	1729	183	528	85	-1837	16	4071	84	-2159	58	555	145	1729
82	82	49	-632	361	28	571	577	447	127	37	1729	180	525	88	87	1884	-4024	2197	31	61	552	148	1729
79	85	-238	-43	456	-112	453	450	435	130	34	1729	177	-1729	-1898	816	2025	40	138	46	1836	127	151	1729
109	-715	-2010	2025	100	103	106	138	112	133	1628	1729	397	2511	49	-203	-1412	573	475	567	64	-1223	-69	1729
879	1688	2174	-1861	64	61	58	26	52	-1443	31	1729	-342	225	222	219	216	213	210	207	204	201	154	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1579										
180	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	121	568	1729	269	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	1046	1729
204	-36	91	3924	-2002	143	-1677	137	684	137	124	1729	277	-173	40	3775	-1952	228	-1627	226	658	226	51	1729
201	481	246	-3714	2212	67	1887	73	73	76	127	1729	276	249	433	-3515	2212	32	1887	34	34	35	52	1729
198	19	191	-78	189	192	970	-292	323	-113	130	1729	275	-240	500	15	269	562	17	18	544	-284	53	1729
195	131	79	371	101	-169	22	656	46	164	133	1729	274	224	36	1407	-80	191	192	-829	25	235	54	1729
192	128	82	10	13	280	25	653	49	161	136	1729	273	223	37	14	373	101	-171	564	26	234	55	1729
189	125	85	-274	19	1272	339	-375	52	158	139	1729	272	222	38	13	10	11	282	565	27	233	56	1729
186	122	88	952	659	-594	-375	339	55	155	142	1729	271	221	39	-568	309	16	561	563	28	232	57	1729
183	264	43	-1712	2025	34	138	40	58	511	145	1729	270	439	24	-1557	2025	21	138	23	29	259	58	1729
391	167	496	1922	-1815	176	72	170	61	152	-63	1729	140	236	254	1817	-1765	239	122	237	30	231	188	1729
-390	231	228	225	222	219	216	213	210	207	148	1729	-868	286	285	284	283	282	281	280	279	278	59	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1579										
179	98	101	104	107	110	113	116	119	122	560	1729	262	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	990	1729
203	158	2212	-22	164	161	1887	-3853	77	617	125	1729	270	2212	22	-3669	23	1887	33	373	3707	-3187	58	1729
200	47	44	224	38	41	4055	-3742	80	614	128	1729	269	33	25	4066	26	-3675	34	372	477	43	59	1729
197	8	194	-76	188	191	242	-40	83	611	131	1729	268	1880	-3671	27	35	2204	877	-471	476	44	60	1729
194	149	53	368	101	-166	29	173	86	608	134	1729	267	29	2214	18	-1817	31	35	371	475	45	61	1729
191	146	56	11	14	278	32	170	1922	-1228	137	1729	266	-3679	1885	33	2208	28	36	370	-4262	4782	62	1729
188	4073	4076	260	20	23	-7771	26	89	605	140	1729	265	2377	2025	-3557	138	32	203	-337	474	46	63	1729
185	-3874	-5928	-58	182	179	2233	7973	92	602	143	1729	264	-1971	-1619	3963	268	374	-337	203	473	47	64	1729
182	2025	1806	65	68	-1744	71	138	347	-1375	146	1729	263	38	-64	1684	39	40	41	42	260	-679	65	1729
392	-1331	-1112	629	626	2438	623	556	-1375	347	-64	1729	147	482	584	-1164	481	480	479	478	-679	260	181	1729
-382	230	227	224	221	218	215	212	209	206	149	1729	-812	279	278	277	276	275	274	273	272	271	66	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

9	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1579
273	38	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	1078	1729	
281	3998	-1685	-2010	575	-171	21	73	31	569	47	1729	
280	-5907	101	6109	15	389	22	72	32	568	48	1729	
279	2212	1887	-3796	16	388	23	71	33	567	49	1729	
278	-4241	14	4833	202	-101	145	-51	34	566	50	1729	
277	4645	390	-4429	-101	202	24	70	1899	-1299	51	1729	
276	-2426	2025	19	479	138	47	519	35	565	52	1729	
275	2520	-1931	75	-385	-44	519	47	36	564	53	1729	
274	26	-746	27	28	2706	29	30	300	-999	54	1729	
136	574	1346	573	572	-2106	571	570	-999	300	192	1729	
-900	290	289	288	287	286	285	284	283	282	55	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

10	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1579
271	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	1062	1729	
279	16	-395	679	680	19	24	178	7019	-6819	49	1729	
278	1083	-78	190	191	-387	25	177	166	34	50	1729	
277	691	370	101	-168	5	403	-201	165	35	51	1729	
276	14	11	12	280	682	26	176	164	36	52	1729	
275	-805	1091	17	16	680	27	175	-7139	7339	53	1729	
274	1718	2212	-5335	1887	23	101	595	163	37	54	1729	
273	-1516	-2010	5537	-1685	179	595	101	162	38	55	1729	
272	2025	1950	-3506	30	31	32	138	100	601	56	1729	
138	-1825	-1750	3706	170	169	168	62	601	100	190	1729	
-884	288	287	286	285	284	283	282	281	280	57	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

11	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1579
253	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	918	1729	
261	858	11	12	13	14	15	278	51	149	67	1729	
260	16	2212	2154	-1939	-3148	1887	19	52	148	68	1729	
259	199	-165	20	21	22	1081	23	53	147	69	1729	
258	24	307	25	26	27	28	764	54	146	70	1729	
257	29	2025	-1088	31	32	138	34	55	145	71	1729	
256	35	36	37	3007	38	-1991	39	56	144	72	1729	
255	40	-3225	41	42	4216	43	44	379	-179	73	1729	
254	2177	46	47	48	49	50	-1717	100	601	74	1729	
156	-1977	154	153	152	151	150	1917	601	100	172	1729	
-740	270	269	268	267	266	265	264	263	262	75	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

12	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										479
359	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	866	1729	
367	37	243	30	690	31	32	38	155	45	61	1729	
366	34	2212	22	-3255	23	1887	178	154	46	62	1729	
365	34	33	25	4066	26	-3261	178	-215	415	63	1729	
364	35	1880	-3257	27	35	2204	177	153	47	64	1729	
363	36	29	2214	18	-1403	31	176	152	48	65	1729	
362	33	-3265	1885	33	2208	28	179	151	49	66	1729	
361	892	-31	182	-478	181	180	175	150	50	67	1729	
360	2025	1733	-3322	41	42	43	138	100	501	68	1729	
150	-1825	-1533	3522	159	158	157	62	501	100	278	1729	
-1688	376	375	374	373	372	371	370	369	368	69	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

13	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1579
225	69	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	811	1729	
241	2212	-80	25	-2899	27	29	1887	55	145	87	1729	
239	1189	-77	189	191	719	-213	-797	57	143	89	1729	
237	-466	369	101	-167	19	487	858	59	141	91	1729	
235	35	11	13	279	21	485	357	61	139	93	1729	
233	37	-201	17	943	253	-203	355	340	-140	95	1729	
231	31	707	489	-437	-203	253	361	63	137	97	1729	
229	-1837	472	367	3291	365	363	-1820	65	135	99	1729	
227	2025	1498	47	49	-3108	51	138	100	601	101	1729	
265	-1825	-1298	153	151	3308	149	62	601	100	63	1729	
-633	259	257	255	253	251	249	247	245	243	103	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

14	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1579
171	106	109	112	115	118	121	124	127	130	496	1729	
195	2212	635	40	-3662	43	46	1887	-1181	1381	133	1729	
192	1812	25	241	278	31	34	-1220	88	112	136	1729	
189	52	583	-78	189	192	-277	540	91	109	139	1729	
186	55	22	371	101	-169	284	537	94	106	142	1729	
183	58	19	10	13	280	287	534	1411	-1211	145	1729	
180	49	-40	65	28	275	281	543	97	103	148	1729	
177	-3037	-43	552	4254	549	546	-1620	100	100	151	1729	
174	2025	73	76	79	-1773	82	138	100	601	154	1729	
400	-1825	127	124	121	1973	118	62	601	100	-72	1729	
-318	222	219	216	213	210	207	204	201	198	157	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

15	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-3833
706	80	82	84	86	88	90	92	94	96	231	1729		
722	2212	-1923	14	18	263	22	26	-1610	1887	98	1729		
720	-1921	1951	273	265	-219	257	249	2024	-1970	100	1729		
718	12	275	16	20	259	24	28	-111	386	102	1729		
716	32	235	36	40	221	42	46	207	50	104	1729		
714	237	-163	229	3699	-3613	217	209	-107	201	106	1729		
712	34	231	38	-3436	3695	44	48	203	52	108	1729		
710	54	191	58	62	175	66	70	159	74	110	1729		
708	-1776	1894	185	177	-43	169	161	51	91	112	1729		
276	2025	-1782	60	64	171	68	72	93	138	544	1729		
-4973	740	738	736	734	732	730	728	726	724	114	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

16	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-1865
268	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	1038	1729		
276	653	-4575	2212	29	30	31	1887	33	1101	52	1729		
275	660	180	2025	-60	182	181	138	-1939	34	53	1729		
274	659	23	22	262	20	21	2141	-1782	35	54	1729		
273	658	-50	252	-78	190	191	268	-66	36	55	1729		
272	657	177	25	370	101	-168	17	185	37	56	1729		
271	656	176	26	11	12	280	18	184	38	57	1729		
270	655	2147	2148	274	14	15	-3907	16	39	58	1729		
269	654	-1946	-3791	-72	188	187	2032	4109	40	59	1729		
141	-3851	5269	-1518	665	664	663	-1193	661	41	187	1729		
-860	285	284	283	282	281	280	279	278	277	60	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

17	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											2581
117	160	163	166	169	172	175	178	181	184	64	1729		
141	46	367	115	118	121	124	127	130	253	187	1729		
138	67	1003	10	13	16	19	22	118	133	190	1729		
135	64	2212	28	139	2039	-5135	31	1887	136	193	1729		
132	61	-4249	4275	37	40	43	1009	46	139	196	1729		
129	58	49	2102	52	55	58	61	-1176	142	199	1729		
126	55	64	67	772	70	73	76	79	145	202	1729		
123	52	2025	85	88	-1122	91	-104	138	148	205	1729		
120	49	97	-5366	100	103	6052	106	109	151	208	1729		
454	949	-167	85	82	79	76	73	70	154	-126	1729		
114	168	165	162	159	156	153	150	147	144	211	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

18	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											2581
268	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	1038	1729		
276	159	-42	28	29	30	31	32	33	1101	52	1729		
275	166	3996	-1681	-2006	869	-269	21	271	34	53	1729		
274	165	-5899	103	6105	15	585	22	270	35	54	1729		
273	164	2212	1887	-3790	16	584	23	269	36	55	1729		
272	163	-4339	14	5225	300	-291	640	-348	37	56	1729		
271	162	4939	586	-4625	-291	300	24	268	38	57	1729		
270	161	-2332	2025	19	880	138	146	325	39	58	1729		
269	160	2624	-1733	273	-588	154	325	146	40	59	1729		
141	101	242	172	171	170	169	168	167	41	187	1729		
-860	285	284	283	282	281	280	279	278	277	60	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

19	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											-2837
1627	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-321	1729		
1635	-2562	4039	28	29	30	31	32	33	-1618	52	1729		
1634	-1195	2212	12	-3319	13	1887	23	375	34	53	1729		
1633	-1196	23	15	4076	16	-3325	24	374	35	54	1729		
1632	-1197	1880	-3321	17	25	2204	897	-499	36	55	1729		
1631	-1198	19	2214	8	-1457	21	25	373	37	56	1729		
1630	-1199	-3329	1885	23	2208	18	26	372	38	57	1729		
1629	-1200	2389	2025	-3579	138	22	199	9	39	58	1729		
1628	-1201	-1991	-1627	3977	260	376	9	199	40	59	1729		
141	10990	-5200	-1189	-1190	-1191	-1192	-1193	-1194	1401	1546	1729		
-13091	1644	1643	1642	1641	1640	1639	1638	1637	1636	60	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

20	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											2581
217	77	79	81	83	85	87	89	91	93	747	1729		
233	127	89	47	49	51	53	55	57	873	95	1729		
231	141	2212	-3798	381	25	1887	37	457	59	97	1729		
229	139	520	-77	189	191	-116	39	455	61	99	1729		
227	137	47	369	101	-167	357	1075	-581	63	101	1729		
225	135	17	11	13	279	387	41	453	65	103	1729		
223	133	-2089	4202	23	379	-1808	43	451	67	105	1729		
221	131	2473	2025	-3436	138	35	247	-281	69	107	1729		
219	129	-1979	-1531	3930	356	459	-281	247	71	109	1729		
273	329	111	153	151	149	147	145	143	73	55	1729		
-569	251	249	247	245	243	241	239	237	235	111	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

21	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1861	22	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										2239
266	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	1022	1729	268	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	1038	1729		
274	157	-36	30	31	32	33	34	35	1085	54	1729	276	159	-42	28	29	30	31	32	33	1101	52	1729		
273	164	27	467	20	616	21	22	28	36	55	1729	275	166	2212	411	18	-3366	19	20	1887	34	53	1729		
272	163	24	2212	12	-3369	13	1887	422	37	56	1729	274	165	736	1936	190	-1823	606	-100	-344	35	54	1729		
271	162	1378	23	2025	1944	138	-3375	-932	38	57	1729	273	164	22	-3658	101	3860	15	491	370	36	55	1729		
270	161	25	-130	-3249	17	2035	2082	421	39	58	1729	272	163	23	2025	12	-1734	138	368	369	37	56	1729		
269	160	26	2029	2092	8	-3517	143	420	40	59	1729	271	162	24	-2108	14	2853	253	-203	368	38	57	1729		
268	159	23	-3379	-125	2155	2086	18	423	41	60	1729	270	161	21	2614	492	-2347	-203	253	371	39	58	1729		
267	158	-302	-21	426	-170	425	424	419	42	61	1729	269	160	-1837	-19	374	3758	373	372	-1820	40	59	1729		
143	117	236	170	169	168	167	166	165	43	185	1729	141	101	242	172	171	170	169	168	167	41	187	1729		
-844	283	282	281	280	279	278	277	276	275	62	1729	-860	285	284	283	282	281	280	279	278	277	60	1729		
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

23	semi	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										1327
265	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	1014	1729	
273	162	-135	39	40	41	42	43	44	1125	55	1729	
272	169	2212	414	21	-3378	22	23	1887	31	56	1729	
271	168	724	2025	-1861	489	18	138	-332	32	57	1729	
270	167	25	-701	-78	190	191	1207	367	33	58	1729	
269	166	26	15	370	101	-168	491	366	34	59	1729	
268	165	27	14	11	12	280	492	365	35	60	1729	
267	164	24	-544	2367	17	488	-1519	368	36	61	1729	
266	163	-1837	-22	371	3770	370	369	-1820	37	62	1729	
144	77	335	161	160	159	158	157	156	38	184	1729	
-836	282	281	280	279	278	277	276	275	274	63	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

► **Third-Type**

Let's consider the following three examples of magic squares of order 11

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										19019
18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	15389	3432	26	19019	
3440	3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	3433	-11931	3431	27	19019	
15203	-11745	4	2212	6	1887	4536	3450	8	3430	28	19019	
48	3410	3454	1246	3452	1571	-1078	3449	9	3429	29	19019	
47	3411	8581	-5123	-1724	3455	3456	3448	10	3428	30	19019	
46	3412	17	3441	6909	1729	-3451	3447	11	3427	31	19019	
45	3413	16	3442	2	3	5182	-5149	8607	3426	32	19019	
44	3414	15	3443	-665	1433	3445	3320	1112	3425	33	19019	
43	3415	16	3442	4123	2025	13	138	2346	-11867	15325	19019	
42	3416	-11809	3418	3419	3420	3421	3422	3423	3424	3423	19019	
43	3415	15267	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	19019	
19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										19019
17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	18804	25	26	19019	
3441	3440	3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	-15346	3433	3432	19019	
11842	-8384	2212	4	5	6	7982	7	1887	3431	27	19019	
46	3412	1246	3454	3453	3452	-4524	3451	1571	3430	28	19019	
45	3413	5156	-1698	-1726	3456	3457	3445	13	3429	29	19019	
44	3414	16	3442	6912	1729	-3454	3444	14	3428	30	19019	
43	3415	15	3443	1	2	5184	-1702	5160	3427	31	19019	
42	3416	3313	1433	-8386	3448	3447	3320	5528	3426	32	19019	
41	3417	145	2025	11844	10	11	138	-2070	-8468	11926	19019	
3419	3418	-15196	3419	3420	3421	3422	3423	3424	3425	3424	19019	
39	40	18654	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	19019	
19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	

11	mgc	11x11 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										19019
-1708	3447	3448	3446	12	3442	16	3434	24	3422	36	19019	
6885	1729	-3427	3445	13	3441	17	3433	25	3421	37	19019	
10	11	5166	-1704	5162	3440	18	3432	26	3420	38	19019	
6880	3444	-8565	3443	3443	3439	19	3431	27	3419	39	19019	
-3422	14	12023	15	15	-5117	8575	3430	28	3418	40	19019	
16686	1246	3437	1571	-17707	3435	3435	3429	29	3417	41	19019	
-13228	2212	21	1887	21165	23	23	-8486	11944	3416	42	19019	
3304	3428	1433	3426	3320	3424	-9620	3423	3423	3415	43	19019	
154	30	2025	32	138	34	13078	35	35	-11787	15245	19019	
33393	3414	3413	3412	3411	3410	3409	3408	-45065	3407	3407	19019	
-29935	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	48523	51	51	19019	
19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	19019	

• **Details**

Above there are 51 examples magic squares of order 11 with magic sum either 1729 or multiple of 1729. The first 25 examples are different types of magic squares. The next 23 examples, i.e., from 26 to 48 are of **semi-magic** squares of order 11. The last three examples are of different types. Except the magic squares of order 3 or 5, the others are all **magic rectangles** of width 2 with value 2×1729 . The lengths are proportional according to values of the width. In all the three example the magic sum is $S_{11 \times 11} := 19019 = 11 \times 1729$

All 51 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [22, 23]

11 Magic Squares of Order 12

Let’s consider following 26 magic squares of order 12 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

1	mgc												1729	
		304	62	311	310	309	308	-700	307	306	305	-405	312	1729
		61	60	53	54	55	56	1064	57	58	59	52	100	1729
		301	63	29	30	619	26	27	28	-366	608	45	319	1729
		300	64	-564	618	-269	324	323	322	608	-361	46	318	1729
		299	65	643	-293	2212	98	-3896	1887	-284	634	47	317	1729
		298	66	18	332	16	2025	138	-1878	329	21	48	316	1729
		-630	994	19	331	1883	2086	-3948	280	328	22	1120	-756	1729
		297	67	20	330	-3810	-3908	8007	12	327	23	49	315	1729
		296	68	802	-550	-254	319	318	317	24	25	50	314	1729
		295	69	34	203	604	31	32	33	35	29	51	313	1729
		116	572	37	38	39	40	1176	41	42	43	44	-459	1729
		-208	-421	327	326	325	324	-812	323	322	321	582	320	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

2	mgc												1729	
		2212	88	-3886	1887	70	30	38	562	150	50	66	462	1729
		26	2025	138	-1888	69	31	39	561	149	51	67	461	1729
		1883	2096	-3958	280	-7	107	40	560	148	52	68	460	1729
		-3820	-3908	8007	22	68	32	1600	-1000	147	53	69	459	1729
		8157	72	-8100	71	50	151	41	559	-229	429	2010	-1482	1729
		-8057	28	8200	29	151	50	42	558	146	54	70	458	1729
		34	-8612	35	10270	36	37	300	-1099	145	55	71	457	1729
		566	9212	565	-9670	564	563	-1099	300	144	56	72	456	1729
		12651	156	155	154	153	-12772	152	151	100	301	73	455	1729
		-12451	44	45	46	47	12972	48	49	301	100	74	454	1729
		58	-870	59	60	3018	61	62	63	64	65	264	-1175	1729
		470	1398	469	468	-2490	467	466	465	464	463	-1175	264	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

3	mgc												1729	
		38	39	-6	35	36	37	839	-17	152	48	69	459	1729
		79	-7	57	16	15	14	-17	844	151	49	70	458	1729
		18	33	2212	686	-3886	1887	42	9	-243	443	71	457	1729
		27	24	26	2025	138	-1290	21	30	150	50	72	456	1729
		28	23	1883	2096	-3360	280	20	31	149	51	1983	-1455	1729
		29	22	-3222	-3908	8007	22	19	32	148	52	73	455	1729
		739	93	72	11	10	9	33	34	147	53	74	454	1729
		43	774	-21	40	41	42	44	38	146	54	75	453	1729
		145	-7360	7305	144	143	142	141	140	100	301	76	452	1729
		55	7560	-7105	56	57	58	59	60	301	100	77	451	1729
		-6879	61	62	63	9003	64	65	66	67	68	264	-1175	1729
		7407	467	466	465	-8475	464	463	462	461	460	-1175	264	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

4	mgc												1729	
		74	578	25	26	27	28	165	29	19	30	60	668	1729
		37	38	75	74	73	72	-65	71	595	31	61	667	1729
		130	-30	2212	-102	-3896	1887	680	20	61	39	62	666	1729
		32	68	16	2025	138	-2078	-637	1337	60	40	63	665	1729
		33	67	1883	2086	-4148	280	679	21	5	95	3064	-2336	1729
		34	66	-4010	-3908	8007	12	678	22	59	41	64	664	1729
		35	65	682	-6887	6924	681	350	-949	58	42	65	663	1729
		36	64	18	7587	-6224	19	-949	350	57	43	66	662	1729
		539	-476	54	40	53	52	51	50	43	595	67	661	1729
		51	561	46	60	47	48	49	50	44	45	68	660	1729
		-4879	52	53	54	8075	55	56	57	58	59	364	-2275	1729
		5607	676	675	674	-7347	673	672	671	670	669	-2275	364	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

5 mgc												1729	6 mgc												1729
-117	884	55	57	59	61	-115	63	-11	65	115	613	1729	1321	393	-1932	342	340	37	455	45	137	63	105	423	1729
51	53	5	3	1	-1	175	-3	650	67	117	611	1729	-924	2212	-92	-3887	1887	1305	-10176	10676	-117	317	107	421	1729
-45	105	3257	843	-4842	794	796	33	-21	81	119	609	1729	350	25	2025	138	-2068	31	9868	-9368	135	65	109	419	1729
41	19	-2356	2212	-158	-3891	1887	3187	-23	83	121	607	1729	348	1881	2093	-4136	282	33	453	47	133	67	111	417	1729
43	17	804	21	2025	138	-2134	27	305	-245	2533	-1805	1729	346	-3998	-3906	8005	19	35	451	49	131	69	1623	-1095	1729
45	15	802	1878	2086	-4199	285	29	-25	85	123	605	1729	-940	-12	2313	39	41	-940	449	51	129	71	113	415	1729
47	13	800	-4061	-3903	8002	12	31	-27	87	125	603	1729	19298	19299	-38432	447	445	443	250	-749	127	73	115	413	1729
49	11	-2426	-12	5673	37	35	-2426	-29	89	127	601	1729	-18798	-18799	38932	53	55	57	-749	250	125	75	117	411	1729
808	-674	-9	245	-11	-13	-15	-17	91	596	129	599	1729	123	-29362	29454	121	119	117	115	113	100	301	119	409	1729
79	558	69	-185	71	73	75	77	91	93	131	597	1729	77	29562	-29254	79	81	83	85	87	301	100	121	407	1729
99	-13989	101	103	16781	105	107	109	111	113	364	-2275	1729	-28521	89	91	93	30393	95	97	99	101	103	264	-1175	1729
629	14717	627	625	-16053	623	621	619	617	615	-2275	364	1729	29049	439	437	435	-29865	433	431	429	427	425	-1175	264	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

7 mgc												1729	8 mgc												1729
842	2249	851	-5980	848	845	839	507	104	96	152	376	1729	856	-4370	859	361	858	857	855	725	151	49	70	458	1729
833	2212	-133	-3886	1887	-18	38	68	107	93	155	373	1729	864	6	8	-5984	6115	7	-52	37	150	50	71	457	1729
830	26	2025	138	-2109	103	-83	71	110	90	158	370	1729	863	11	2212	-153	-3886	1887	29	38	-236	436	72	456	1729
827	1880	2093	-4176	283	-21	41	74	113	87	161	367	1729	862	10	26	2025	138	-2129	30	39	149	51	73	455	1729
824	-4038	-3905	8004	19	-24	44	77	9	191	1164	-636	1729	861	9	1880	2093	-4196	283	31	40	148	52	1974	-1446	1729
821	-12	-8360	8427	-15	10	50	80	116	84	164	364	1729	860	12	-4058	-3905	8004	19	28	41	147	53	74	454	1729
836	32	8380	-8407	35	50	10	65	119	81	167	361	1729	865	52	32	6024	-6075	33	34	36	146	54	75	453	1729
-4812	-1348	50	6881	53	56	62	59	122	78	170	358	1729	-5030	5271	42	540	43	44	46	45	145	55	76	452	1729
-8996	86	89	92	9235	95	98	101	100	301	173	355	1729	144	-13475	13426	143	142	141	140	139	100	301	77	451	1729
9196	114	111	108	-9035	105	102	99	301	100	176	352	1729	56	13675	-13226	57	58	59	60	61	301	100	78	450	1729
128	162	131	134	1370	137	140	143	146	149	264	-1175	1729	-12964	62	63	64	15080	65	66	67	68	69	264	-1175	1729
400	366	397	394	-842	391	388	385	382	379	-1175	264	1729	13492	466	465	464	-14552	463	462	461	460	459	-1175	264	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

9 mgc												1729	10 mgc												1729
-700	2956	85	87	89	91	93	95	97	-1692	117	411	1729	-809	3362	73	75	77	79	81	83	85	-1905	105	423	1729
-932	49	51	25	43	45	47	738	3	1132	119	409	1729	-943	2212	-142	-3887	1887	7	33	843	47	1144	107	421	1729
71	67	23	55	37	35	33	3	748	129	121	407	1729	59	25	2025	138	-2118	65	-25	9060	-8170	142	109	419	1729
73	73	7	2212	629	-3887	1887	25	55	127	123	405	1729	61	1881	2093	-4186	282	5	35	-9750	10640	140	111	417	1729
75	27	53	25	2025	138	-1347	47	33	125	1515	-987	1729	63	-4048	-3906	8005	19	3	37	841	49	138	1623	-1095	1729
77	29	51	1881	2093	-3415	282	45	35	123	125	403	1729	65	11	-8304	8364	9	20	10	839	51	136	113	415	1729
79	31	49	-3277	-3906	8005	19	43	37	121	127	401	1729	67	29	8344	-8324	31	10	20	837	53	134	115	413	1729
81	666	95	85	27	25	23	39	41	119	129	399	1729	69	890	170	-931	849	847	845	445	-2115	132	117	411	1729
83	59	672	-5	53	55	57	61	49	117	131	397	1729	71	0	720	1821	41	43	45	-2115	445	130	119	409	1729
2294	-2756	115	113	111	109	107	105	103	900	133	395	1729	2498	-3161	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	1010	121	407	1729
101	-7883	103	105	9659	107	109	111	113	115	264	-1175	1729	89	-13681	91	93	15553	95	97	99	101	103	264	-1175	1729
427	8411	425	423	-9131	421	419	417	415	413	-1175	264	1729	439	14209	437	435	-15025	433	431	429	427	425	-1175	264	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

11	mgc											1729	12	mgc											1729
-809	3392	71	73	75	77	79	81	83	-1921	103	425	1729	-809	3782	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	-2101	60	468	1729
-945	-89	32	174	-13	-15	31	841	39	1146	105	423	1729	-964	267	4069	270	-5217	269	268	266	808	1165	61	467	1729
57	121	2212	-108	-3891	1887	-101	-7317	8197	144	107	421	1729	37	275	2212	197	-3896	1887	280	20	25	164	62	466	1729
59	-5	21	2025	138	-2084	25	6605	-5725	142	109	419	1729	38	274	16	2025	138	-1779	-237	537	26	163	63	465	1729
61	-7	1879	2087	-4150	284	27	839	41	140	1641	-1113	1729	39	273	1883	2086	-3849	280	279	21	27	162	2064	-1536	1729
63	-9	-4012	-3904	8003	13	29	837	43	138	111	417	1729	40	272	-3711	-3908	8007	12	278	22	28	161	64	464	1729
65	109	-12	-154	33	35	109	835	45	136	113	415	1729	41	271	282	-7388	7425	281	150	-50	29	160	65	463	1729
67	17225	16465	-33543	833	831	829	440	-2080	134	115	413	1729	42	276	18	7688	-7125	19	-50	150	24	159	66	462	1729
69	-16345	-15585	34423	47	49	51	-2080	440	132	117	411	1729	43	-908	-3769	30	5517	31	32	34	33	158	67	461	1729
2514	-3191	130	128	126	124	122	120	118	1010	119	409	1729	2694	-3581	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	1010	68	460	1729
87	-29950	89	91	31838	93	95	97	99	101	264	-1175	1729	-6788	52	53	54	8984	55	56	57	58	59	264	-1175	1729
441	30478	439	437	-31310	435	433	431	429	427	-1175	264	1729	7316	476	475	474	-8456	473	472	471	470	469	-1175	264	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

13	mgc											1729
247	795	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	-205	65	463	1729
-1059	663	-3490	666	384	665	664	662	886	1160	66	462	1729
42	672	255	257	-5935	5270	256	297	28	59	67	461	1729
43	671	261	2212	-83	-3896	1887	19	29	58	68	460	1729
44	670	260	16	2025	138	-2059	20	30	57	2019	-1491	1729
45	669	259	1883	2086	-4129	280	21	31	56	69	459	1729
46	668	262	-3991	-3908	8007	12	18	32	55	70	458	1729
47	673	-897	23	6215	-4990	24	25	27	54	71	457	1729
48	-3586	4190	34	316	35	36	38	37	53	72	456	1729
1698	-694	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	-146	73	455	1729
57	-13967	58	59	16123	60	61	62	63	64	264	-1175	1729
471	14495	470	469	-15595	468	467	466	465	464	-1175	264	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

26	pan	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748
20748	9648	-1180	-3281	7680	796	-3289	11769	-5275	-1307	11785	-5494	-1104	20748
20748	-11200	1729	14658	-9240	1729	12698	-11347	1729	14805	-11160	1729	14618	20748
20748	6739	4638	-6190	6747	2662	-4222	4765	8733	-8311	4562	8952	-8327	20748
20748	2370	1571	1246	-1687	3435	3439	-1671	3427	3431	434	3320	1433	20748
20748	605	1729	2853	6855	1729	-3397	6831	1729	-3373	2728	1729	730	20748
20748	2212	1887	1088	19	23	5145	27	31	5129	2025	138	3024	20748
20748	-1639	3411	3415	-1623	3403	3407	-1607	3395	3399	-1591	3387	3391	20748
20748	6783	1729	-3325	6759	1729	-3301	6735	1729	-3277	6711	1729	-3253	20748
20748	43	47	5097	51	55	5081	59	63	5065	67	71	5049	20748
20748	-1575	3379	3383	-1559	3371	3375	-1543	3363	3367	-1527	3355	3359	20748
20748	6687	1729	-3229	6663	1729	-3205	6639	1729	-3181	6615	1729	-3157	20748
	75	79	5033	83	87	5017	91	95	5001	99	103	4985	20748
	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748	20748

• Details

Above there are 26 examples magic squares of order 12 with magic sum 1729. The first 13 examples are different types of magic squares. The next 10, i.e., 14 to 23 examples are of *semi-magic* squares of order 12. The last three examples are of different type. All the three examples are *pandiagonal*. The example 24 is based on 18 equal sums *magic rectangles* of order 2×4 . The example 25 is with 9 equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4. The example 26 is based on 12 equal sums magic squares of order 3. The magic sums of examples 24, 25 and 26 are $S_{12 \times 12} := 10374 = 6 \times 1729$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 10374 = 6 \times 1729$ and $S_{12 \times 12} := 20748 = 12 \times 1729$ respectively. See below the sums of magic rectangles and magic squares of lower orders of examples 24, 25 and 26:

► Magic Rectangles of Equal Sums of Example 24

3088	1144	5063	-5837	3458	3093	1145	3079	-3859	3458	3194	1050	5069	-5855	3458
-1359	585	-3334	7566	3458	-1364	584	-1350	5588	3458	-1465	679	-3340	7584	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
4	4194	1980	-2720	3458	7	2210	1883	-642	3458	11	2212	1887	-652	3458
1725	-2465	-251	4449	3458	1722	-481	-154	2371	3458	1718	-483	-158	2381	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
11	14	15	3418	3458	15	16	17	3410	3458	18	19	20	3401	3458
1718	1715	1714	-1689	3458	1714	1713	1712	-1681	3458	1711	1710	1709	-1672	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
2007	21	22	1408	3458	23	24	25	3386	3458	27	26	27	3378	3458
-278	1708	1707	321	3458	1706	1705	1704	-1657	3458	1702	1703	1702	-1649	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
28	29	30	3371	3458	31	32	33	3362	3458	34	35	36	3353	3458
1701	1700	1699	-1642	3458	1698	1697	1696	-1633	3458	1695	1694	1693	-1624	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	
37	2025	138	1258	3458	40	41	42	3335	3458	43	44	45	3326	3458
1692	-296	1591	471	3458	1689	1688	1687	-1606	3458	1686	1685	1684	-1597	3458
1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	

► 9 Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Example 25

	pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458	
3458	-4	1604	299	1559	3458	3458	2	1875	-1859	3440	3458	3458	17	20	23	3398	3458	
3458	2212	-354	1909	-309	3458	3458	14	1567	1875	2	3458	3458	1887	1534	1881	-1844	3458	
3458	1430	170	1733	125	3458	3458	3588	-1711	1727	-146	3458	3458	1706	-1669	1712	1709	3458	
	-180	2038	-483	2083	3458		-146	1727	1715	162	3458		-152	3573	-158	195	3458	
	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	
	pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458	
3458	29	1974	32	1423	3458	3458	38	32	41	3347	3458	3458	47	50	53	3308	3458	
3458	35	1420	32	1971	3458	3458	44	3344	41	29	3458	3458	56	3305	50	47	3458	
3458	1697	306	1700	-245	3458	3458	1688	-1618	1691	1697	3458	3458	1676	-1579	1682	1679	3458	
	1697	-242	1694	309	3458		1688	1700	1685	-1615	3458		1679	1682	1673	-1576	3458	
	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	
	pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458		pan	3458	3458	3458	3458	
3458	59	2025	65	1309	3458	3458	71	74	77	3236	3458	3458	83	86	138	3151	3458	
3458	68	1306	62	2022	3458	3458	80	3233	74	71	3458	3458	92	3197	37	132	3458	
3458	1664	420	1670	-296	3458	3458	1652	-1507	1658	1655	3458	3458	1591	-1422	1646	1643	3458	
	1667	-293	1661	423	3458		1655	1658	1649	-1504	3458		1692	1597	1637	-1468	3458	
	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	

► Two Magic Squares of Order 3 for the Example 26

mgc			5187	mgc			5187
9648	-1180	-3281	5187	7680	796	-3289	5187
-11200	1729	14658	5187	-9240	1729	12698	5187
6739	4638	-6190	5187	6747	2662	-4222	5187
5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187

In the similar way we can make the sums other 14 magic squares of order 3 for the Example 26. All are of equal magic sums, i.e., 1729.

► Forth-Type

27	mgc												6916
	10	1708	11	6742	-5027	14	24	1680	25	42	1644	43	6916
	1236	-1213	1706	-5026	5055	1700	1679	2348	-2298	1643	11299	-11213	6916
	483	1234	12	13	1701	15	26	-2299	4002	44	-11214	12899	6916
	16	1695	18	2212	-2370	1887	27	1674	28	45	1638	46	6916
	1696	-1659	1692	-504	2414	-181	1673	-1615	1671	1637	-1543	1635	6916
	17	1693	19	21	1685	23	29	1670	30	47	1634	48	6916
	31	1666	32	35	1658	36	39	-1568	3258	49	1630	50	6916
	1665	-1599	1663	1657	-1583	1655	1650	1649	-1570	1629	-1527	1627	6916
	33	1662	34	37	1654	38	40	1648	41	51	1626	52	6916
	53	1622	54	57	1614	58	2025	-434	138	65	-1464	3128	6916
	1621	-1511	1619	1613	-1495	1611	-359	561	1527	1598	1597	-1466	6916
	55	1618	56	59	1610	60	63	1602	64	66	1596	67	6916
	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916

This magic square of order 12 is composed of 16 equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. Instead considering magic squares of order 3 if we consider **semi-magic** squares of order 3, we avoid decimal entries in a magic square of order 12. See below the partial sums of order 3:

3	semi			-719	semi			5082	semi			2399	semi			11386
	10	1708	11	1729	6742	-5027	14	1729	24	1680	25	1729	42	1644	43	1729
	1236	-1213	1706	1729	-5026	5055	1700	1729	1679	2348	-2298	1729	1643	11299	-11213	1729
	483	1234	12	1729	13	1701	15	1729	26	-2299	4002	1729	44	-11214	12899	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1191	1729	1729	1729	11812	1729	1729	1729	6374	1729	1729	1729	24240
3	semi			-1624	semi			4322	semi			-1558	semi			-1450
	16	1695	18	1729	2212	-2370	1887	1729	27	1674	28	1729	45	1638	46	1729
	1696	-1659	1692	1729	-504	2414	-181	1729	1673	-1615	1671	1729	1637	-1543	1635	1729
	17	1693	19	1729	21	1685	23	1729	29	1670	30	1729	47	1634	48	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1624	1729	1729	1729	4649	1729	1729	1729	-1558	1729	1729	1729	-1450
3	semi			-1534	semi			-1510	semi			4947	semi			-1426
	31	1666	32	1729	35	1658	36	1729	39	-1568	3258	1729	49	1630	50	1729
	1665	-1599	1663	1729	1657	-1583	1655	1729	1650	1649	-1570	1729	1629	-1527	1627	1729
	33	1662	34	1729	37	1654	38	1729	40	1648	41	1729	51	1626	52	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1534	1729	1729	1729	-1510	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	-1426
3	semi			-1402	semi			-1378	semi			762	semi			4791
	53	1622	54	1729	57	1614	58	1729	2025	-434	138	1729	65	-1464	3128	1729
	1621	-1511	1619	1729	1613	-1495	1611	1729	-359	561	1527	1729	1598	1597	-1466	1729
	55	1618	56	1729	59	1610	60	1729	63	1602	64	1729	66	1596	67	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1402	1729	1729	1729	-1378	1729	1729	1729	2650	1729	1729	1729	1729

Proceeding on the same idea for the magic square of order 12 composed of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4, we can consider magic squares of order 4. See below

12	mgc													5187
	2212	11	-2381	1887	17	18	1672	22	38	39	1609	43	5187	
	12	13	16	1688	19	20	23	1667	40	41	44	1604	5187	
	1889	2210	-510	-1860	24	15	1671	19	45	36	1608	40	5187	
	-2384	-505	4604	14	1669	1676	-1637	21	1606	1613	-1532	42	5187	
	24	25	1651	29	31	32	1630	36	2025	46	-480	138	5187	
	26	27	30	1646	33	34	37	1625	47	48	51	1583	5187	
	31	22	1650	26	38	29	1629	33	140	2023	-393	-41	5187	
	1648	1655	-1602	28	1627	1634	-1567	35	-483	-388	2551	49	5187	
	52	53	1567	57	59	60	1546	64	66	67	1525	71	5187	
	54	55	58	1562	61	62	65	1541	68	69	1729	-137	5187	
	59	50	1566	54	66	57	1545	61	73	-1593	1524	1725	5187	
	1564	1571	-1462	56	1543	1550	-1427	63	1522	3186	-3049	70	5187	
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	

This magic square is composed of equal sums magic squares of order 4. By considering this way, we avoid decimal entries. See below the partial sums of order 4.

4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729
	2212	11	-2381	1887	1729		17	18	1672	22	1729		38	39	1609	43	1729			
	12	13	16	1688	1729		19	20	23	1667	1729		40	41	44	1604	1729			
	1889	2210	-510	-1860	1729		24	15	1671	19	1729		45	36	1608	40	1729			
	-2384	-505	4604	14	1729		1669	1676	-1637	21	1729		1606	1613	-1532	42	1729			
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			
4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729
	24	25	1651	29	1729		31	32	1630	36	1729		2025	46	-480	138	1729			
	26	27	30	1646	1729		33	34	37	1625	1729		47	48	51	1583	1729			
	31	22	1650	26	1729		38	29	1629	33	1729		140	2023	-393	-41	1729			
	1648	1655	-1602	28	1729		1627	1634	-1567	35	1729		-483	-388	2551	49	1729			
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			
4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729	4	mgc					1729
	52	53	1567	57	1729		59	60	1546	64	1729		66	67	1525	71	1729			
	54	55	58	1562	1729		61	62	65	1541	1729		68	69	1729	-137	1729			
	59	50	1566	54	1729		66	57	1545	61	1729		73	-1593	1524	1725	1729			
	1564	1571	-1462	56	1729		1543	1550	-1427	63	1729		1522	3186	-3049	70	1729			
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			

► Fifth-Type

Below are two more types of magic squares of order 12. Both are blocks magic square of order 6 but in a different way.

12	mgc													3458
		1934	4	7	11	15	-242	91	27	30	34	38	1509	3458
		1669	5	8	12	16	19	1554	28	31	35	39	42	3458
		-4091	5761	9	13	17	20	9	1569	32	36	40	43	3458
		2212	-4335	1933	14	18	1887	24	1493	90	37	41	44	3458
		2	6	-238	2193	-256	22	25	29	1513	-1378	1495	45	3458
		3	288	10	-514	1919	23	26	-1417	33	2965	76	46	3458
		114	50	53	57	61	1394	185	73	76	80	84	1231	3458
		1439	51	54	58	62	65	1324	74	77	81	85	88	3458
		32	1454	55	59	63	66	-1948	3342	78	82	86	89	3458
		47	1378	113	60	64	67	2025	-788	184	83	87	138	3458
		48	52	1398	-1217	1380	68	71	75	1235	-960	1217	91	3458
		49	-1256	56	2712	99	69	72	-1047	79	2363	170	92	3458
		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

The magic sum of order 6 are as follows:

6	mgc							1729	6	mgc							1729
		1934	4	7	11	15	-242	1729			91	27	30	34	38	1509	1729
		1669	5	8	12	16	19	1729			1554	28	31	35	39	42	1729
		-4091	5761	9	13	17	20	1729			9	1569	32	36	40	43	1729
		2212	-4335	1933	14	18	1887	1729			24	1493	90	37	41	44	1729
		2	6	-238	2193	-256	22	1729			25	29	1513	-1378	1495	45	1729
		3	288	10	-514	1919	23	1729			26	-1417	33	2965	76	46	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
6	mgc							1729	6	mgc							1729
		114	50	53	57	61	1394	1729			185	73	76	80	84	1231	1729
		1439	51	54	58	62	65	1729			1324	74	77	81	85	88	1729
		32	1454	55	59	63	66	1729			-1948	3342	78	82	86	89	1729
		47	1378	113	60	64	67	1729			2025	-788	184	83	87	138	1729
		48	52	1398	-1217	1380	68	1729			71	75	1235	-960	1217	91	1729
		49	-1256	56	2712	99	69	1729			72	-1047	79	2363	170	92	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729			1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

The another type is as follows:

12	mgc												6916
	2212	-2370	1887	6830	-5107	6	16	1696	17	6676	-4967	20	6916
	-999	2890	-162	-5106	5119	1716	-4953	4988	1694	-4966	5007	1688	6916
	516	1209	4	5	1717	7	6666	-4955	18	19	1689	21	6916
	8	1711	10	12	1703	14	22	1683	24	26	1675	28	6916
	1712	-1691	1708	1704	-1675	1700	1684	-1635	1680	1676	-1619	1672	6916
	9	1709	11	13	1701	15	23	1681	25	27	1673	29	6916
	30	1668	31	6522	-4827	34	2025	-434	138	6368	-4687	48	6916
	-4813	4876	1666	-4826	4895	1660	-2599	2783	1545	-4686	4783	1632	6916
	6512	-4815	32	33	1661	35	2303	-620	46	47	1633	49	6916
	36	1655	38	40	1647	42	50	1627	52	54	1619	56	6916
	1656	-1579	1652	1648	-1563	1644	1628	-1523	1624	1620	-1507	1616	6916
	37	1653	39	41	1645	43	51	1625	53	55	1617	57	6916
	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916

This magic square is composed of **semi-magic** squares of order 3. Same as one of the previous example. The difference is that each block of order 6 is a magic square. See below:

3	semi	5293	semi	5130	semi	11671	semi	5046								
	2212	-2370	1887	1729	6830	-5107	6	1729	16	1696	17	1729	6676	-4967	20	1729
	-999	2890	-162	1729	-5106	5119	1716	1729	-4953	4988	1694	1729	-4966	5007	1688	1729
	516	1209	4	1729	5	1717	7	1729	6666	-4955	18	1729	19	1689	21	1729
	1729	1729	1729	5106	1729	1729	1729	11956	1729	1729	1729	5022	1729	1729	1729	11704
3	semi	-1672	semi	-1648	semi	-1588	semi	-1564								
	8	1711	10	1729	12	1703	14	1729	22	1683	24	1729	26	1675	28	1729
	1712	-1691	1708	1729	1704	-1675	1700	1729	1684	-1635	1680	1729	1676	-1619	1672	1729
	9	1709	11	1729	13	1701	15	1729	23	1681	25	1729	27	1673	29	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1672	1729	1729	1729	-1648	1729	1729	1729	-1588	1729	1729	1729	-1564
3	semi	11419	semi	4962	semi	5224	semi	4878								
	30	1668	31	1729	6522	-4827	34	1729	2025	-434	138	1729	6368	-4687	48	1729
	-4813	4876	1666	1729	-4826	4895	1660	1729	-2599	2783	1545	1729	-4686	4783	1632	1729
	6512	-4815	32	1729	33	1661	35	1729	2303	-620	46	1729	47	1633	49	1729
	1729	1729	1729	4938	1729	1729	1729	11452	1729	1729	1729	4854	1729	1729	1729	11200
3	semi	-1504	semi	-1480	semi	-1420	semi	-1396								
	36	1655	38	1729	40	1647	42	1729	50	1627	52	1729	54	1619	56	1729
	1656	-1579	1652	1729	1648	-1563	1644	1729	1628	-1523	1624	1729	1620	-1507	1616	1729
	37	1653	39	1729	41	1645	43	1729	51	1625	53	1729	55	1617	57	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1504	1729	1729	1729	-1480	1729	1729	1729	-1420	1729	1729	1729	-1396

6	mgc						3458	6	mgc							3458
		2212	-2370	1887	6830	-5107	6			16	1696	17	6676	-4967	20	3458
		-999	2890	-162	-5106	5119	1716	3458		-4953	4988	1694	-4966	5007	1688	3458
		516	1209	4	5	1717	7	3458		6666	-4955	18	19	1689	21	3458
		8	1711	10	12	1703	14	3458		22	1683	24	26	1675	28	3458
		1712	-1691	1708	1704	-1675	1700	3458		1684	-1635	1680	1676	-1619	1672	3458
		9	1709	11	13	1701	15	3458		23	1681	25	27	1673	29	3458
		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458
6	mgc							3458	6	mgc						3458
		30	1668	31	6522	-4827	34	3458		2025	-434	138	6368	-4687	48	3458
		-4813	4876	1666	-4826	4895	1660	3458		-2599	2783	1545	-4686	4783	1632	3458
		6512	-4815	32	33	1661	35	3458		2303	-620	46	47	1633	49	3458
		36	1655	38	40	1647	42	3458		50	1627	52	54	1619	56	3458
		1656	-1579	1652	1648	-1563	1644	3458		1628	-1523	1624	1620	-1507	1616	3458
		37	1653	39	41	1645	43	3458		51	1625	53	55	1617	57	3458
		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458		3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

► Sixth-Type: Striped Magic Squares

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										10374		
		74	77	80	83	86	89	92	95	98	7871	1628	101	10374
		1655	1652	1649	1646	1643	1640	1637	1634	1631	-6142	1625	104	10374
		7190	-5461	2212	23	26	29	1887	1010	1694	35	1622	107	10374
		173	1556	-483	1706	1703	1700	-158	719	1691	38	1619	110	10374
		170	1559	4856	-3127	3449	2	5	2	1688	41	1616	113	10374
		167	1562	71	1658	-1720	1727	1724	1727	1685	44	1613	116	10374
		164	1565	68	1661	8	11	-4	3443	1682	47	1610	119	10374
		161	1568	65	1664	1721	1718	1733	-1714	-3253	4982	1607	122	10374
		158	1571	62	1667	-3237	-296	1673	1676	1591	3780	1604	125	10374
		155	1574	65	1664	4966	2025	56	53	138	-2051	-5899	7628	10374
		152	1577	-5677	1580	1583	1586	1589	1592	1595	1598	1601	1598	10374
		155	1574	7406	149	146	143	140	137	134	131	128	131	10374
		10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											10374
	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	10055	33	34	10374
	1705	1704	1703	1702	1701	1700	1699	1698	1697	-8326	1696	1695	10374
	6538	-4809	2212	7	8	9	10	2772	11	1887	1694	35	10374
	57	1672	-483	1722	1721	1720	1719	-1043	1718	-158	1693	36	10374
	56	1673	3392	-1663	3451	-1722	4	1725	1716	13	1692	37	10374
	55	1674	23	1706	2	1727	5	1724	1715	14	1691	38	10374
	54	1675	22	1707	3	1726	0	1729	1714	15	1690	39	10374
	53	1676	21	1708	2	1727	3449	-1720	-1687	3416	1689	40	10374
	52	1677	3901	2025	-1545	19	18	17	138	2343	1688	41	10374
	51	1678	-2172	-296	3274	1710	1711	1712	1591	-614	-4921	6650	10374
	1680	1679	-8139	1680	1681	1682	1683	1684	1685	1686	1687	1686	10374
	49	50	9868	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	43	10374
	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

12	mgc	12x12 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											10374
	3454	1	2	1	5	1724	1718	11	1708	21	1694	35	10374
	-1725	1728	1727	1728	6	1723	1717	12	1707	22	1693	36	10374
	3	4	-1	3452	7	1722	1716	13	1706	23	1692	37	10374
	1726	1725	1730	-1723	3440	-1711	1715	14	1705	24	1691	38	10374
	5175	1721	1720	-6867	1719	1719	1714	15	1704	25	1690	39	10374
	-3446	8	9	8596	10	10	-3393	5122	1703	26	1689	40	10374
	-5638	-483	1712	1711	-158	6354	1709	1709	1702	27	1688	41	10374
	7367	2212	17	18	1887	-4625	20	20	-5019	6748	1687	42	10374
	-299	-296	1700	1699	1698	1697	1591	-2535	1695	1695	1686	43	10374
	2028	2025	29	30	31	32	138	4264	34	34	-6565	8294	10374
	3087	1685	1684	1683	1682	1681	1680	1679	1678	-9519	1677	1677	10374
	-1358	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	11248	52	52	10374
	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

Above there are three magic square of order 12 based on magic rectangles. The first and second are **double-digit** magic squares, while the third one is **cornered-type** magic square. The the width of the strip is always same, i.e., 1729. The change is only in the lengths. The magic sum for all the three magic square is same, i.e., $S_{12 \times 12} := 10374 = 6 \times 1729$.

All 33 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [24, 25]

12 Magic Squares of Order 13

Let's consider following 3 magic squares of order 13 having the magic sum 1729:

13	mgc	13x13 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729		
		32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	1098	224	42	1729
		234	233	232	231	230	229	228	227	226	225	-832	223	43	1729
		816	-550	2212	11	12	13	14	1887	-3218	250	16	222	44	1729
		69	197	-1946	255	254	253	252	-1621	3484	249	17	221	45	1729
		68	198	758	-492	2	3	651	4	5	248	18	220	46	1729
		67	199	31	235	14	6	-7	7	645	247	19	219	47	1729
		66	200	30	236	-2	649	8	16	-6	246	20	218	48	1729
		65	201	29	237	10	4	-1	640	12	245	21	217	49	1729
		64	202	28	238	641	3	14	-2	9	-554	820	216	50	1729
		63	203	27	239	-493	-1759	241	242	243	128	2329	215	51	1729
		62	204	28	238	759	2025	25	24	23	138	-2063	-732	998	1729
		61	205	-640	206	207	208	209	210	211	212	213	214	213	1729
		62	204	906	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

13	mgc	13x13 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729		
		33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	42	1267	43	44	1729
		233	232	231	230	229	228	227	226	225	224	-1001	223	222	1729
		665	-399	11	2212	13	14	15	16	-2989	1887	18	221	45	1729
		70	196	255	-1946	253	252	251	250	3255	-1621	248	220	46	1729
		69	197	543	-277	3	4	647	5	6	241	25	219	47	1729
		68	198	29	237	15	7	-6	8	641	240	26	218	48	1729
		67	199	30	236	-1	645	9	17	-5	239	27	217	49	1729
		66	200	31	235	11	5	0	636	13	238	28	216	50	1729
		65	201	32	234	637	4	15	-1	10	-293	559	215	51	1729
		64	202	-3628	-1759	7551	246	245	244	243	128	-2073	214	52	1729
		63	203	3894	2025	-7285	20	21	22	23	138	2339	-543	809	1729
		205	204	-773	205	206	207	208	209	210	211	212	213	212	1729
		61	62	1039	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	54	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

13	mgc	13x13 Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											1729		
		-130	264	265	263	3	259	7	251	15	239	27	223	43	1729
		528	133	-262	262	4	258	8	250	16	238	28	222	44	1729
		1	2	396	-126	392	257	9	249	17	237	29	221	45	1729
		523	261	-639	260	260	256	10	248	18	236	30	220	46	1729
		-257	5	905	6	6	-365	631	247	19	235	31	219	47	1729
		-789	-1946	254	-1621	4529	252	252	246	20	234	32	218	48	1729
		1055	2212	12	1887	-4263	14	14	-560	826	233	33	217	49	1729
		-3497	-1759	244	128	242	241	5118	240	240	232	34	216	50	1729
		3763	2025	22	138	24	25	-4852	26	26	-687	953	215	51	1729
		-3666	231	230	229	228	227	226	225	3085	224	224	214	52	1729
		3932	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	-2819	42	42	-722	988	1729
		89	213	212	211	210	209	208	207	206	205	-649	204	204	1729
		177	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	915	62	62	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

• **Details**

Above there are 3 examples magic squares of order 13 with magic sum 1729. All 3 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four numbers 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

13 Magic Squares of Order 14

Let's consider following 4 magic squares of order 14 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													1729
180	-576	191	190	189	188	187	186	185	184	183	182	181	79	1729	
-533	2	2702	-2214	4	8	484	-8	10	14	478	-14	16	780	1729	
179	7	2217	6	-1736	13	11	12	458	19	17	1887	-1429	68	1729	
178	0	-1	-1728	2223	6	5	466	17	12	-1858	448	1892	69	1729	
177	485	-4424	4430	3	467	-6	24	9	449	1857	-1827	15	70	1729	
176	20	472	-20	22	26	466	-26	28	32	460	-32	34	71	1729	
175	25	23	24	422	31	29	30	404	37	35	36	386	72	1729	
174	18	17	430	29	24	23	412	35	30	29	394	41	73	1729	
173	431	-18	60	21	413	-24	78	27	395	-30	96	33	74	1729	
172	38	2438	-2022	40	44	448	-44	46	50	442	-50	52	75	1729	
171	43	2025	42	-1616	49	47	48	350	55	53	138	248	76	1729	
170	36	35	-1608	2031	42	41	358	53	48	-37	340	143	77	1729	
169	377	-4004	4082	39	359	-42	132	45	341	36	66	51	78	1729	
168	823	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	1729	
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

► Second-Type

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1729		
		40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	987	196	51	1729
		207	206	205	204	203	202	201	200	199	198	197	-740	195	52	1729
		644	-397	2212	15	16	17	18	19	20	-1329	-1640	1887	194	53	1729
		81	166	-1965	232	231	230	229	228	227	1576	225	22	193	54	1729
		80	167	611	-364	726	1	2	3	4	5	224	23	192	55	1729
		79	168	39	208	-479	246	245	244	243	242	223	24	191	56	1729
		78	169	38	209	6	7	8	732	-21	9	222	25	190	57	1729
		77	170	37	210	241	240	239	-485	268	238	221	26	189	58	1729
		76	171	2025	-1778	735	10	-40	11	12	13	109	138	188	59	1729
		75	172	35	212	-488	237	287	236	235	234	1404	-1157	187	60	1729
		74	173	34	213	-2727	214	215	216	217	218	219	2416	186	61	1729
		73	174	-1831	2078	2974	33	32	31	30	29	28	-2169	-619	866	1729
		72	175	-507	176	177	178	179	180	181	182	183	184	185	184	1729
		73	174	754	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												1729		
		39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	1144	50	51	1729
		208	207	206	205	204	203	202	201	200	199	198	-897	197	196	1729
		551	-304	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	1082	20	21	195	52	1729
		80	167	234	233	232	231	230	229	228	-835	227	226	194	53	1729
		79	168	-3603	3850	1	246	4	243	7	240	225	22	193	54	1729
		78	169	2212	-1965	2	245	479	-232	8	239	-1640	1887	192	55	1729
		77	170	37	210	3	244	5	242	470	-223	223	24	191	56	1729
		76	171	36	211	488	-241	6	241	9	238	222	25	190	57	1729
		75	172	2025	-1778	239	237	236	-439	235	233	109	138	189	58	1729
		74	173	34	213	8	10	11	686	12	14	1602	-1355	188	59	1729
		73	174	215	214	-718	215	216	217	218	219	220	219	187	60	1729
		72	175	32	33	965	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	-484	731	1729
		177	176	-624	177	178	179	180	181	182	183	184	185	186	185	1729
		70	71	871	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	1729
		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/												1729	
	-5491	2212	1887	1886	5	242	236	11	226	21	212	35	194	53	1729
	5738	-1965	-1640	-1639	6	241	235	12	225	22	211	36	193	54	1729
	3	4	4095	-3608	7	240	234	13	224	23	210	37	192	55	1729
	244	243	-3848	3855	476	-229	233	14	223	24	209	38	191	56	1729
	-9480	-1778	109	11416	237	237	232	15	222	25	208	39	190	57	1729
	9727	2025	138	-11169	10	10	-429	676	221	26	207	40	189	58	1729
	12006	231	230	229	228	-12390	227	227	220	27	206	41	188	59	1729
	-11759	16	17	18	19	12637	20	20	-573	820	205	42	187	60	1729
	216	219	218	217	216	215	214	-706	213	213	204	43	186	61	1729
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	953	34	34	-637	884	185	62	1729
	-13079	203	12575	201	202	199	198	197	196	200	195	195	184	63	1729
	13326	44	-12328	46	45	48	49	50	51	47	52	52	-597	844	1729
	-12195	183	182	181	180	179	178	177	176	175	174	11793	173	173	1729
	12442	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	-11546	74	74	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► Third-Type

14	mgc	14x14 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT												3458	
	539	36	2	7	2215	16	-1086	-1486	59	25	30	29	39	3033	3458
	2223	-2711	2212	8	12	-35	20	83	-283	26	31	1887	-58	43	3458
	1695	1050	0	-1099	45	17	21	1557	-1217	1875	1168	-1738	40	44	3458
	-576	-31	-500	2783	13	18	22	1495	-8	-281	401	36	41	45	3458
	-506	88	4	9	-585	2696	23	-287	157	27	32	1440	314	46	3458
	507	2171	5	10	14	-1002	24	288	-15	28	33	37	1311	47	3458
	-2153	1126	6	11	15	19	2705	79	3036	29	34	38	42	-1529	3458
	674	82	48	53	2028	62	-1218	-1118	105	71	76	75	85	2435	3458
	2128	-2521	2025	54	58	-81	66	221	1236	72	77	138	-104	89	3458
	1419	1182	46	-1231	183	63	67	1281	-2414	126	2365	195	86	90	3458
	-619	15	-543	2685	59	64	68	1219	38	1238	-1026	82	87	91	3458
	-549	226	50	55	-720	2598	69	1232	295	73	78	1072	-1113	92	3458
	550	1984	51	56	60	-1042	70	-1231	31	74	79	83	2600	93	3458
	-1874	761	52	57	61	65	2607	125	2438	75	80	84	88	-1161	3458
	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

• Details

Above there are 5 examples magic squares of order 14. The first four examples are with magic sum 1729. The last example is with magic sum double of 1729. This is due to the fact that it is divided in four equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7 with magic sum 1729. See below the individual sum of **pandiagonal** magic square of order 7.

7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	539	36	2	7	2215	16	-1086	1729	1729	-1486	59	25	30	29	39	3033	1729
1729	2223	-2711	2212	8	12	-35	20	1729	1729	83	-283	26	31	1887	-58	43	1729
1729	1695	1050	0	-1099	45	17	21	1729	1729	1557	-1217	1875	1168	-1738	40	44	1729
1729	-576	-31	-500	2783	13	18	22	1729	1729	1495	-8	-281	401	36	41	45	1729
1729	-506	88	4	9	-585	2696	23	1729	1729	-287	157	27	32	1440	314	46	1729
1729	507	2171	5	10	14	-1002	24	1729	1729	288	-15	28	33	37	1311	47	1729
	-2153	1126	6	11	15	19	2705	1729		79	3036	29	34	38	42	-1529	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	7x7	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	674	82	48	53	2028	62	-1218	1729	1729	-1118	105	71	76	75	85	2435	1729
1729	2128	-2521	2025	54	58	-81	66	1729	1729	221	1236	72	77	138	-104	89	1729
1729	1419	1182	46	-1231	183	63	67	1729	1729	1281	-2414	126	2365	195	86	90	1729
1729	-619	15	-543	2685	59	64	68	1729	1729	1219	38	1238	-1026	82	87	91	1729
1729	-549	226	50	55	-720	2598	69	1729	1729	1232	295	73	78	1072	-1113	92	1729
1729	550	1984	51	56	60	-1042	70	1729	1729	-1231	31	74	79	83	2600	93	1729
	-1874	761	52	57	61	65	2607	1729		125	2438	75	80	84	88	-1161	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

The last three examples we call as **striped** magic squares of order 14. All 5 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four numbers 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

14 Magic Squares of Order 15

Let's consider following 2 magic squares of order 15 having the magic sum 1729:

► **First-Type**

15	mgc															5187
	2212	14	-2404	1887	20	35	38	1571	41	44	59	62	1475	65	68	5187
	47	23	4055	26	-2422	71	47	8	50	1553	95	71	32	74	1457	5187
	1869	-2410	29	-1817	4058	23	1565	53	77	11	47	1469	77	101	35	5187
	-1835	2218	1872	-567	41	59	41	26	1538	65	83	65	50	1442	89	5187
	-564	1884	-1823	2200	32	1541	38	71	23	56	1445	62	95	47	80	5187
	107	110	1289	107	116	83	86	1379	89	92	131	134	1187	137	140	5187
	143	119	74	122	1271	119	2025	-1914	138	1361	167	143	104	146	1169	5187
	89	1283	125	155	77	-1859	1413	101	2055	19	119	1181	149	173	107	5187
	137	113	92	1250	137	2037	49	74	-584	153	155	137	122	1154	161	5187
	1253	104	149	95	128	1349	-1844	2089	31	104	1157	134	167	119	152	5187
	155	158	1091	161	164	179	182	995	185	188	203	206	899	209	212	5187
	191	167	128	170	1073	215	191	152	194	977	239	215	176	218	881	5187
	143	1085	173	197	131	167	989	197	221	155	191	893	221	245	179	5187
	179	161	146	1058	185	203	185	170	962	209	227	209	194	866	233	5187
	1061	158	191	143	176	965	182	215	167	200	869	206	239	191	224	5187
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187

15	mgc															8645
	-569 1/3	1148 2/3	1149 2/3	-565 1/3	1146 2/3	1147 2/3	3522 2/3	-734 1/3	-1059 1/3	-557 1/3	1142 2/3	1143 2/3	-553 1/3	1140 2/3	1141 2/3	8645
	2295 1/3	576 1/3	-1142 2/3	2289 1/3	576 1/3	-1136 2/3	-4005 2/3	576 1/3	5158 1/3	2277 1/3	576 1/3	-1124 2/3	2271 1/3	576 1/3	-1118 2/3	8645
	3	4	1722	5	6	1718	2212	1887	-2370	9	10	1710	11	12	1706	8645
	-549 1/3	1138 2/3	1139 2/3	-545 1/3	1136 2/3	1137 2/3	-541 1/3	1134 2/3	1135 2/3	-537 1/3	1132 2/3	1133 2/3	-533 1/3	1130 2/3	1131 2/3	8645
	2265 1/3	576 1/3	-1112 2/3	2259 1/3	576 1/3	-1106 2/3	2253 1/3	576 1/3	-1100 2/3	2247 1/3	576 1/3	-1094 2/3	2241 1/3	576 1/3	-1088 2/3	8645
	13	14	1702	15	16	1698	17	18	1694	19	20	1690	21	22	1686	8645
	-529 1/3	1128 2/3	1129 2/3	-525 1/3	1126 2/3	1127 2/3	-521 1/3	1124 2/3	1125 2/3	-517 1/3	1122 2/3	1123 2/3	-513 1/3	1120 2/3	1121 2/3	8645
	2235 1/3	576 1/3	-1082 2/3	2229 1/3	576 1/3	-1076 2/3	2223 1/3	576 1/3	-1070 2/3	2217 1/3	576 1/3	-1064 2/3	2211 1/3	576 1/3	-1058 2/3	8645
	23	24	1682	25	26	1678	27	28	1674	29	30	1670	31	32	1666	8645
	-509 1/3	1118 2/3	1119 2/3	-505 1/3	1116 2/3	1117 2/3	1586 2/3	1014 2/3	-872 1/3	-497 1/3	1112 2/3	1113 2/3	-493 1/3	1110 2/3	1111 2/3	8645
	2205 1/3	576 1/3	-1052 2/3	2199 1/3	576 1/3	-1046 2/3	-1882 2/3	576 1/3	3035 1/3	2187 1/3	576 1/3	-1034 2/3	2181 1/3	576 1/3	-1028 2/3	8645
	33	34	1662	35	36	1658	2025	138	-434	39	40	1650	41	42	1646	8645
	-489 1/3	1108 2/3	1109 2/3	-485 1/3	1106 2/3	1107 2/3	-481 1/3	1104 2/3	1105 2/3	-477 1/3	1102 2/3	1103 2/3	-473 1/3	1100 2/3	1101 2/3	8645
	2175 1/3	576 1/3	-1022 2/3	2169 1/3	576 1/3	-1016 2/3	2163 1/3	576 1/3	-1010 2/3	2157 1/3	576 1/3	-1004 2/3	2151 1/3	576 1/3	-998 2/3	8645
	43	44	1642	45	46	1638	47	48	1634	49	50	1630	51	52	1626	8645
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645

● **Details**

Above there are 2 examples magic squares of order 15 with magic sums $5187 = 3 \times 1729$ and $8645 = 5 \times 1729$. First examples is based on 9 equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5. The second example is based on 25 equal sums magic squares of order 3. It contains fractional entries. See below the details of these magic squares of orders 5 and 3:

5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	2212	14	-2404	1887	20	1729	1729	35	38	1571	41	44	1729	1729	59	62	1475	65	68	1729	1729	
1729	47	23	4055	26	-2422	1729	1729	71	47	8	50	1553	1729	1729	95	71	32	74	1457	1729	1729	
1729	1869	-2410	29	-1817	4058	1729	1729	23	1565	53	77	11	1729	1729	47	1469	77	101	35	1729	1729	
1729	-1835	2218	1872	-567	41	1729	1729	59	41	26	1538	65	1729	1729	83	65	50	1442	89	1729	1729	
	-564	1884	-1823	2200	32	1729		1541	38	71	23	56	1729		1445	62	95	47	80	1729	1729	
©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	107	110	1289	107	116	1729	1729	83	86	1379	89	92	1729	1729	131	134	1187	137	140	1729	1729	
1729	143	119	74	122	1271	1729	1729	119	2025	-1914	138	1361	1729	1729	167	143	104	146	1169	1729	1729	
1729	89	1283	125	155	77	1729	1729	-1859	1413	101	2055	19	1729	1729	119	1181	149	173	107	1729	1729	
1729	137	113	92	1250	137	1729	1729	2037	49	74	-584	153	1729	1729	155	137	122	1154	161	1729	1729	
	1253	104	149	95	128	1729		1349	-1844	2089	31	104	1729		1157	134	167	119	152	1729	1729	
©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	5x5	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	155	158	1091	161	164	1729	1729	179	182	995	185	188	1729	1729	203	206	899	209	212	1729	1729	
1729	191	167	128	170	1073	1729	1729	215	191	152	194	977	1729	1729	239	215	176	218	881	1729	1729	
1729	143	1085	173	197	131	1729	1729	167	989	197	221	155	1729	1729	191	893	221	245	179	1729	1729	
1729	179	161	146	1058	185	1729	1729	203	185	170	962	209	1729	1729	227	209	194	866	233	1729	1729	
	1061	158	191	143	176	1729		965	182	215	167	200	1729		869	206	239	191	224	1729	1729	
©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	©IJT	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

It contains 15 equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5.

3	mgc			1729	3	mgc		1729	
	-569 1/3	1148 2/3	1149 2/3	1729		-565 1/3	1146 2/3	1147 2/3	1729
	2295 1/3	576 1/3	-1142 2/3	1729		2289 1/3	576 1/3	-1136 2/3	1729
	3	4	1722	1729		5	6	1718	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729

There are only two magic squares order 3 are written. The other 23 are also of same magic sums.

► **Second-Type**

In the first example given above we have fractional values, because the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. To avoid the we can have **semi-magic** squares of order 3. It don't require any condition. See below the example of magic square of order 15 composed of 25 equal **semi-magic** sums of order 3.

15	mgc	15x15	https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	8645								
2	1724	3	6830	-5107	6	16	1696	17	34	1660	35	60	1608	61	8645
1180	-1173	1722	-5106	5119	1716	1695	2436	-2402	1659	11459	-11389	1607	5533	-5411	8645
547	1178	4	5	1717	7	18	-2403	4114	36	-11390	13083	62	-5412	7079	8645
8	1711	10	2212	-2370	1887	19	1690	20	2025	-434	138	63	1602	64	8645
1712	-1691	1708	-496	2398	-173	1689	-1647	1687	-335	513	1551	1601	-1471	1599	8645
9	1709	11	13	1701	15	21	1686	22	39	1650	40	65	1598	66	8645
23	1682	24	27	1674	28	31	-1600	3298	41	1646	42	67	1594	68	8645
1681	-1631	1679	1673	-1615	1671	1666	1665	-1602	1645	-1559	1643	1593	-1455	1591	8645
25	1678	26	29	1670	30	32	1664	33	43	1642	44	69	1590	70	8645
45	1638	46	49	1630	50	53	1622	54	57	-1496	3168	71	1586	72	8645
1637	-1543	1635	1629	-1527	1627	1621	-1511	1619	1614	1613	-1498	1585	-1439	1583	8645
47	1634	48	51	1626	52	55	1618	56	58	1612	59	73	1582	74	8645
75	1578	76	79	1570	80	83	1562	84	87	1554	88	91	-1360	2998	8645
1577	-1423	1575	1569	-1407	1567	1561	-1391	1559	1553	-1375	1551	1546	1545	-1362	8645
77	1574	78	81	1566	82	85	1558	86	89	1550	90	92	1544	93	8645
8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645

Below are examples of few **semi-magic** squares with there **semi-magic** sums. The other can also be calculated in the similar way.

3	mgc		4298	3	mgc		-1606	3	mgc		690	
	2212	-2370	1887	1729	19	1690	20	1729	2025	-434	138	1729
	-496	2398	-173	1729	1689	-1647	1687	1729	-335	513	1551	1729
	13	1701	15	1729	21	1686	22	1729	39	1650	40	1729
	1729	1729	1729	4625	1729	1729	1729	-1606	1729	1729	1729	2578
3	mgc		-1426	3	mgc		-1402	3	mgc		4839	
	49	1630	50	1729	53	1622	54	1729	57	-1496	3168	1729
	1629	-1527	1627	1729	1621	-1511	1619	1729	1614	1613	-1498	1729
	51	1626	52	1729	55	1618	56	1729	58	1612	59	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1426	1729	1729	1729	-1402	1729	1729	1729	1729

This magic square is constructed in such a way that the blocks of orders 6, 9 and 12 in the upper-left corner are magic squares. All the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic** squares. See below

15	mgc														8645	
	2	1724	3	6830	-5107	6	16	1696	17	34	1660	35	60	1608	61	8645
	1180	-1173	1722	-5106	5119	1716	1695	2436	-2402	1659	11459	-11389	1607	5533	-5411	8645
	547	1178	4	5	1717	7	18	-2403	4114	36	-11390	13083	62	-5412	7079	8645
	8	1711	10	2212	-2370	1887	19	1690	20	2025	-434	138	63	1602	64	8645
	1712	-1691	1708	-496	2398	-173	1689	-1647	1687	-335	513	1551	1601	-1471	1599	8645
	9	1709	11	13	1701	15	21	1686	22	39	1650	40	65	1598	66	8645
	23	1682	24	27	1674	28	31	-1600	3298	41	1646	42	67	1594	68	8645
	1681	-1631	1679	1673	-1615	1671	1666	1665	-1602	1645	-1559	1643	1593	-1455	1591	8645
	25	1678	26	29	1670	30	32	1664	33	43	1642	44	69	1590	70	8645
	45	1638	46	49	1630	50	53	1622	54	57	-1496	3168	71	1586	72	8645
	1637	-1543	1635	1629	-1527	1627	1621	-1511	1619	1614	1613	-1498	1585	-1439	1583	8645
	47	1634	48	51	1626	52	55	1618	56	58	1612	59	73	1582	74	8645
	75	1578	76	79	1570	80	83	1562	84	87	1554	88	91	-1360	2998	8645
	1577	-1423	1575	1569	-1407	1567	1561	-1391	1559	1553	-1375	1551	1546	1545	-1362	8645
	77	1574	78	81	1566	82	85	1558	86	89	1550	90	92	1544	93	8645
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645

► Third-Type

Let's consider the following three examples of magic squares of order 15:

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT													25935	
	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	21823	3397	61	25935
	3409	3408	3407	3406	3405	3404	3403	3402	3401	3400	3399	3398	-18365	3396	62	25935
	21413	-17955	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	15389	3432	26	3395	63	25935
	94	3364	3440	3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	3433	-11931	3431	27	3394	64	25935
	93	3365	15203	-11745	2212	5	6	1887	4535	3450	8	3430	28	3393	65	25935
	92	3366	48	3410	1246	3453	3452	1571	-1077	3449	9	3429	29	3392	66	25935
	91	3367	47	3411	8581	-5123	-1724	3455	3456	3448	10	3428	30	3391	67	25935
	90	3368	46	3412	17	3441	6909	1729	-3451	3447	11	3427	31	3390	68	25935
	89	3369	45	3413	16	3442	2	3	5182	-5149	8607	3426	32	3389	69	25935
	88	3370	44	3414	15	3443	-5080	1433	3445	3320	5527	3425	33	3388	70	25935
	87	3371	43	3415	16	3442	8538	2025	13	138	-2069	-11867	15325	3387	71	25935
	86	3372	42	3416	-11809	3418	3419	3420	3421	3422	3423	3424	3423	3386	72	25935
	85	3373	43	3415	15267	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	35	-18221	21679	25935
	84	3374	-18087	3375	3376	3377	3378	3379	3380	3381	3382	3383	3384	3385	3384	25935
	85	3373	21545	83	82	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	74	25935
	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														25935
	47	48	49	50	51	52	53	54	55	56	57	58	25186	59	60	25935
	3411	3410	3409	3408	3407	3406	3405	3404	3403	3402	3401	3400	-21728	3399	3398	25935
	18144	-14686	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	18804	25	26	3397	61	25935
	92	3366	3441	3440	3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	-15346	3433	3432	3396	62	25935
	91	3367	11842	-8384	2212	4	5	6	7982	7	1887	3431	27	3395	63	25935
	90	3368	46	3412	1246	3454	3453	3452	-4524	3451	1571	3430	28	3394	64	25935
	89	3369	45	3413	5156	-1698	-1726	3456	3457	3445	13	3429	29	3393	65	25935
	88	3370	44	3414	16	3442	6912	1729	-3454	3444	14	3428	30	3392	66	25935
	87	3371	43	3415	15	3443	1	2	5184	-1702	5160	3427	31	3391	67	25935
	86	3372	42	3416	3313	1433	-8386	3448	3447	3320	5528	3426	32	3390	68	25935
	85	3373	41	3417	145	2025	11844	10	11	138	-2070	-8468	11926	3389	69	25935
	84	3374	3419	3418	-15196	3419	3420	3421	3422	3423	3424	3425	3424	3388	70	25935
	83	3375	39	40	18654	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	34	-14906	18364	25935
	3377	3376	-21406	3377	3378	3379	3380	3381	3382	3383	3384	3385	3386	3387	3386	25935
	81	82	24864	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	72	25935
	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935

15	mgc	15x15 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														25935
	-1722	3454	3455	3453	5	3449	9	3441	17	3429	29	3413	45	3393	65	25935
	6906	1729	-3448	3452	6	3448	10	3440	18	3428	30	3412	46	3392	66	25935
	3	4	5180	-1718	5176	3447	11	3439	19	3427	31	3411	47	3391	67	25935
	6901	3451	-8607	3450	3450	3446	12	3438	20	3426	32	3410	48	3390	68	25935
	-3443	7	12065	8	8	-5145	8603	3437	21	3425	33	3409	49	3389	69	25935
	18948	3445	3444	3443	-24061	3442	3442	3436	22	3424	34	3408	50	3388	70	25935
	-15490	13	14	15	27519	16	16	-8528	11986	3423	35	3407	51	3387	71	25935
	2980	1246	3434	3433	3432	1571	-7395	3430	3430	3422	36	3406	52	3386	72	25935
	478	2212	24	25	26	1887	10853	28	28	-11843	15301	3405	53	3385	73	25935
	35807	1433	3420	3419	3418	3320	3416	3415	-45457	3414	3414	3404	54	3384	74	25935
	-32349	2025	38	39	40	138	42	43	48915	44	44	-15066	18524	3383	75	25935
	-175	3403	3402	3401	3400	3399	3398	3397	3396	3395	-14727	3394	3394	3382	76	25935
	3633	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	18185	64	64	-18173	21631	25935
	24361	3381	3380	3379	3378	3377	3376	3375	3374	3373	3372	3371	-42302	3370	3370	25935
	-20903	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	45760	88	88	25935
	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935	25935

All the six examples of magic squares of order 15 are with magic sum either 1729 or multiple of 1729. The last three examples are of different types. Except the magic squares of order 3, the others are all **magic rectangles** of equal width, i.e., 2×1729 . The lengths are proportional according to values of the width. In all the three example the magic sum is $S_{15 \times 15} := 25935 = 15 \times 1729$.

All the six examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]. The last three examples are little different.

15 Magic Squares of Order 16

Let's consider a following magic square of order 16 having the magic sum $S_{16 \times 16} := 6916 := 4 \times 1729$:

► First-Type

16	mgc	16x16 https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	6916				
2	1725	-2	4	8	1719	-8	10	14	1713	-14	16	20	1707	-20	22	6916
7	5	6	1711	13	11	12	1693	19	17	18	1675	25	23	24	1657	6916
0	-1	1719	11	6	5	1701	17	12	11	1683	23	18	17	1665	29	6916
1720	0	6	3	1702	-6	24	9	1684	-12	42	15	1666	-18	60	21	6916
2212	-485	-1885	1887	32	1695	-32	34	38	1689	-38	40	2025	-298	-136	138	6916
31	29	30	1639	37	35	36	1621	43	41	42	1603	49	47	48	1585	6916
1883	2209	-539	-1824	30	29	1629	41	36	35	1611	47	134	2022	-388	-39	6916
-2397	-24	4123	27	1630	-30	96	33	1612	-36	114	39	-479	-42	2205	45	6916
50	1677	-50	52	56	1671	-56	58	62	1665	-62	64	68	1659	-68	70	6916
55	53	54	1567	61	59	60	1549	67	65	66	1531	73	71	72	1513	6916
48	47	1575	59	54	53	1557	65	60	59	1539	71	66	65	1521	77	6916
1576	-48	150	51	1558	-54	168	57	1540	-60	186	63	1522	-66	204	69	6916
74	1653	-74	76	80	1647	-80	82	86	1641	-86	88	92	1635	-92	94	6916
79	77	78	1495	85	83	84	1477	91	89	90	1459	97	95	96	1441	6916
72	71	1503	83	78	77	1485	89	84	83	1467	95	90	89	1449	101	6916
1504	-72	222	75	1486	-78	240	81	1468	-84	258	87	1450	-90	276	93	6916
6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916

► Second-Type

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/				https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/				©IJT	13832					
59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	11258	1657	72	13832
1670	1669	1668	1667	1666	1665	1664	1663	1662	1661	1660	1659	1658	-9529	1656	73	13832
10775	-9046	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	8384	1695	34	1655	74	13832
108	1621	1704	1703	1702	1701	1700	1699	1698	1697	1696	-6655	1694	35	1654	75	13832
107	1622	8157	-6428	2212	8	9	10	1887	1061	1717	12	1693	36	1653	76	13832
106	1623	58	1671	-483	1721	1720	1719	-158	668	1716	13	1692	37	1652	77	13832
105	1624	57	1672	5075	-3346	3454	1	2	1	1715	14	1691	38	1651	78	13832
104	1625	56	1673	24	1705	-1725	1728	1727	1728	1714	15	1690	39	1650	79	13832
103	1626	55	1674	23	1706	3	4	-1	3452	1713	16	1689	40	1649	80	13832
102	1627	54	1675	22	1707	1726	1725	1730	-1723	-3388	5117	1688	41	1648	81	13832
101	1628	53	1676	21	1708	-3324	-296	1710	1711	1591	3795	1687	42	1647	82	13832
100	1629	52	1677	22	1707	5053	2025	19	18	138	-2066	-6574	8303	1646	83	13832
99	1630	51	1678	-6500	1679	1680	1681	1682	1683	1684	1685	1686	1685	1645	84	13832
98	1631	52	1677	8229	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	-9360	11089	13832
97	1632	-9202	1633	1634	1635	1636	1637	1638	1639	1640	1641	1642	1643	1644	1643	13832
98	1631	10931	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	13832
13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														13832
66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	12739	78	79	13832
1663	1662	1661	1660	1659	1658	1657	1656	1655	1654	1653	1652	1651	-11010	1651	1650	13832
9175	-7446	2212	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	5942	41	1887	1649	80	13832
114	1615	-483	1696	1695	1694	1693	1692	1691	1690	1689	-4213	1688	-158	1648	81	13832
113	1616	6482	-4753	14	15	16	17	18	6797	19	20	1686	43	1647	82	13832
112	1617	65	1664	1715	1714	1713	1712	1711	-5068	1710	1709	1685	44	1646	83	13832
111	1618	64	1665	3368	-1639	3427	-1698	12	1717	1708	21	1684	45	1645	84	13832
110	1619	63	1666	31	1698	10	1719	13	1716	1707	22	1683	46	1644	85	13832
109	1620	62	1667	30	1699	11	1718	8	1721	1706	23	1682	47	1643	86	13832
108	1621	61	1668	29	1700	10	1719	3425	-1696	-1663	3392	1681	48	1642	87	13832
107	1622	60	1669	29	28	6734	27	26	25	24	23	1680	49	1641	88	13832
106	1623	59	1670	1700	1701	-5005	1702	1703	1704	1705	1706	-4865	6594	1640	89	13832
105	1624	1550	-296	-7966	1672	1673	1674	1675	1676	1677	1678	1591	3770	1639	90	13832
104	1625	179	2025	9695	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	138	-2041	-7710	9439	13832
1627	1626	-10648	1627	1628	1629	1630	1631	1632	1633	1634	1635	1636	1637	1638	1637	13832
102	103	12377	102	101	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	92	13832
13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832

16	mgc	16x16 https://numbers-magic.com/ https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT														13832
3452	1	4	1	13	1716	1698	31	1668	61	1626	103	1572	157	1506	223	13832
-1723	1728	1725	1728	16	1713	1695	34	1665	64	1623	106	1569	160	1503	226	13832
7	10	-5	3446	19	1710	1692	37	1662	67	1620	109	1566	163	1500	229	13832
1722	1719	1734	-1717	3410	-1681	1689	40	1659	70	1617	112	1563	166	1497	232	13832
5161	1707	1704	-6787	1701	1701	1686	43	1656	73	1614	115	1560	169	1494	235	13832
-3432	22	25	8516	28	28	-3273	5002	1653	76	1611	118	1557	172	1491	238	13832
-5586	-483	1680	1677	-158	6444	1671	1671	1650	79	1608	121	1554	175	1488	241	13832
7315	2212	49	52	1887	-4715	58	58	-4697	6426	1605	124	1551	178	1485	244	13832
1638	1647	1644	1641	1638	1635	1632	-6088	1629	1629	1602	127	1548	181	1482	247	13832
91	82	85	88	91	94	97	7817	100	100	-5881	7610	1545	184	1479	250	13832
1338	-296	1596	1593	1591	1589	1584	1581	1578	-4930	1575	1575	1542	187	1476	253	13832
391	2025	133	136	138	140	145	148	151	6659	154	154	-6753	8482	1473	256	13832
1524	1539	1536	1533	1530	1527	1524	1521	1518	1515	1512	-7694	1509	1509	1470	259	13832
205	190	193	196	199	202	205	208	211	214	217	9423	220	220	-7241	8970	13832
-12614	1467	1464	1461	1458	1455	1452	1449	1446	1443	1440	1437	1434	6178	1431	1431	13832
14343	262	265	268	271	274	277	280	283	286	289	292	295	-4449	298	298	13832
13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832	13832

• Details

The first example is composed of 16 equal sums magic square of order 4 with magic sum $S_{4 \times 4} := 1729$. See below the magic sum of these 16 magic square

4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729
	2	1725	-2	4	1729		8	1719	-8	10	1729		14	1713	-14	16	1729		20	1707	-20	22	1729	
	7	5	6	1711	1729		13	11	12	1693	1729		19	17	18	1675	1729		25	23	24	1657	1729	
	0	-1	1719	11	1729		6	5	1701	17	1729		12	11	1683	23	1729		18	17	1665	29	1729	
	1720	0	6	3	1729		1702	-6	24	9	1729		1684	-12	42	15	1729		1666	-18	60	21	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729
	2212	-485	-1885	1887	1729		32	1695	-32	34	1729		38	1689	-38	40	1729		2025	-298	-136	138	1729	
	31	29	30	1639	1729		37	35	36	1621	1729		43	41	42	1603	1729		49	47	48	1585	1729	
	1883	2209	-539	-1824	1729		30	29	1629	41	1729		36	35	1611	47	1729		134	2022	-388	-39	1729	
	-2397	-24	4123	27	1729		1630	-30	96	33	1729		1612	-36	114	39	1729		-479	-42	2205	45	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729
	50	1677	-50	52	1729		56	1671	-56	58	1729		62	1665	-62	64	1729		68	1659	-68	70	1729	
	55	53	54	1567	1729		61	59	60	1549	1729		67	65	66	1531	1729		73	71	72	1513	1729	
	48	47	1575	59	1729		54	53	1557	65	1729		60	59	1539	71	1729		66	65	1521	77	1729	
	1576	-48	150	51	1729		1558	-54	168	57	1729		1540	-60	186	63	1729		1522	-66	204	69	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729	4	mgc			1729
	74	1653	-74	76	1729		80	1647	-80	82	1729		86	1641	-86	88	1729		92	1635	-92	94	1729	
	79	77	78	1495	1729		85	83	84	1477	1729		91	89	90	1459	1729		97	95	96	1441	1729	
	72	71	1503	83	1729		78	77	1485	89	1729		84	83	1467	95	1729		90	89	1449	101	1729	
	1504	-72	222	75	1729		1486	-78	240	81	1729		1468	-84	258	87	1729		1450	-90	276	93	1729	
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

The last three examples of magic squares of order 16 based on **magic rectangles**. The second and third are **double-digit** magic squares, while the third one is **cornered-type** magic square. The width of the strip is always the same, i.e., 1729. The change is only in the lengths. The magic sum for all three magic squares is the same, i.e., $S_{16 \times 16} := 13832 = 8 \times 1729$.

All 4 examples contain the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

16 Magic Squares of Order 17

Below are three magic squares of order 17 with the magic sum as multiple of 1729.

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	29393										
205	208	211	214	217	220	223	226	229	232	235	238	241	244	22792	3211	247	29393
3253	3250	3247	3244	3241	3238	3235	3232	3229	3226	3223	3220	3217	3214	-19334	3208	250	29393
21106	-17648	91	94	97	100	103	106	109	112	115	118	17974	3337	121	3205	253	29393
364	3094	3367	3364	3361	3358	3355	3352	3349	3346	3343	3340	-14516	3334	124	3202	256	29393
361	3097	15287	-11829	2212	28	31	34	37	40	9721	1571	1887	3331	127	3199	259	29393
358	3100	202	3256	1246	3430	3427	3424	3421	3418	-6263	3412	46	3328	130	3196	262	29393
355	3103	199	3259	13458	-10000	1	4	8623	7	10	3409	49	3325	133	3193	265	29393
352	3106	196	3262	88	3370	37	13	-26	16	8605	3406	52	3322	136	3190	268	29393
349	3109	193	3265	85	3373	-11	8617	19	43	-23	3403	55	3319	139	3187	271	29393
346	3112	190	3268	82	3376	25	7	-8	8590	31	3400	58	3316	142	3184	274	29393
343	3115	187	3271	79	3379	8593	4	37	-11	22	-6498	9956	3313	145	3181	277	29393
340	3118	2025	1433	76	3382	-10433	3385	3388	3391	3394	3397	5581	3320	138	3178	280	29393
337	3121	181	3277	-1765	5223	13891	73	70	67	64	61	-2123	-14226	17684	3175	283	29393
334	3124	178	3280	-13940	3283	3286	3289	3292	3295	3298	3301	3304	3307	3304	3172	286	29393
331	3127	181	3277	17398	175	172	169	166	163	160	157	154	151	154	-18746	22204	29393
328	3130	-18194	3133	3136	3139	3142	3145	3148	3151	3154	3157	3160	3163	3166	3169	3166	29393
331	3127	21652	325	322	319	316	313	310	307	304	301	298	295	292	289	292	29393
29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393

17	mgc	17x17	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	29393										
70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	28153	84	85	29393
3388	3387	3386	3385	3384	3383	3382	3381	3380	3379	3378	3377	3376	3375	-24695	3374	3373	29393
21067	-17609	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	22027	42	43	3372	86	29393
123	3335	3426	3425	3424	3423	3422	3421	3420	3419	3418	3417	-18569	3416	3415	3371	87	29393
122	3336	10932	-7474	10	11	12	13	14	15	15453	16	17	3414	44	3370	88	29393
121	3337	2212	1246	3448	3447	3446	3445	3444	3443	-11995	3442	3441	1571	1887	3369	89	29393
120	3338	68	3390	8527	-5069	2	3	8631	4	5	3434	24	3412	46	3368	90	29393
119	3339	67	3391	28	3430	14	6	-7	7	8625	3433	25	3411	47	3367	91	29393
118	3340	66	3392	29	3429	-2	8629	8	16	-6	3432	26	3410	48	3366	92	29393
117	3341	65	3393	30	3428	10	4	-1	8620	12	3431	27	3409	49	3365	93	29393
116	3342	64	3394	31	3427	8621	3	14	-2	9	-5085	8543	3408	50	3364	94	29393
115	3343	2025	1433	3441	3440	-11939	3439	3438	3437	3436	3435	3434	3320	138	3363	95	29393
114	3344	62	3396	17	18	15397	19	20	21	22	23	24	-9794	13252	3362	96	29393
113	3345	3398	3397	-18341	3398	3399	3400	3401	3402	3403	3404	3405	3406	3405	3361	97	29393
112	3346	60	61	21799	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	53	-17921	21379	29393
3348	3347	-24263	3348	3349	3350	3351	3352	3353	3354	3355	3356	3357	3358	3359	3360	3359	29393
110	111	27721	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	99	29393
29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393

17	mgc	17x17														29393		
		https://numbers-magic.com/							https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/							@IJTANEJA	©IJT	
	-1726	3456	3457	3455	3	3451	7	3443	15	3431	27	3415	43	3395	63	3371	87	29393
	6912	1729	-3454	3454	4	3450	8	3442	16	3430	28	3414	44	3394	64	3370	88	29393
	1	2	5184	-1722	5180	3449	9	3441	17	3429	29	3413	45	3393	65	3369	89	29393
	6907	3453	-8619	3452	3452	3448	10	3440	18	3428	30	3412	46	3392	66	3368	90	29393
	-3449	5	12077	6	6	-5153	8611	3439	19	3427	31	3411	47	3391	67	3367	91	29393
	16767	1246	3446	1571	-17815	3444	3444	3438	20	3426	32	3410	48	3390	68	3366	92	29393
	-13309	2212	12	1887	21273	14	14	-8540	11998	3425	33	3409	49	3389	69	3365	93	29393
	1291	1433	3436	3320	3434	3433	-7650	3432	3432	3424	34	3408	50	3388	70	3364	94	29393
	2167	2025	22	138	24	25	11108	26	26	-11859	15317	3407	51	3387	71	3363	95	29393
	31446	3423	3422	3421	3420	3419	3418	3417	-43199	3416	3416	3406	52	3386	72	3362	96	29393
	-27988	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	46657	42	42	-15086	18544	3385	73	3361	97	29393
	1685	3405	3404	3403	3402	3401	3400	3399	3398	3397	-16609	3396	3396	3384	74	3360	98	29393
	1773	53	54	55	56	57	58	59	60	61	20067	62	62	-18197	21655	3359	99	29393
	24729	3383	3382	3381	3380	3379	3378	3377	3376	3375	3374	3373	-42696	3372	3372	3358	100	29393
	-21271	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	46154	86	86	-21168	24626	29393
	1647	3357	3356	3355	3354	3353	3352	3351	3350	3349	3348	3347	3346	3345	-22505	3344	3344	29393
	1811	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	25963	114	114	29393
	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393	29393

• Details

All the three examples are with magic sum as multiple of 1729, i.e., $S_{17 \times 17} := 29393 = 17 \times 1729$. All 3 examples contain the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four entries 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

17 Magic Squares of Order 18

Let's consider following 5 magic squares of order 18 having the magic sum 1729:

► First-Type

1	mgc	18x18 https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA	©IJT	31122									
	-1726	3456	3457	-1722	3454	3455	-1718	3452	3453	-1714	3450	3451	-1710	3448	3449	-1706	3446	3447	31122
	6912	1729	-3454	6906	1729	-3448	6900	1729	-3442	6894	1729	-3436	6888	1729	-3430	6882	1729	-3424	31122
	1	2	5184	3	4	5180	5	6	5176	7	8	5172	9	10	5168	11	12	5164	31122
	-1702	3444	3445	-1698	3442	3443	-1694	3440	3441	-1690	3438	3439	-1686	3436	3437	-1682	3434	3435	31122
	6876	1729	-3418	6870	1729	-3412	6864	1729	-3406	6858	1729	-3400	6852	1729	-3394	6846	1729	-3388	31122
	13	14	5160	15	16	5156	17	18	5152	19	20	5148	21	22	5144	23	24	5140	31122
	-1678	3432	3433	2370	1571	1246	-1670	3428	3429	-1666	3426	3427	434	3320	1433	-1658	3422	3423	31122
	6840	1729	-3382	605	1729	2853	6828	1729	-3370	6822	1729	-3364	2728	1729	730	6810	1729	-3352	31122
	25	26	5136	2212	1887	1088	29	30	5128	31	32	5124	2025	138	3024	35	36	5116	31122
	-1654	3420	3421	-1650	3418	3419	-1646	3416	3417	-1642	3414	3415	-1638	3412	3413	-1634	3410	3411	31122
	6804	1729	-3346	6798	1729	-3340	6792	1729	-3334	6786	1729	-3328	6780	1729	-3322	6774	1729	-3316	31122
	37	38	5112	39	40	5108	41	42	5104	43	44	5100	45	46	5096	47	48	5092	31122
	-1630	3408	3409	-1626	3406	3407	-1622	3404	3405	-1618	3402	3403	-1614	3400	3401	-1610	3398	3399	31122
	6768	1729	-3310	6762	1729	-3304	6756	1729	-3298	6750	1729	-3292	6744	1729	-3286	6738	1729	-3280	31122
	49	50	5088	51	52	5084	53	54	5080	55	56	5076	57	58	5072	59	60	5068	31122
	-1606	3396	3397	-1602	3394	3395	-1598	3392	3393	-1594	3390	3391	-1590	3388	3389	-1586	3386	3387	31122
	6732	1729	-3274	6726	1729	-3268	6720	1729	-3262	6714	1729	-3256	6708	1729	-3250	6702	1729	-3244	31122
	61	62	5064	63	64	5060	65	66	5056	67	68	5052	69	70	5048	71	72	5044	31122
	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122	31122

This magic square is composed of equal sums magic squares of order 3. Since in this case the magic square of order 3 should be a multiple of 3, that's why we consider the sum of each magic sum of order 3 as $S_{3 \times 3} := 3 \times 1729 = 5187$ resulting in sum of magic square of order 18 as $S_{18 \times 18} := 18 \times 1729 = 31122$. See below few examples with magic sum of order 3:

3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187					
	2370	1571	1246	5187	-1670	3428	3429	5187	-1666	3426	3427	5187	434	3320	1433	5187
	605	1729	2853	5187	6828	1729	-3370	5187	6822	1729	-3364	5187	2728	1729	730	5187
	2212	1887	1088	5187	29	30	5128	5187	31	32	5124	5187	2025	138	3024	5187
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187
3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187	3	mgc	5187					
	-1626	3406	3407	5187	-1622	3404	3405	5187	-1618	3402	3403	5187	-1614	3400	3401	5187
	6762	1729	-3304	5187	6756	1729	-3298	5187	6750	1729	-3292	5187	6744	1729	-3286	5187
	51	52	5084	5187	53	54	5080	5187	55	56	5076	5187	57	58	5072	5187
	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187

► **Second-Type**

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT															10374	
2	1724	3	6830	-5107	6	16	1696	17	34	1660	35	60	1608	61	94	1540	95	10374
-5093	5100	1722	-5106	5119	1716	1695	8382	-8348	1659	5556	-5486	1607	7721	-7599	1539	16689	-16499	10374
6820	-5095	4	5	1717	7	18	-8349	10060	36	-5487	7180	62	-7600	9267	96	-16500	18133	10374
8	1711	10	12	1703	14	19	1690	20	37	1654	38	63	1602	64	97	1534	98	10374
1712	-1691	1708	1704	-1675	1700	1689	-1647	1687	1653	-1575	1651	1601	-1471	1599	1533	-1335	1531	10374
9	1709	11	13	1701	15	21	1686	22	39	1650	40	65	1598	66	99	1530	100	10374
23	1682	24	2212	-2370	1887	31	-1600	3298	41	1646	42	2025	-434	138	101	1526	102	10374
1681	-1631	1679	-512	2429	-188	1666	1665	-1602	1645	-1559	1643	-365	573	1521	1525	-1319	1523	10374
25	1678	26	29	1670	30	32	1664	33	43	1642	44	69	1590	70	103	1522	104	10374
45	1638	46	49	1630	50	53	1622	54	57	-1496	3168	71	1586	72	105	1518	106	10374
1637	-1543	1635	1629	-1527	1627	1621	-1511	1619	1614	1613	-1498	1585	-1439	1583	1517	-1303	1515	10374
47	1634	48	51	1626	52	55	1618	56	58	1612	59	73	1582	74	107	1514	108	10374
75	1578	76	79	1570	80	83	1562	84	87	1554	88	91	-1360	2998	109	1510	110	10374
1577	-1423	1575	1569	-1407	1567	1561	-1391	1559	1553	-1375	1551	1546	1545	-1362	1509	-1287	1507	10374
77	1574	78	81	1566	82	85	1558	86	89	1550	90	92	1544	93	111	1506	112	10374
113	1502	114	117	1494	118	121	1486	122	125	1478	126	129	1470	130	133	-1192	2788	10374
1501	-1271	1499	1493	-1255	1491	1485	-1239	1483	1477	-1223	1475	1469	-1207	1467	1462	1461	-1194	10374
115	1498	116	119	1490	120	123	1482	124	127	1474	128	131	1466	132	134	1460	135	10374
10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

Instead of considering magic square of order 3, here we considered equal sums as **semi-magic** squares of order 3. In this case, we don't magic sum as multiple of 3. In this case the **semi-magic** sums of order 3 are $SM_{3 \times 3} := 1729$ resulting in magic square of order 18 as $S_{18 \times 18} := 6 \times 1729 = 10374$. See below few examples of **semi-magic** sums of order 3:

3	semi		4345	3	semi		4995	3	semi		-1474	3	semi		780	
	2212	-2370	1887	1729	31	-1600	3298	1729	41	1646	42	1729	2025	-434	138	1729
	-512	2429	-188	1729	1666	1665	-1602	1729	1645	-1559	1643	1729	-365	573	1521	1729
	29	1670	30	1729	32	1664	33	1729	43	1642	44	1729	69	1590	70	1729
	1729	1729	1729	4671	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	-1474	1729	1729	1729	2668
3	semi		-1018	3	semi		-994	3	semi		-970	3	semi		-946	
	117	1494	118	1729	121	1486	122	1729	125	1478	126	1729	129	1470	130	1729
	1493	-1255	1491	1729	1485	-1239	1483	1729	1477	-1223	1475	1729	1469	-1207	1467	1729
	119	1490	120	1729	123	1482	124	1729	127	1474	128	1729	131	1466	132	1729
	1729	1729	1729	-1018	1729	1729	1729	-994	1729	1729	1729	-970	1729	1729	1729	-946

Moreover, this example is written in such a way that magic squares of orders 6, 9, 12 and 15 are at the upper-left corner. See below

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja			https://indertaneja.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA			©IJT			10374		
2	1724	3	6830	-5107	6	16	1696	17	34	1660	35	60	1608	61	94	1540	95	10374	
-5093	5100	1722	-5106	5119	1716	1695	8382	-8348	1659	5556	-5486	1607	7721	-7599	1539	16689	-16499	10374	
6820	-5095	4	5	1717	7	18	-8349	10060	36	-5487	7180	62	-7600	9267	96	-16500	18133	10374	
8	1711	10	12	1703	14	19	1690	20	37	1654	38	63	1602	64	97	1534	98	10374	
1712	-1691	1708	1704	-1675	1700	1689	-1647	1687	1653	-1575	1651	1601	-1471	1599	1533	-1335	1531	10374	
9	1709	11	13	1701	15	21	1686	22	39	1650	40	65	1598	66	99	1530	100	10374	
23	1682	24	2212	-2370	1887	31	-1600	3298	41	1646	42	2025	-434	138	101	1526	102	10374	
1681	-1631	1679	-512	2429	-188	1666	1665	-1602	1645	-1559	1643	-365	573	1521	1525	-1319	1523	10374	
25	1678	26	29	1670	30	32	1664	33	43	1642	44	69	1590	70	103	1522	104	10374	
45	1638	46	49	1630	50	53	1622	54	57	-1496	3168	71	1586	72	105	1518	106	10374	
1637	-1543	1635	1629	-1527	1627	1621	-1511	1619	1614	1613	-1498	1585	-1439	1583	1517	-1303	1515	10374	
47	1634	48	51	1626	52	55	1618	56	58	1612	59	73	1582	74	107	1514	108	10374	
75	1578	76	79	1570	80	83	1562	84	87	1554	88	91	-1360	2998	109	1510	110	10374	
1577	-1423	1575	1569	-1407	1567	1561	-1391	1559	1553	-1375	1551	1546	1545	-1362	1509	-1287	1507	10374	
77	1574	78	81	1566	82	85	1558	86	89	1550	90	92	1544	93	111	1506	112	10374	
113	1502	114	117	1494	118	121	1486	122	125	1478	126	129	1470	130	133	-1192	2788	10374	
1501	-1271	1499	1493	-1255	1491	1485	-1239	1483	1477	-1223	1475	1469	-1207	1467	1462	1461	-1194	10374	
115	1498	116	119	1490	120	123	1482	124	127	1474	128	131	1466	132	134	1460	135	10374	
10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

► Third-Type

The following example is formed by equal sums magic squares of order 6 resulting in magic square of order 18

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja			https://indertaneja.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA			©IJT			5187		
1934	5	8	12	16	-246	92	28	31	35	39	1504	185	51	54	58	62	1319	5187	
1664	6	9	13	17	20	1549	29	32	36	40	43	1434	52	55	59	63	66	5187	
-4088	5754	10	14	18	21	10	1564	33	37	41	44	-2014	3496	56	60	64	67	5187	
2212	-4337	1933	15	19	1887	25	1488	91	38	42	45	2025	-744	184	61	65	138	5187	
3	7	-242	2198	-260	23	26	30	1508	-1371	1490	46	49	53	1323	-1070	1305	69	5187	
4	294	11	-523	1919	24	27	-1410	34	2954	77	47	50	-1179	57	2561	170	70	5187	
138	74	77	81	85	1274	161	97	100	104	108	1159	184	120	123	127	131	1044	5187	
1319	75	78	82	86	89	1204	98	101	105	109	112	1089	121	124	128	132	135	5187	
56	1334	79	83	87	90	79	1219	102	106	110	113	102	1104	125	129	133	136	5187	
71	1258	137	84	88	91	94	1143	160	107	111	114	117	1028	183	130	134	137	5187	
72	76	1278	-1049	1260	92	95	99	1163	-888	1145	115	118	122	1048	-727	1030	138	5187	
73	-1088	80	2448	123	93	96	-927	103	2195	146	116	119	-766	126	1942	169	139	5187	
207	143	146	150	154	929	230	166	169	173	177	814	253	189	192	196	200	699	5187	
974	144	147	151	155	158	859	167	170	174	178	181	744	190	193	197	201	204	5187	
125	989	148	152	156	159	148	874	171	175	179	182	171	759	194	198	202	205	5187	
140	913	206	153	157	160	163	798	229	176	180	183	186	683	252	199	203	206	5187	
141	145	933	-566	915	161	164	168	818	-405	800	184	187	191	703	-244	685	207	5187	
142	-605	149	1689	192	162	165	-444	172	1436	215	185	188	-283	195	1183	238	208	5187	
5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187	5187

Since the above example is formed by 9 equal sums magic squares of order 6. See below the individual sums of these magic squares:

6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729												
1934	5	8	12	16	-246	1729	92	28	31	35	39	1504	1729	185	51	54	58	62	1319	1729
1664	6	9	13	17	20	1729	1549	29	32	36	40	43	1729	1434	52	55	59	63	66	1729
-4088	5754	10	14	18	21	1729	10	1564	33	37	41	44	1729	-2014	3496	56	60	64	67	1729
2212	-4337	1933	15	19	1887	1729	25	1488	91	38	42	45	1729	2025	-744	184	61	65	138	1729
3	7	-242	2198	-260	23	1729	26	30	1508	-1371	1490	46	1729	49	53	1323	-1070	1305	69	1729
4	294	11	-523	1919	24	1729	27	-1410	34	2954	77	47	1729	50	-1179	57	2561	170	70	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729												
138	74	77	81	85	1274	1729	161	97	100	104	108	1159	1729	184	120	123	127	131	1044	1729
1319	75	78	82	86	89	1729	1204	98	101	105	109	112	1729	1089	121	124	128	132	135	1729
56	1334	79	83	87	90	1729	79	1219	102	106	110	113	1729	102	1104	125	129	133	136	1729
71	1258	137	84	88	91	1729	94	1143	160	107	111	114	1729	117	1028	183	130	134	137	1729
72	76	1278	-1049	1260	92	1729	95	99	1163	-888	1145	115	1729	118	122	1048	-727	1030	138	1729
73	-1088	80	2448	123	93	1729	96	-927	103	2195	146	116	1729	119	-766	126	1942	169	139	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729	6	mgc	1729												
207	143	146	150	154	929	1729	230	166	169	173	177	814	1729	253	189	192	196	200	699	1729
974	144	147	151	155	158	1729	859	167	170	174	178	181	1729	744	190	193	197	201	204	1729
125	989	148	152	156	159	1729	148	874	171	175	179	182	1729	171	759	194	198	202	205	1729
140	913	206	153	157	160	1729	163	798	229	176	180	183	1729	186	683	252	199	203	206	1729
141	145	933	-566	915	161	1729	164	168	818	-405	800	184	1729	187	191	703	-244	685	207	1729
142	-605	149	1689	192	162	1729	165	-444	172	1436	215	185	1729	188	-283	195	1183	238	208	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

► Forth-Type

The following example order 18 is also formed by equal sums magic square of order 6, but the difference is that each block of order 6 is formed by 4 equal sums semi-magic squares of order 3 resulting in a magic square of order 6:

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT												10374				
2	1722	5	6702	-4987	14	44	1638	47	6240	-4567	56	86	1554	89	5778	-4147	98	10374
-4945	4958	1716	-4984	5015	1698	-4525	4622	1632	-4564	4679	1614	-4105	4286	1548	-4144	4343	1530	10374
6672	-4951	8	11	1701	17	6210	-4531	50	53	1617	59	5748	-4111	92	95	1533	101	10374
20	1683	26	32	1659	38	62	1599	68	74	1575	80	104	1515	110	116	1491	122	10374
1686	-1631	1674	1662	-1583	1650	1602	-1463	1590	1578	-1415	1566	1518	-1295	1506	1494	-1247	1482	10374
23	1677	29	35	1653	41	65	1593	71	77	1569	83	107	1509	113	119	1485	125	10374
2212	-614	131	1822	-1980	1887	170	1386	173	4854	-3307	182	2025	-511	215	4564	-2973	138	10374
-1601	1866	1464	-230	2260	-301	-3265	3614	1380	-3304	3671	1362	-1032	1465	1296	-3056	3421	1364	10374
1118	477	134	137	1449	143	4824	-3271	176	179	1365	185	736	775	218	221	1281	227	10374
146	1431	152	158	1407	164	188	1347	194	200	1323	206	230	1263	236	242	1239	248	10374
1434	-1127	1422	1410	-1079	1398	1350	-959	1338	1326	-911	1314	1266	-791	1254	1242	-743	1230	10374
149	1425	155	161	1401	167	191	1341	197	203	1317	209	233	1257	239	245	1233	251	10374
254	1218	257	3930	-2467	266	296	1134	299	3468	-2047	308	338	1050	341	3006	-1627	350	10374
-2425	2942	1212	-2464	2999	1194	-2005	2606	1128	-2044	2663	1110	-1585	2270	1044	-1624	2327	1026	10374
3900	-2431	260	263	1197	269	3438	-2011	302	305	1113	311	2976	-1591	344	347	1029	353	10374
272	1179	278	284	1155	290	314	1095	320	326	1071	332	356	1011	362	368	987	374	10374
1182	-623	1170	1158	-575	1146	1098	-455	1086	1074	-407	1062	1014	-287	1002	990	-239	978	10374
275	1173	281	287	1149	293	317	1089	323	329	1065	335	359	1005	365	371	981	377	10374
10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374	10374

In this case, the semi-magic sums of order 3 are of equal sum forming 9 equal sums magic squares of order 6. See below the magic sums of orders 3 and 6.

3 mgc		3115	3 mgc		4284		
2212	-614	131	1729	1822	-1980	1887	1729
-1601	1866	1464	1729	-230	2260	-301	1729
1118	477	134	1729	137	1449	143	1729
1729	1729	1729	4212	1729	1729	1729	4225
3 mgc		2416	3 mgc		3780		
2025	-511	215	1729	4564	-2973	138	1729
-1032	1465	1296	1729	-3056	3421	1364	1729
736	775	218	1729	221	1281	227	1729
1729	1729	1729	3708	1729	1729	1729	8212

6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458												
2	1722	5	6702	-4987	14	3458	44	1638	47	6240	-4567	56	3458	86	1554	89	5778	-4147	98	3458
-4945	4958	1716	-4984	5015	1698	3458	-4525	4622	1632	-4564	4679	1614	3458	-4105	4286	1548	-4144	4343	1530	3458
6672	-4951	8	11	1701	17	3458	6210	-4531	50	53	1617	59	3458	5748	-4111	92	95	1533	101	3458
20	1683	26	32	1659	38	3458	62	1599	68	74	1575	80	3458	104	1515	110	116	1491	122	3458
1686	-1631	1674	1662	-1583	1650	3458	1602	-1463	1590	1578	-1415	1566	3458	1518	-1295	1506	1494	-1247	1482	3458
23	1677	29	35	1653	41	3458	65	1593	71	77	1569	83	3458	107	1509	113	119	1485	125	3458
3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458
6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458												
2212	-614	131	1822	-1980	1887	3458	170	1386	173	4854	-3307	182	3458	2025	-511	215	4564	-2973	138	3458
-1601	1866	1464	-230	2260	-301	3458	-3265	3614	1380	-3304	3671	1362	3458	-1032	1465	1296	-3056	3421	1364	3458
1118	477	134	137	1449	143	3458	4824	-3271	176	179	1365	185	3458	736	775	218	221	1281	227	3458
146	1431	152	158	1407	164	3458	188	1347	194	200	1323	206	3458	230	1263	236	242	1239	248	3458
1434	-1127	1422	1410	-1079	1398	3458	1350	-959	1338	1326	-911	1314	3458	1266	-791	1254	1242	-743	1230	3458
149	1425	155	161	1401	167	3458	191	1341	197	203	1317	209	3458	233	1257	239	245	1233	251	3458
3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458
6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458	6 mgc		3458												
254	1218	257	3930	-2467	266	3458	296	1134	299	3468	-2047	308	3458	338	1050	341	3006	-1627	350	3458
-2425	2942	1212	-2464	2999	1194	3458	-2005	2606	1128	-2044	2663	1110	3458	-1585	2270	1044	-1624	2327	1026	3458
3900	-2431	260	263	1197	269	3458	3438	-2011	302	305	1113	311	3458	2976	-1591	344	347	1029	353	3458
272	1179	278	284	1155	290	3458	314	1095	320	326	1071	332	3458	356	1011	362	368	987	374	3458
1182	-623	1170	1158	-575	1146	3458	1098	-455	1086	1074	-407	1062	3458	1014	-287	1002	990	-239	978	3458
275	1173	281	287	1149	293	3458	317	1089	323	329	1065	335	3458	359	1005	365	371	981	377	3458
3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458	3458

► Fifth-Type

18	mgc	18x18 https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																7780.5
751.5	-4478	766.5	765.5	764.5	763.5	762.5	761.5	760.5	759.5	758.5	757.5	756.5	755.5	754.5	753.5	752.5	114	7780.5
749.5	2	1725	-2	4	8	1719	-8	10	14	1713	-14	16	20	1707	-20	22	115	7780.5
748.5	7	5	6	1711	13	11	12	1693	19	17	18	1675	25	23	24	1657	116	7780.5
747.5	0	-1	1719	11	6	5	1701	17	12	11	1683	23	18	17	1665	29	117	7780.5
746.5	1720	0	6	3	1702	-6	24	9	1684	-12	42	15	1666	-18	60	21	118	7780.5
745.5	2212	-485	-1885	1887	32	1695	-32	34	38	1689	-38	40	2025	-298	-136	138	119	7780.5
744.5	31	29	30	1639	37	35	36	1621	43	41	42	1603	49	47	48	1585	120	7780.5
743.5	1883	2209	-539	-1824	30	29	1629	41	36	35	1611	47	134	2022	-388	-39	121	7780.5
742.5	-2397	-24	4123	27	1630	-30	96	33	1612	-36	114	39	-479	-42	2205	45	122	7780.5
741.5	50	1677	-50	52	56	1671	-56	58	62	1665	-62	64	68	1659	-68	70	123	7780.5
740.5	55	53	54	1567	61	59	60	1549	67	65	66	1531	73	71	72	1513	124	7780.5
739.5	48	47	1575	59	54	53	1557	65	60	59	1539	71	66	65	1521	77	125	7780.5
738.5	1576	-48	150	51	1558	-54	168	57	1540	-60	186	63	1522	-66	204	69	126	7780.5
737.5	74	1653	-74	76	80	1647	-80	82	86	1641	-86	88	92	1635	-92	94	127	7780.5
736.5	79	77	78	1495	85	83	84	1477	91	89	90	1459	97	95	96	1441	128	7780.5
735.5	72	71	1503	83	78	77	1485	89	84	83	1467	95	90	89	1449	101	129	7780.5
-4859	1504	-72	222	75	1486	-78	240	81	1468	-84	258	87	1450	-90	276	93	5724	7780.5
750.5	5342	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	7780.5
7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5	7780.5

► Sixth-Type: Striped Magic Squares

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																15561
82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	12497	1632	97	15561
1647	1646	1645	1644	1643	1642	1641	1640	1639	1638	1637	1636	1635	1634	1633	-10768	1631	98	15561
11850	-10121	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	9879	1678	51	1630	99	15561
139	1590	1689	1688	1687	1686	1685	1684	1683	1682	1681	1680	1679	-8150	1677	52	1629	100	15561
138	1591	9536	-7807	2212	15	16	17	18	19	1887	2732	1708	21	1676	53	1628	101	15561
137	1592	81	1648	-483	1714	1713	1712	1711	1710	-158	-1003	1707	22	1675	54	1627	102	15561
136	1593	80	1649	6662	-4933	5172	1	2	3	4	5	1706	23	1674	55	1626	103	15561
135	1594	79	1650	39	1690	-3443	1728	1727	1726	1725	1724	1705	24	1673	56	1625	104	15561
134	1595	78	1651	38	1691	6	7	8	5178	-21	9	1704	25	1672	57	1624	105	15561
133	1596	77	1652	37	1692	1723	1722	1721	-3449	1750	1720	1703	26	1671	58	1623	106	15561
132	1597	76	1653	36	1693	5181	10	-40	11	12	13	1702	27	1670	59	1622	107	15561
131	1598	75	1654	35	1694	-3452	1719	1769	1718	1717	1716	-5019	6748	1669	60	1621	108	15561
130	1599	74	1655	34	1695	-4961	-296	1697	1698	1699	1700	1591	3788	1668	61	1620	109	15561
129	1600	73	1656	35	1694	6690	2025	32	31	30	29	138	-2059	-8029	9758	1619	110	15561
128	1601	72	1657	-7917	1658	1659	1660	1661	1662	1663	1664	1665	1666	1667	1666	1618	111	15561
127	1602	73	1656	9646	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	-10543	12272	15561
126	1603	-10331	1604	1605	1606	1607	1608	1609	1610	1611	1612	1613	1614	1615	1616	1617	1616	15561
127	1602	12060	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	113	15561
15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																15561	
	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	14048	96	97	15561
	1648	1647	1646	1645	1644	1643	1642	1641	1640	1639	1638	1637	1636	1635	1634	-12319	1633	1632	15561
	10387	-8658	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	11518	50	51	1631	98	15561
	138	1591	1690	1689	1688	1687	1686	1685	1684	1683	1682	1681	1680	-9789	1679	1678	1630	99	15561
	137	1592	7961	-6232	2212	14	15	16	17	18	19	4427	20	1887	1677	52	1629	100	15561
	136	1593	80	1649	-483	1715	1714	1713	1712	1711	1710	-2698	1709	-158	1676	53	1628	101	15561
	135	1594	79	1650	5007	-3278	1	1728	4	1725	7	1722	1707	22	1675	54	1627	102	15561
	134	1595	78	1651	38	1691	2	1727	3443	-1714	8	1721	1706	23	1674	55	1626	103	15561
	133	1596	77	1652	37	1692	3	1726	5	1724	3434	-1705	1705	24	1673	56	1625	104	15561
	132	1597	76	1653	36	1693	3452	-1723	6	1723	9	1720	1704	25	1672	57	1624	105	15561
	131	1598	75	1654	35	1694	1721	1719	1718	-3403	1717	1715	1703	26	1671	58	1623	106	15561
	130	1599	74	1655	34	1695	8	10	11	5132	12	14	-3338	5067	1670	59	1622	107	15561
	129	1600	73	1656	1571	-296	-6505	1697	1698	1699	1700	1701	1591	3789	1669	60	1621	108	15561
	128	1601	72	1657	158	2025	8234	32	31	30	29	28	138	-2060	-6412	8141	1620	109	15561
	127	1602	1659	1658	-9516	1659	1660	1661	1662	1663	1664	1665	1666	1667	1668	1667	1619	110	15561
	126	1603	70	71	11245	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	-9022	10751	15561
	1605	1604	-11826	1605	1606	1607	1608	1609	1610	1611	1612	1613	1614	1615	1616	1617	1618	1617	15561
	124	125	13555	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	112	15561
	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																15561	
	3454	1	2	1	5	1724	1718	11	1708	21	1694	35	1676	53	1654	75	1628	101	15561
	-1725	1728	1727	1728	6	1723	1717	12	1707	22	1693	36	1675	54	1653	76	1627	102	15561
	3	4	-1	3452	7	1722	1716	13	1706	23	1692	37	1674	55	1652	77	1626	103	15561
	1726	1725	1730	-1723	3440	-1711	1715	14	1705	24	1691	38	1673	56	1651	78	1625	104	15561
	5175	1721	1720	-6867	1719	1719	1714	15	1704	25	1690	39	1672	57	1650	79	1624	105	15561
	-3446	8	9	8596	10	10	-3393	5122	1703	26	1689	40	1671	58	1649	80	1623	106	15561
	-3442	1713	1712	1711	1710	94	1709	1709	1702	27	1688	41	1670	59	1648	81	1622	107	15561
	5171	16	17	18	19	1635	20	20	-5019	6748	1687	42	1669	60	1647	82	1621	108	15561
	1698	1701	1700	1699	-483	1697	-158	-2599	1695	1695	1686	43	1668	61	1646	83	1620	109	15561
	31	28	29	30	2212	32	1887	4328	34	34	-6565	8294	1667	62	1645	84	1619	110	15561
	-7022	-296	1684	1683	1682	1681	1680	1679	1591	2658	1677	1677	1666	63	1644	85	1618	111	15561
	8751	2025	45	46	47	48	49	50	138	-929	52	52	-8007	9736	1643	86	1617	112	15561
	3841	1665	1664	1663	1662	1661	1660	1659	1658	1657	1656	-11653	1655	1655	1642	87	1616	113	15561
	-2112	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	13382	74	74	-9321	11050	1615	114	15561
	-7526	1641	1640	1639	1638	1637	1636	1635	1634	1633	1632	1631	1630	-1526	1629	1629	1614	115	15561
	9255	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	3255	100	100	-10483	12212	15561
	1606	1613	1612	1611	1610	1609	1608	1607	1606	1605	1604	1603	1602	1601	1600	-11734	1599	1599	15561
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	13463	130	130	15561
	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561	15561

It is little different from other four examples given above. It is single-digit bordered magic square wither magic square of order 16 is embedded in the inner part. This magic square of order 16 is with 16 equal sums magic squares of order 4. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 1729$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 4.5 \times 1729 = 7780.5$. Here the magic sum of order 18 is with decimal value. In order to avoid this, we can consider the magic sum of order 4 as double of 1729. The last three examples of magic square of order 16 based on **magic rectangles**. The second and third are **double-digit** magic squares, while the third one is **cornered-type** magic square. The width of the strip is always same, i.e., 1729. The change is only in the lengths. The magic sum for all the three magic squares is same, i.e., $S_{18 \times 18} := 15561 = 9 \times 1729$

Above there are 5 examples magic squares of order 18. All 5 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four numbers 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

18 Magic Squares of Order 19

Let's consider following 3 magic squares of order 19 having the magic sum 1729:

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																	1729	
	281	284	287	290	293	296	299	302	305	308	311	314	317	320	323	326	-3309	-147	329	1729
	-99	-102	-105	-108	-111	-114	-117	-120	-123	-126	-129	-132	-135	-138	-141	-144	3491	-150	332	1729
	-5523	5705	143	2212	149	152	155	158	161	164	167	170	173	1887	-4508	3	179	-153	335	1729
	464	-282	39	-2030	33	30	27	24	21	18	15	12	9	-1705	4690	0	182	-156	338	1729
	461	-279	-1961	2143	50	53	56	59	62	65	68	71	335	108	74	-3	185	-159	341	1729
	458	-276	278	-96	132	129	126	123	120	117	114	111	-153	105	77	-6	188	-162	344	1729
	455	-273	275	-93	-223	405	8	11	14	17	405	162	20	102	80	-9	191	-165	347	1729
	452	-270	272	-90	140	42	174	171	168	165	-223	159	23	99	83	-12	194	-168	350	1729
	449	-267	269	-87	137	45	279	-97	-84	177	180	156	26	96	86	-15	197	-171	353	1729
	446	-264	266	-84	134	48	47	135	355	91	-173	153	29	93	89	-18	200	-174	356	1729
	443	-261	263	-81	131	51	44	138	2	5	266	-175	357	90	92	-21	203	-177	359	1729
	440	-258	260	-78	128	54	41	141	-133	144	147	150	147	87	95	-24	206	-180	362	1729
	437	-255	257	-75	125	57	44	138	315	38	35	32	35	39	143	-27	209	-183	365	1729
	434	-252	254	-72	122	60	213	66	69	72	75	78	81	84	81	-30	212	-186	368	1729
	431	-249	251	-69	125	57	-31	116	113	110	107	104	101	98	101	1345	-1163	-189	371	1729
	428	-246	248	-66	5439	-1843	-60	-57	-54	-51	-48	-45	-42	-39	-36	44	-2025	-192	374	1729
	425	-243	251	-69	-5257	2025	242	239	236	233	230	227	224	221	218	138	2207	4259	-4077	1729
	422	-240	4985	-237	-234	-231	-228	-225	-222	-219	-216	-213	-210	-207	-204	-201	-198	-195	-198	1729
	425	-243	-4803	419	416	413	410	407	404	401	398	395	392	389	386	383	380	377	380	1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																	1729
277	280	283	286	289	292	295	298	301	304	307	310	313	316	319	322	-3716	325	328	1729
-95	-98	-101	-104	-107	-110	-113	-116	-119	-122	-125	-128	-131	-134	-137	-140	3898	-143	-146	1729
-4802	4984	139	142	145	148	151	154	157	160	163	166	169	172	-854	175	178	-149	331	1729
460	-278	43	40	37	34	31	28	25	22	19	16	13	10	1036	7	4	-152	334	1729
457	-275	-1604	1786	2212	52	55	58	61	64	67	70	-3598	73	1887	1	181	-155	337	1729
454	-272	274	-92	-2030	130	127	124	121	118	115	112	3780	109	-1705	-2	184	-158	340	1729
451	-269	271	-89	-2029	2211	7	10	13	16	550	19	22	103	79	-5	187	-161	343	1729
448	-266	268	-86	136	46	175	172	169	166	-368	163	160	100	82	-8	190	-164	346	1729
445	-263	265	-83	133	49	184	-2	-86	178	181	145	37	97	85	-11	193	-167	349	1729
442	-260	262	-80	2025	-1843	46	136	358	91	-176	142	40	44	138	-14	196	-170	352	1729
439	-257	259	-77	127	55	43	139	1	4	268	-14	196	91	91	-17	199	-173	355	1729
436	-254	256	-74	124	58	160	157	-278	154	151	148	145	88	94	-20	202	-176	358	1729
433	-251	253	-71	121	61	22	25	460	28	31	34	37	114	68	-23	205	-179	361	1729
430	-248	250	-68	1878	64	-3718	67	70	73	76	79	82	85	2245	-26	208	-182	364	1729
427	-245	247	-65	-1696	118	3900	115	112	109	106	103	100	97	-2063	1126	-944	-185	367	1729
424	-242	-59	-62	2002	-59	-56	-53	-50	-47	-44	-41	-38	-35	-32	-29	-32	-188	370	1729
421	-239	241	244	-1820	241	238	235	232	229	226	223	220	217	214	211	214	3724	-3542	1729
-233	-236	5572	-233	-230	-227	-224	-221	-218	-215	-212	-209	-206	-203	-200	-197	-194	-191	-194	1729
415	418	-5390	415	412	409	406	403	400	397	394	391	388	385	382	379	376	373	376	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

19	mgc	19x19 Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																	1729
-88	180	181	179	3	175	7	167	15	155	27	139	43	119	63	95	87	67	115	1729
360	91	-178	178	4	174	8	166	16	154	28	138	44	118	64	94	88	66	116	1729
1	2	270	-84	266	173	9	165	17	153	29	137	45	117	65	93	89	65	117	1729
355	177	-429	176	176	172	10	164	18	152	30	136	46	116	66	92	90	64	118	1729
-173	5	611	6	6	-239	421	163	19	151	31	135	47	115	67	91	91	63	119	1729
950	171	170	169	-1159	168	168	162	20	150	32	134	48	114	68	90	92	62	120	1729
-768	11	12	13	1341	14	14	-350	532	149	33	133	49	113	69	89	93	61	121	1729
-1936	-2030	160	159	158	157	7561	-1705	-1705	148	34	132	50	112	70	88	94	60	122	1729
2118	2212	22	23	24	25	-7379	1887	1887	-393	575	131	51	111	71	87	95	59	123	1729
1801	147	146	145	144	143	142	141	-2088	140	140	130	52	110	72	86	96	58	124	1729
-1619	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	2270	42	42	-344	526	109	73	85	97	57	125	1729
-1925	-1843	128	127	126	125	124	44	122	121	3794	120	120	108	74	84	98	56	126	1729
2107	2025	54	55	56	57	58	138	60	61	-3612	62	62	-179	361	83	99	55	127	1729
-8723	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	97	8774	96	96	82	100	54	128	1729
8905	75	76	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	-8592	86	86	126	56	53	129	1729
1870	81	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	70	69	-1434	68	68	52	130	1729
-1688	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	1616	114	114	595	-413	1729
2677	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	-1680	36	36	1729
-2495	131	132	133	134	135	136	137	138	139	140	141	142	143	144	145	1862	146	146	1729
1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729

• Details

Above there are 3 examples magic squares of order 19 with magic sum 1729. All 3 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four numbers 2212,

1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on *reduced-entry algebraic* magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

19 Magic Squares of Order 20

Below are few examples of magic squares of order 20 having the details of S. Ramanujan.

► First-Type: Striped Magic Squares

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja				https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	8645					
	1	1726	-1	3	7	1720	-7	9	13	1714	-13	15	19	1708	-19	21	25	1702	-25	27	8645
	6	4	5	1714	12	10	11	1696	18	16	17	1678	24	22	23	1660	30	28	29	1642	8645
	-1	-2	1722	10	5	4	1704	16	11	10	1686	22	17	16	1668	28	23	22	1650	34	8645
	1723	1	3	2	1705	-5	21	8	1687	-11	39	14	1669	-17	57	20	1651	-23	75	26	8645
	31	1696	-2210	2212	37	1690	-37	39	43	1684	-43	45	49	1678	-49	51	1887	-160	-55	57	8645
	36	34	35	1624	42	40	41	1606	48	46	47	1588	54	52	53	1570	60	58	59	1552	8645
	2208	28	1632	-2139	35	34	1614	46	41	40	1596	52	47	46	1578	58	53	1884	-272	64	8645
	-546	-29	2272	32	1615	-35	111	38	1597	-41	129	44	1579	-47	147	50	-271	-53	1997	56	8645
	61	1666	-61	63	67	1660	-67	69	73	1654	-73	75	79	1648	-79	81	85	1642	-85	87	8645
	66	64	65	1534	72	70	71	1516	78	76	77	1498	84	82	83	1480	90	88	89	1462	8645
	59	58	1542	70	65	64	1524	76	71	70	1506	82	77	76	1488	88	83	82	1470	94	8645
	1543	-59	183	62	1525	-65	201	68	1507	-71	219	74	1489	-77	237	80	1471	-83	255	86	8645
	91	1636	-2023	2025	97	1630	-97	99	103	1624	-103	105	109	1618	-109	111	138	1589	-115	117	8645
	96	94	95	1444	102	100	101	1426	108	106	107	1408	114	112	113	1390	120	118	119	1372	8645
	2021	88	1452	-1832	95	94	1434	106	101	100	1416	112	107	106	1398	118	113	135	1357	124	8645
	-479	-89	2205	92	1435	-95	291	98	1417	-101	309	104	1399	-107	327	110	1358	-113	368	116	8645
	121	1606	-121	123	127	1600	-127	129	133	1594	-133	135	139	1588	-139	141	145	1582	-145	147	8645
	126	124	125	1354	132	130	131	1336	138	136	137	1318	144	142	143	1300	150	148	149	1282	8645
	119	118	1362	130	125	124	1344	136	131	130	1326	142	137	136	1308	148	143	142	1290	154	8645
	1363	-119	363	122	1345	-125	381	128	1327	-131	399	134	1309	-137	417	140	1291	-143	435	146	8645
	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645	8645

The above magic square is composed of equal sums magic squares of order 4. The sum of each magic square of order 4 is 1729. Thus, the magic sum of order 20 is given as $S_{20 \times 20} := 8645 = 5 \times 1729$. See below the sum of magic squares of order 4:

4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729								
	1	1726	-1	3	1729	7	1720	-7	9	1729	13	1714	-13	15	1729	19	1708	-19	21	1729	25	1702	-25	27	1729		
	6	4	5	1714	1729	12	10	11	1696	1729	18	16	17	1678	1729	24	22	23	1660	1729	30	28	29	1642	1729		
	-1	-2	1722	10	1729	5	4	1704	16	1729	11	10	1686	22	1729	17	16	1668	28	1729	23	22	1650	34	1729		
	1723	1	3	2	1729	1705	-5	21	8	1729	1687	-11	39	14	1729	1669	-17	57	20	1729	1651	-23	75	26	1729		
4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
	31	1696	-2210	2212	1729	37	1690	-37	39	1729	43	1684	-43	45	1729	49	1678	-49	51	1729	1887	-160	-55	57	1729		
	36	34	35	1624	1729	42	40	41	1606	1729	48	46	47	1588	1729	54	52	53	1570	1729	60	58	59	1552	1729		
	2208	28	1632	-2139	1729	35	34	1614	46	1729	41	40	1596	52	1729	47	46	1578	58	1729	53	1884	-272	64	1729		
	-546	-29	2272	32	1729	1615	-35	111	38	1729	1597	-41	129	44	1729	1579	-47	147	50	1729	-271	-53	1997	56	1729		
4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729
	61	1666	-61	63	1729	67	1660	-67	69	1729	73	1654	-73	75	1729	79	1648	-79	81	1729	85	1642	-85	87	1729		
	66	64	65	1534	1729	72	70	71	1516	1729	78	76	77	1498	1729	84	82	83	1480	1729	90	88	89	1462	1729		
	59	58	1542	70	1729	65	64	1524	76	1729	71	70	1506	82	1729	77	76	1488	88	1729	83	82	1470	94	1729		
	1543	-59	183	62	1729	1525	-65	201	68	1729	1507	-71	219	74	1729	1489	-77	237	80	1729	1471	-83	255	86	1729		
4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		
	91	1636	-2023	2025	1729	97	1630	-97	99	1729	103	1624	-103	105	1729	109	1618	-109	111	1729	138	1589	-115	117	1729		
	96	94	95	1444	1729	102	100	101	1426	1729	108	106	107	1408	1729	114	112	113	1390	1729	120	118	119	1372	1729		
	2021	88	1452	-1832	1729	95	94	1434	106	1729	101	100	1416	112	1729	107	106	1398	118	1729	113	135	1357	124	1729		
	-479	-89	2205	92	1729	1435	-95	291	98	1729	1417	-101	309	104	1729	1399	-107	327	110	1729	1358	-113	368	116	1729		
4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729
	121	1606	-121	123	1729	127	1600	-127	129	1729	133	1594	-133	135	1729	139	1588	-139	141	1729	145	1582	-145	147	1729		
	126	124	125	1354	1729	132	130	131	1336	1729	138	136	137	1318	1729	144	142	143	1300	1729	150	148	149	1282	1729		
	119	118	1362	130	1729	125	124	1344	136	1729	131	130	1326	142	1729	137	136	1308	148	1729	143	142	1290	154	1729		
	1363	-119	363	122	1729	1345	-125	381	128	1729	1327	-131	399	134	1729	1309	-137	417	140	1729	1291	-143	435	146	1729		
4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729	4	mgc		1729
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		

► Second-Type: Striped Magic Squares

20	mgc	20x20	Inder J. Taneja	https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	6916														
	2	3	1715	4	5	10	11	1683	12	13	18	19	1651	20	21	26	27	1619	28	29	6916	
	14	6	-7	7	1709	22	14	1	15	1677	30	22	9	23	1645	38	30	17	31	1613	6916	
	-2	1713	8	16	-6	6	1681	16	24	2	14	1649	24	32	10	22	1617	32	40	18	6916	
	10	4	-1	1704	12	18	12	7	1672	20	26	20	15	1640	28	34	28	23	1608	36	6916	
	1705	3	14	-2	9	1673	11	22	6	17	1641	19	30	14	25	1609	27	38	22	33	6916	
	34	35	-586	34	2212	42	43	1555	44	45	50	51	1523	52	53	1887	59	-338	60	61	6916	
	46	38	2198	39	-592	54	46	33	47	1549	62	54	41	55	1517	70	62	1878	63	-344	6916	
	2203	-588	40	50	24	38	1553	48	56	34	46	1521	56	64	42	54	-340	64	72	1879	6916	
	44	36	29	1576	44	50	44	39	1544	52	58	52	47	1512	60	66	1889	55	-349	68	6916	
	-598	2208	48	30	41	1545	43	54	38	49	1513	51	62	46	57	-348	59	70	1883	65	6916	
	66	67	1459	68	69	74	75	1429	74	77	82	83	1395	84	85	90	91	1363	92	93	6916	
	78	70	57	71	1453	86	78	63	79	1423	94	86	73	87	1389	102	94	81	95	1357	6916	
	62	1457	72	80	58	68	1427	80	90	64	78	1393	88	96	74	86	1361	96	104	82	6916	
	74	68	63	1448	76	84	76	69	1416	84	90	84	79	1384	92	98	92	87	1352	100	6916	
	1449	67	78	62	73	1417	73	88	70	81	1385	83	94	78	89	1353	91	102	86	97	6916	
	98	99	-593	100	2025	106	107	1299	108	109	114	115	1269	114	117	138	123	1219	124	125	6916	
	110	102	2013	103	-599	118	110	97	111	1293	126	118	103	119	1263	134	126	129	127	1213	6916	
	2018	-595	104	112	90	102	1297	112	120	98	108	1267	120	130	104	118	1217	128	136	130	6916	
	106	100	95	1320	108	114	108	103	1288	116	124	116	109	1256	124	130	140	119	1208	132	6916	
	-603	2023	110	94	105	1289	107	118	102	113	1257	113	128	110	121	1209	123	134	134	129	6916	
	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916	6916

The above magic square is compose of equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. The sum of each magic square of order 5 is 1729. Thus, the magic sum of order 20 is given as $S_{20 \times 20} := 6916 = 4 \times 1729$. See below the magic sums of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5:

	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729
1729	2	3	1715	4	5	1729	1729	10	11	1683	12	13	1729	1729	18	19	1651	20	21	1729	1729	26	27	1619	28	29	1729	1729		
1729	14	6	-7	7	1709	1729	1729	22	14	1	15	1677	1729	1729	30	22	9	23	1645	1729	1729	38	30	17	31	1613	1729	1729		
1729	-2	1713	8	16	-6	1729	1729	6	1681	16	24	2	1729	1729	14	1649	24	32	10	1729	1729	22	1617	32	40	18	1729	1729		
1729	10	4	-1	1704	12	1729	1729	18	12	7	1672	20	1729	1729	26	20	15	1640	28	1729	1729	34	28	23	1608	36	1729	1729		
	1705	3	14	-2	9	1729		1673	11	22	6	17	1729		1641	19	30	14	25	1729		1609	27	38	22	33	1729	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
1729	34	35	-586	34	2212	1729	1729	42	43	1555	44	45	1729	1729	50	51	1523	52	53	1729	1729	1887	59	-338	60	61	1729	1729		
1729	46	38	2198	39	-592	1729	1729	54	46	33	47	1549	1729	1729	62	54	41	55	1517	1729	1729	70	62	1878	63	-344	1729	1729		
1729	2203	-588	40	50	24	1729	1729	38	1553	48	56	34	1729	1729	46	1521	56	64	42	1729	1729	54	-340	64	72	1879	1729	1729		
1729	44	36	29	1576	44	1729	1729	50	44	39	1544	52	1729	1729	58	52	47	1512	60	1729	1729	66	1889	55	-349	68	1729	1729		
	-598	2208	48	30	41	1729		1545	43	54	38	49	1729		1513	51	62	46	57	1729		-348	59	70	1883	65	1729	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
1729	66	67	1459	68	69	1729	1729	74	75	1429	74	77	1729	1729	82	83	1395	84	85	1729	1729	90	91	1363	92	93	1729	1729		
1729	78	70	57	71	1453	1729	1729	86	78	63	79	1423	1729	1729	94	86	73	87	1389	1729	1729	102	94	81	95	1357	1729	1729		
1729	62	1457	72	80	58	1729	1729	68	1427	80	90	64	1729	1729	78	1393	88	96	74	1729	1729	86	1361	96	104	82	1729	1729		
1729	74	68	63	1448	76	1729	1729	84	76	69	1416	84	1729	1729	90	84	79	1384	92	1729	1729	98	92	87	1352	100	1729	1729		
	1449	67	78	62	73	1729		1417	73	88	70	81	1729		1385	83	94	78	89	1729		1353	91	102	86	97	1729	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
	pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		pan	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	
1729	98	99	-593	100	2025	1729	1729	106	107	1299	108	109	1729	1729	114	115	1269	114	117	1729	1729	138	123	1219	124	125	1729	1729		
1729	110	102	2013	103	-599	1729	1729	118	110	97	111	1293	1729	1729	126	118	103	119	1263	1729	1729	134	126	129	127	1213	1729	1729		
1729	2018	-595	104	112	90	1729	1729	102	1297	112	120	98	1729	1729	108	1267	120	130	104	1729	1729	118	1217	128	136	130	1729	1729		
1729	106	100	95	1320	108	1729	1729	114	108	103	1288	116	1729	1729	124	116	109	1256	124	1729	1729	130	140	119	1208	132	1729	1729		
	-603	2023	110	94	105	1729		1289	107	118	102	113	1729		1257	113	128	110	121	1729		1209	123	134	134	129	1729	1729		
	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729		1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	1729	

► **Third-Type: Striped Magic Squares**

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		17290
109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	13572	1603	126	17290
1620	1619	1618	1617	1616	1615	1614	1613	1612	1611	1610	1609	1608	1607	1606	1605	1604	-11843	1602	127	17290
12737	-11008	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	11258	1657	72	1601	128	17290
174	1555	1670	1669	1668	1667	1666	1665	1664	1663	1662	1661	1660	1659	1658	-9529	1656	73	1600	129	17290
173	1556	10775	-9046	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	8384	1695	34	1655	74	1599	130	17290
172	1557	108	1621	1704	1703	1702	1701	1700	1699	1698	1697	1696	-6655	1694	35	1654	75	1598	131	17290
171	1558	107	1622	8157	-6428	2212	8	9	10	1887	1061	1717	12	1693	36	1653	76	1597	132	17290
170	1559	106	1623	58	1671	-483	1721	1720	1719	-158	668	1716	13	1692	37	1652	77	1596	133	17290
169	1560	105	1624	57	1672	5075	-3346	3454	1	2	1	1715	14	1691	38	1651	78	1595	134	17290
168	1561	104	1625	56	1673	24	1705	-1725	1728	1727	1728	1714	15	1690	39	1650	79	1594	135	17290
167	1562	103	1626	55	1674	23	1706	3	4	-1	3452	1713	16	1689	40	1649	80	1593	136	17290
166	1563	102	1627	54	1675	22	1707	1726	1725	1730	-1723	-3388	5117	1688	41	1648	81	1592	137	17290
165	1564	101	1628	53	1676	21	1708	-3324	-296	1710	1711	1591	3795	1687	42	1647	82	1591	138	17290
164	1565	100	1629	52	1677	22	1707	5053	2025	19	18	138	-2066	-6574	8303	1646	83	1590	139	17290
163	1566	99	1630	51	1678	-6500	1679	1680	1681	1682	1683	1684	1685	1686	1685	1645	84	1589	140	17290
162	1567	98	1631	52	1677	8229	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	44	-9360	11089	1588	141	17290
161	1568	97	1632	-9202	1633	1634	1635	1636	1637	1638	1639	1640	1641	1642	1643	1644	1643	1587	142	17290
160	1569	98	1631	10931	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	86	-11554	13283	17290
159	1570	-11280	1571	1572	1573	1574	1575	1576	1577	1578	1579	1580	1581	1582	1583	1584	1585	1586	1585	17290
160	1569	13009	158	157	156	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	144	17290
17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT																		17290
106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	114	115	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	15105	123	124	17290
1623	1622	1621	1620	1619	1618	1617	1616	1615	1614	1613	1612	1611	1610	1609	1608	1607	-13376	1606	1605	17290
11372	-9643	57	58	59	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	12874	69	70	1604	125	17290
171	1558	1672	1671	1670	1669	1668	1667	1666	1665	1664	1663	1662	1661	1660	-11145	1660	1659	1603	126	17290
170	1559	9274	-7545	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	10066	32	33	1658	71	1602	127	17290
169	1560	105	1624	1706	1705	1704	1703	1702	1701	1700	1699	1698	-8337	1697	1696	1657	72	1601	128	17290
168	1561	104	1625	6545	-4816	2212	6	7	8	9	2777	10	1887	1695	34	1656	73	1600	129	17290
167	1562	103	1626	56	1673	-483	1723	1722	1721	1720	-1048	1719	-158	1694	35	1655	74	1599	130	17290
166	1563	102	1627	55	1674	3395	-1666	3454	-1725	3	1726	1717	12	1693	36	1654	75	1598	131	17290
165	1564	101	1628	54	1675	22	1707	1	1728	4	1725	1716	13	1692	37	1653	76	1597	132	17290
164	1565	100	1629	53	1676	21	1708	2	1727	-1	1730	1715	14	1691	38	1652	77	1596	133	17290
163	1566	99	1630	52	1677	20	1709	1	1728	3452	-1723	-1690	3419	1690	39	1651	78	1595	134	17290
162	1567	98	1631	51	1678	3902	2025	-1544	18	17	16	138	2344	1689	40	1650	79	1594	135	17290
161	1568	97	1632	50	1679	-2173	-296	3273	1711	1712	1713	1591	-615	-4928	6657	1649	80	1593	136	17290
160	1569	96	1633	1681	1680	-8150	1681	1682	1683	1684	1685	1686	1687	1688	1687	1648	81	1592	137	17290
159	1570	95	1634	48	49	9879	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	42	-7809	9538	1591	138	17290
158	1571	1636	1635	-10783	1636	1637	1638	1639	1640	1641	1642	1643	1644	1645	1646	1647	1646	1590	139	17290
157	1572	93	94	12512	93	92	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	83	-10123	11852	17290
1574	1573	-12749	1574	1575	1576	1577	1578	1579	1580	1581	1582	1583	1584	1585	1586	1587	1588	1589	1588	17290
155	156	14478	155	154	153	152	151	150	149	148	147	146	145	144	143	142	141	140	141	17290
17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290

20	mgc	20x20 Inder J. Taneja																https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT				17290
	3454	1	2	1	5	1724	1718	11	1708	21	1694	35	1676	53	1654	75	1628	101	1598	131	17290					
	-1725	1728	1727	1728	6	1723	1717	12	1707	22	1693	36	1675	54	1653	76	1627	102	1597	132	17290					
	3	4	-1	3452	7	1722	1716	13	1706	23	1692	37	1674	55	1652	77	1626	103	1596	133	17290					
	1726	1725	1730	-1723	3440	-1711	1715	14	1705	24	1691	38	1673	56	1651	78	1625	104	1595	134	17290					
	5175	1721	1720	-6867	1719	1719	1714	15	1704	25	1690	39	1672	57	1650	79	1624	105	1594	135	17290					
	-3446	8	9	8596	10	10	-3393	5122	1703	26	1689	40	1671	58	1649	80	1623	106	1593	136	17290					
	-3442	1713	1712	1711	1710	94	1709	1709	1702	27	1688	41	1670	59	1648	81	1622	107	1592	137	17290					
	5171	16	17	18	19	1635	20	20	-5019	6748	1687	42	1669	60	1647	82	1621	108	1591	138	17290					
	1698	1701	1700	1699	1698	1697	1696	-6634	1695	1695	1686	43	1668	61	1646	83	1620	109	1590	139	17290					
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	8363	34	34	-6565	8294	1667	62	1645	84	1619	110	1589	140	17290					
	-7209	-483	4785	1683	1684	1681	1680	1679	1678	-158	1677	1677	1666	63	1644	85	1618	111	1588	141	17290					
	8938	2212	-3056	46	45	48	49	50	51	1887	52	52	-8007	9736	1643	86	1617	112	1587	142	17290					
	-1441	1665	1664	1663	1662	1661	1660	1659	1658	1657	1656	-6371	1655	1655	1642	87	1616	113	1586	143	17290					
	3170	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	8100	74	74	-9321	11050	1615	114	1585	144	17290					
	-13512	-296	1640	1639	1638	1637	1636	1635	1634	1633	1632	1631	1591	6436	1629	1629	1614	115	1584	145	17290					
	15241	2025	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	138	-4707	100	100	-10483	12212	1583	146	17290					
	1606	1613	1612	1611	1610	1609	1608	1607	1606	1605	1604	1603	1602	1601	1600	-11734	1599	1599	1582	147	17290					
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	13463	130	130	-11469	13198	17290					
	-8513	1581	1580	1579	1578	1577	1576	1575	1574	1573	1572	1571	1570	1569	1568	1567	1566	-2503	1565	1565	17290					
	10242	148	149	150	151	152	153	154	155	156	157	158	159	160	161	162	163	4232	164	164	17290					
	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290	17290					

It is little different from other four examples given above. It is single-digit bordered magic square wither magic square of order 20 is embedded in the inner part. This magic square of order 16 is with 16 equal sums magic squares of order 4. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 1729$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 4.5 \times 1729 = 7780.5$. Here the magic sum of order 18 is with decimal value. In order de avoid this, we can consider the magic sum of order 4 as double of 1729.

The last three example sof magic square of order 20 are based on **magic rectangles**. The second and third are **double-digit** magic squares, while the third one is **cornered-type** magic square. The the width of the strip is always same, i.e., 1729. The change is only in the lengths. The magic sum for all the three magic square is same, i.e., $S_{20 \times 20} := 17290 = 10 \times 1729$

Above there are 5 examples magic squares of order 20. All 5 examples use special entries, namely the date of birth of S. Ramanujan (22.12.1887) and his 138th anniversary on 22.12.2025. These contain the four numbers 2212, 1887, 2025, and 138. The construction of these magic squares is based on **reduced-entry algebraic** magic squares recently studied by the author [26, 27]

20 Author's Contributions to Recreating Numbers and Magic Squares

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 1. <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 1. <https://indertaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>
 2. <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>

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• Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Dates and Days of the Year

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- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 10 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 21, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15481738>.
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• Reduced Entries Algebraic Magic Squares: Different Styles

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